

DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH STAGGERED
FINS ABSORBER AND NANO-PCM INTEGRATED
STORAGE SYSTEM

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AND NANO-PCM INTEGRATED STORAGE SYSTEM

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PEMANAS UDARA SURIA DUA LALUAN DENGAN PENYERAP SIRIP
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TESIS YANG DIKEMUKAKAN UNTUK MEMPEROLEH
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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis is my own except for quotations and summaries which have been duly acknowledged.

09 August 2023

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ABSTRAK

Pemanas suria digunakan untuk menukar radiasi suria yang terpapar menjadi tenaga terma. Pemanas udara suria digunakan secara meluas kerana penggunaan bahan yang minima, reka bentuk yang lebih mudah, penyelenggaraan yang kurang, masalah korosi yang kurang, dan masalah kebocoran yang sedikit. Kajian ini menyajikan penyelidikan matematik dan eksperimen terhadap pemanas udara suria dua hala (DP-SAH) dengan sirip berperingkat dan PCM (Bahan Bertukar Fasa) dipertingkatkan nano. DP-SAH dengan penyerap sirip berperingkat dan kapsul silinder PCM yang dipertingkatkan nano telah dibina dan diuji dalam simulator suria dalaman. DP-SAH terdiri daripada penutup kaca boleh laras, plat penyerap dengan sirip belakang yang disambungkan, kapsul PCM yang dipertingkatkan nano dan plat belakang. Kapsul PCM yang dipertingkatkan bahan nano, menyerap sinaran dan menyimpan tenaga haba dan boleh dinyahcas kemudian apabila tiada sinaran suria. Dimensi DP-SAH adalah 1.0 m panjang dan 0.3m lebar. Laluan atas boleh dilaraskan dengan kedalaman antara 3 cm hingga 10 cm. Saluran bawah ditetapkan pada 10 cm. Bilangan sirip dan kapsul PCM yang dipertingkatkan nano adalah 23. Nanopartikel yang digunakan dalam kapsul adalah silikon karbida (SiC) dan PCM adalah lilin parafin dengan pecahan isipadu kira-kira 0.5%. Lima persamaan keseimbangan tenaga keadaan mantap telah dibangunkan untuk dua aliran udara yang terdiri daripada penutup kaca, plat penyerap, sirip, kapsul PCM yang dipertingkatkan nano, dan plat belakang. Model matematik telah diselesaikan menggunakan kaedah penyongsangan matriks dalam pengaturcaraan MATLAB untuk meramalkan perolehan tenaga yang berguna, kecekapan terma (η_{en}), kecekapan termo-hidraulik (η_{th}), kecekapan eksergi (η_{ex}) dan potensi peningkatan (IP), suhu udara keluar (T_o) dan nyahcas. masa (tdis). Simulator suria mengemas DP-SAH sehingga nano-PCM di dalam kapsul silinder menjadi fasa cecair dan di bawah proses (mengeras) nyahcas. Sinaran suria diukur menggunakan TES 132 piranometer. Suhu di lokasi terpilih dalam DP-SAH telah diukur menggunakan termokopel jenis K. Udara melalui DP-SAH menggunakan blower elektrik boleh dikawal pada pelbagai halaju. Kajian eksperimen dan teori telah dijalankan di bawah julat tahap sinaran suria 400 – 1000 W/m² dan kadar aliran jisim antara 0.01 – 0.05 kg/s. Kecekapan terma DP-SAH adalah 72–80%, kecekapan termo-hidraulik adalah 64 –76%, kecekapan eksergi adalah 13–20 % dan potensi penambahbaikan 84.6–177 W untuk tahap sinaran suria berjulat dari 400 – 1000 W/m² pada kadar aliran jisim maksimum 0.05 kg/s. Suhu keluar tertinggi dicatatkan pada aras sinaran suria 1000 W/m² dan pada kadar aliran jisim 0.01 kg/s ialah 43°C. Model matematik telah dibandingkan dan disahkan dengan keputusan eksperimen dan menunjukkan ketekalan yang baik dan persetujuan yang rapat. Model pengoptimuman ekonomi telah dibangunkan untuk kajian kos-faedah yang akan memberi pengguna/pereka bentuk pilihan untuk memilih PCM dipertingkatkan nano yang sesuai dan reka bentuk optimum yang diperlukan.

ABSTRACT

Solar heaters are employed to convert incident solar radiation into thermal energy. Solar air heaters are extensively used due minimal use of materials, a simpler design, less maintenance, less corrosion and few leakage problems. This study presents mathematical and experimental investigations of a double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered fins and nano-enhanced PCM (Phase Change Material). The DP-SAH with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM cylindrical capsules were built and tested in an indoor solar simulator. The DP-SAH consists of an adjustable glass cover, an absorber plate with attached back fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, and a back plate. The nano-enhanced PCM capsules absorb the radiation and store the thermal energy and can be discharged as demanded when there is no solar radiation. The DP-SAH dimensions were 1.0 m in length and 0.3m in width. The upper channel can be adjusted to between 3 cm to 10 cm in depth. The lower channel was fixed at 10 cm. The number of fins and nano-enhanced PCM capsules was 23. The used nanoparticle in the capsules was silicon carbide (SiC) and PCM is Paraffin wax with a volume fraction of about 0.5%. Five equations for the steady-state energy equilibrium were developed for two air streams consisting of the glass cover, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, and the back plate. The mathematical model was solved using the matrix inversion method in MATLAB programming to predict useful energy gain, thermal efficiency (η_{en}), thermo-hydraulic efficiency (η_{th}), exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) and improvement potential (IP), outlet air temperature (T_o) and discharging time (t_{dis}). The solar simulator charges the DP-SAH until the nano-PCM inside the cylindrical capsules becomes a liquid phase and under the discharging (solidify) process. The solar irradiance was measured using TES 132 pyranometer. The temperature at selected locations in the DP-SAH has been measured using the K-type thermocouples. The air passed through the DP-SAH using an electrical blower can be controlled at various velocities. Experimental and theoretical studies were conducted under solar irradiance levels range of 400 – 1000 W/m² and mass flow rates between 0.01– 0.05 kg/s. The thermal efficiency of the DP-SAH were 72–80 %, thermo-hydraulic efficiency were 64 –76%, the exergy efficiency were 13–20 % and the improvement potential of 84.6–177 W for solar irradiance levels range from 400 – 1000 W/m² at a maximum mass flow rate 0.05 kg/s. The highest outlet temperature recorded at solar irradiance level of 1000 W/m² and at mass flow rate 0.01 kg/s was 43 °C. The mathematical model was compared and validated with experimental results and show good consistency and close agreement. An economic optimization model was developed for the cost-benefit study that will give the user/designer the choice to select the suitable nano-enhanced PCM and the optimum design needed.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

<i>AC</i>	Annual cost (RM)
<i>ATEG</i>	Annual thermal energy gain (kWh)
<i>APC</i>	Annual pumping cost (RM)
<i>ASV</i>	Annual salvage value (RM)
<i>ACC</i>	Annual capital cost (RM)
<i>AMC</i>	Annual maintenance cost (RM)
<i>CI</i>	Capital investment (RM)
<i>CE</i>	Cost of electricity (RM/kWh)
<i>CRF</i>	Capital recovery factor
<i>DTES</i>	Daily thermal energy stored (kWh)
<i>DP-SAH</i>	Double-pass solar air heater
<i>EDS</i>	Electron Dispersion Spectroscopy
<i>EDX</i>	Electron Dispersion X-ray
<i>FESEM</i>	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope
<i>HRF</i>	Heater recovery factor
<i>HAC</i>	Heater array cost (RM/m ²)
<i>HSSC</i>	Heater support structure cost (RM/m ²)
<i>HFC</i>	Heater fabrication cost (RM/m ²)
<i>IP</i>	Improvement potential (W)
<i>MC</i>	Maintenance cost (RM)
<i>PCM</i>	Phase change material
<i>RMSE</i>	Root mean square error
<i>RM</i>	Malaysian Ringgit
<i>SAH</i>	Solar Air heater
<i>SiC</i>	Silicon Carbide
<i>SV</i>	Salvage value (RM)
<i>SFF</i>	Salvage fund factor
<i>SSE</i>	Sum of square error
<i>XRD</i>	X-Ray Diffraction

LIST OF SYMBOLS

A	Area (m^2)
A_1	Area of surface 1 (m^2)
A_2	Area of surface 2 (m^2)
A_{ap}	Passage area of the air ($L_H \times d$)
A_H	Area of the proposed heater ($L_H \times W_H$) (m^2)
A_f	Channel flow area ($d \times W_H$) (m^2)
A_p	Area of absorber plate (m^2)
A_{fin}	The sectional area of fin (m^2)
A_{Nano}	Surface area of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m^2)
c_{p-air}	Constant pressure-specific heat of the air (J/kg.K)
c_{v-air}	Constant volume-specific heat of the air (J/kg.K)
c_{p-Nano}	Constant pressure - specific heat of nanoparticle (J/kg.K)
d	Depth of the channel (m)
d_1	Depth of the upper channel (m)
d_2	Depth of the lower channel (m)
D_h	Hydraulic diameter (m)
$\dot{E}x_d$	Exergy destruction (W)
$\dot{E}x_i$	Exergy input of solar irradiance (W)
$\dot{E}x_{o,p}$	Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
$\dot{E}x_o$	Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
$\dot{E}x_w$	Exergy of work (W)
f	Friction factor
F_{12}	View factor from surface 1 to surface 2
h	Heat transfer coefficient ($W/m^2.K$)
h_w	Heat transfer coefficient due to wind ($W/m^2.K$)
h_1	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ($W/m^2.K$)
h_2	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ($W/m^2.K$)
h_3	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ($W/m^2.K$)

h_4	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the lower channel and fins ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_5	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the lower channel and nano-enhanced PCM capsules ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_6	Convective heat transfer coefficient between air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_r	Radiative heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_{rgs}	Radiative heat transfer coefficient between glass cover and sky ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_{rpg}	Radiative heat transfer coefficient between absorber plate and glass cover ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
h_{rpb}	Radiative heat transfer coefficient between absorber plate and back plate ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
H_{fin}	Height of fin
H_L	Latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM (J/kg)
I_T	Incident solar irradiance on the proposed heater (W/m^2)
k_{air}	Thermal conductivity of the air ($\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{k}$)
k_p	Thermal conductivity of absorber plate ($\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{k}$)
L_H	Length of the proposed heater (m)
L_{fin}	Length of fin (m)
L_{Nano}	Length of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
m_{Nano}	Mass of nano-enhanced PCM (kg)
m_{PCM}	Weight of melted PCM (Paraffin Wax) (kg)
m_p	weight of nanoparticles (SiC) (g)
\dot{m}_{air}	Mass flow rate (kg/s)
M_{ij}	Element used in Matrix
n	System life time (years)
N_{hr}	The number of hours per day during useful sunshine is available
N_d	Number of operating hours per sunny days in a year
N_{fin}	Number of the fins
N_{Nano}	Number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules
Nu	Nusselt number
Nu_w	Nusselt number due to wind
P_P	Pumping power (W)
P_r	Prandtl number

q_1	Heat transfer rate for channel 1 (W)
q_2	Heat transfer rate for channel 2 (W)
Q_{fin}	Heat transfer rate of fin (W)
Q_{Nano}	Heat transfer rate of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (W)
Q_u	Useful heat input (W)
r	Interest rate (%)
R	Ideal gas constant
Re	Reynold number
R_b	Thermal resistance due to back-plate loss (W)
$R_{cond(p-fin)}$	Thermal resistance due to conduction from absorber-plate to fins (W)
$R_{cond(Nano-b)}$	Thermal resistance due to conduction from Nano-enhanced PCM capsules to back-plate (W)
$R_{conv(g-f1)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from glass cover to air flowing in the upper channel (W)
$R_{conv(p-f1)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from absorber-plate to air flowing in the upper channel (W)
$R_{conv(b-f2)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from back-plate to air flowing in the lower channel (W)
$R_{conv(p-f2)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from absorber-plate to air flowing in the lower channel (W)
$R_{conv(fin-f2)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from fins to air flowing in the lower channel (W)
$R_{conv(Nano-f2)}$	Thermal resistance due to convection from Nano-enhanced PCM capsules to air flowing in the lower channel (W)
$R_{rad(g-sky)}$	Thermal resistance due to radiation from glass to sky (W)
$R_{rad(p-g)}$	Thermal resistance due to radiation from absorber-plate to glass (W)
$R_{rad(p-Nano)}$	Thermal resistance due to radiation from absorber-plate to Nano-enhanced PCM capsules (W)
R_w	Thermal resistance due to wind (W)
t_{op}	Operational time (hr)
T	Temperature (K) / (°C)
T_1	Temperature at surface 1 (K)
T_2	Temperature at surface 2 (K)
T_g	Temperature of glass cover (K)
T_{f1}	Temperature of air in upper channel (K)
T_{f2}	Temperature of air in lower channel (K)

T_a	Ambient temperature (K)
T_p	Temperature of absorber plate (K)
T_b	Temperature of back plate (K)
T_s	Temperature solar intensity (K)
T_N	Temperature at number of nano-enhanced PCM capsule ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
T_{sky}	Temperature of sky (K)
T_{Nano}	Temperature of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (K)
T_o	Outlet temperature of the air ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
T_i	Inlet temperature of the air ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
TES	Thermal energy stored (KJ)
U_t	Overall top loss coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2.\text{K}$)
U_b	Back-plate overall loss coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2.\text{K}$)
U_{edge}	Overall edge loss coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2.\text{K}$)
V_{Nano}	Volume of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m^3)
W_H	Width of the proposed heater
W_{fan}	Power of fan (W)

LIST OF GREEK LETTERS

α_g	Absorptivity of the glass cover
α_p	Absorptivity of the absorber plate
α_b	Absorptivity of the back- plate
β	Slope angle (deg.)
ΔP	Pressure drop (N/m ²)
ε_1	Emissivity of surface 1
ε_2	Emissivity of surface 2
ε_g	Emissivity of glass cover
ε_p	Emissivity of the absorber plate
ε_b	Emissivity of the back-plate
τ_g	Transmittivity of glass cover
ρ	Density (kg/m ³)
ρ_{air}	Air density (kg/m ³)
ρ_{Nano}	Nano-enhanced PCM density (kg/m ³)
ρ_p	Density of nanoparticles (SiC) (kg/m ³)
ρ_{PCM}	Density of melted PCM (Paraffin Wax) (kg/m ³)
σ	Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m ² .K ⁴)
η	Efficiency (%)
η_{en}	Thermal efficiency (%)
η_{ex}	Exergy efficiency (%)
η_{th}	Thermo-hydraulic efficiency (%)
η_{fan}	Fan efficiency (%)
η_{motor}	Motor efficiency (%)
Δ	Time period
μ	Viscosity (N.s/m ²)
μ_{air}	Viscosity of air (N.s/m ²)
μ_w	Viscosity at wall temperature (N.s/m ²)
ϑ_w	Wind speed (m/s)
ϑ_{air}	Air speed through the proposed heater (m/s)

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL OVERVIEW

During the past decade, the increased costs of fossil fuels used for drying purposes have led to a search for alternative methods that consume less fuel energy. Solar energy is one of the most promising renewable energy sources in the world; it is the world's most abundant permanent source of energy. The amount of solar energy that is intercepted by the Earth is 170 trillion kW; of this amount, 30% is reflected into space, 47% is converted to low-temperature heat and reradiated back into space, and 23% powers the evaporation precipitation cycle of the biosphere. Less than 0.5% of this energy is presented in the kinetic energy of wind and waves, as well as in the photosynthesis storage in plants. In contrast to fossil fuels, solar energy does not produce any harmful by products, does not rely on any moving parts, and requires only a minimal amount of upkeep (Zhang et al. 2021).

Solar heaters are used to convert incident solar irradiance into thermal energy at the absorbing surface, and then transmit this energy to a fluid (often water or air) that is flowing through the heater (Ajeena et al. 2022; Gorjian et al. 2020; Kumar et al. 2019). Air is used in the role of conveying fluid in solar air heaters. Without any need for optical concentration, they find widespread use in a variety of commercial and agricultural applications. In comparison to liquid solar systems, the solar air heater makes only minimal use of materials, and its direct use of air as the working fluid reduces the number of required system components. As a result, the solar air heater has a more straightforward design, requires less maintenance, and suffers from less corrosion and fewer leakage issues (Kalidasan et al. 2020). As a consequence of this, a number of studies, both theoretical and experimental, have been carried out to

determine the thermal performance of solar air heaters. As a result of these studies, a number of different modifications have been suggested and applied to improve the heat transfer coefficients in the heater such as the heat transfer coefficients between the absorber plate and upper/lower channel. In addition, integrating the solar heater with storage units as well (Ameri et al. 2021; Chand et al. 2022; Olivkar et al. 2022; Sunilraj et al. 2022).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Solar air heaters (SAHs) play a crucial role in harnessing solar energy and converting it into thermal energy for various applications, including space heating, agricultural processes, and drying applications. However, conventional SAHs have limitations in terms of their operating hours, mainly relying on direct solar radiation during daylight hours and facing reduced efficiency during periods of no sunlight or at night. To overcome these limitations and extend the operational time, the integration of backup thermal energy storage systems becomes necessary, especially in scenarios such as cloudy weather or continuous system operation.

One potential solution to address these limitations is the incorporation of nanoparticles into phase change materials (PCM) as an efficient thermal energy storage medium. This integration can significantly enhance the performance of solar air heaters, particularly when combined with the design of a double-pass system with fins. The utilization of a double-pass configuration improves heat transfer efficiency, while the integration of fins enhances the surface area available for heat exchange. However, there is a lack of comprehensive research and understanding regarding the practical implementation, design optimization, and overall performance evaluation of a double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM. This research gap hinders the development of efficient and reliable solar air heating systems suitable for drying applications or space heating in cold environments. Therefore, this study aims to address this research gap by investigating and optimizing the design parameters, operational characteristics, and overall performance of a double-pass solar air heater integrated with fins and nano-enhanced PCM. The findings of this research will contribute to the advancement of solar thermal systems,

offering improved efficiency, extended operational hours, and enhanced heating capabilities for various applications, particularly in environments where consistent solar radiation is not readily available.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This study aims to employ nanoparticles in phase change material (nano-enhanced PCM) and combining thermal storage technique of this nano-enhanced PCM along with a double-pass solar air heater with staggered rectangular fins. The fins will lead to extend the area of the absorber plate and nano-enhanced PCM capsules work as heat backup during no or low solar radiation. Therefore, the specific objectives of the research are as follows:

1. To develop the steady-state mathematical model for the DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins and nano-enhanced cylindrical PCM integrated storage system.
2. To evaluate the energetic and exergetic performance of the DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins and nano-enhanced cylindrical PCM.
3. To compare the results obtained from the mathematical model and experimental work.
4. To develop cost benefit model of the DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins and nano-enhanced cylindrical PCM for various combinations of the design variables.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The current study focused on developing the DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins and nano-enhanced cylindrical PCM. The scope corresponding to the main objectives is provided as follows:

- **Theoretical Model:** The programming using MATLAB to predict the optimum design and compared theoretically with other designs have the followings limitations: (1). Conventional Double-pass solar air heater; (2). Double-pass solar air heater with fins only; (3). Double-pass solar air heater with nano-enhanced PCM only; (4). Double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM in

different mass flow rates of 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s with different solar irradiance levels from 400 to 1000 W/m².

- **Experimental Studies:** The proposed DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins and nano-enhanced cylindrical PCM has length 1.0 m and width about 0.3 m. The number of fins are 23 with its height is 0.03 m and long 100 mm with thickness is 1 mm. The nano-enhanced PCM capsules are 23 with diameter 4.2 cm and its long exactly 0.292 m. The experimental results have been compared and validated with the results obtained from the mathematical model in different mass flow rates of 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s with different solar simulator irradiance levels ranging from 400 to 1000 W/m².
- **Cost Benefit Ratio Model:** For economic evaluation of the proposed (optimum) heater, analysing the cost-benefit ratio, annual cost (AC) and annual energy gain (AEG) of the heater for different design variables are all within the scope of the current study. The cost that is caused by carbon taxes was not taken into consideration since this cost varies greatly depending on the country of installation.

1.5 STRUCTURE OF THESIS

In this thesis, there are eight chapters which are: Chapter I introduction, Chapter II literature review, Chapter III methodology, Chapter IV mathematical modelling, Chapter V experimental setup, Chapter VI results and discussions, Chapter VII economic analysis and Chapter VIII conclusions & recommendations for future work. The details of each chapter are provided as follows:

Chapter I This chapter gives an introduction to this thesis, including the problem statement, and research objectives. More detailed schematic structures of individual chapters are given in the introduction section of each chapter.

Chapter II This chapter presents a comprehensive literature on solar air heaters and their components including the glass cover, absorber plate, and insulation. Additionally, the performance of the double-pass solar air heater is thoroughly reviewed. Furthermore, an in-depth analysis of nano-enhanced Phase Change Material (PCM) for integrated storage systems is presented. The chapter also covers the

thermo-physical properties of nano-enhanced PCM, such as thermal conductivity, latent heat capacity, density, and viscosity.

Chapter III This chapter details the methodology employed to achieve the objectives outlined in Chapter I. The research design is structured into five sections. The first section offers an overview of the DP-SAH (Double-Pass Solar Air Heater) with staggered fins and nano-enhanced PCM. Sections 2 and 3 outline the steps taken to obtain the mathematical and experimental results. Sections 4 and 5 delve into the synthesis method for nano-enhanced PCM and the error analysis approach, which utilizes Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

Chapter IV This chapter describes the mathematical modelling of the steady-state analysis for double-pass solar air heater with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM. A one-dimensional mathematical model using inverse matrix method has been obtained. This involves energy balance equations linking the radiative and convective heat transfer coefficients of the glass cover, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, and back plate in upper and lower channels. The performance in terms of thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies have been obtained. The pressure drop and exergy efficiency are also presented.

Chapter V This chapter describes the experimental setup and the devices used for the measurements of air mass flow rate, solar irradiance, and temperature. The calibration procedures for the thermocouple and the data acquisition system are presented. The uncertainty analysis of the measurements are discussed.

Chapter VI This chapter provides the results and discussions. The theoretical results are validated with experimental results to ensure the accuracy of the results. Parametric studies are conducted that eventually lead to the development of design curves for the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM. The parameters are temperature rise, solar irradiance, efficiencies, air mass flow rate, and upper channel depths.

Chapter VII This chapter involves the cost-benefit ratio of the heater. This chapter evaluates the annual cost (AC) and the annual energy gain (AEG) of the heater for different design variables. The optimization methodology is based on selecting those combinations of mass flow rates, studied heater lengths and upper channel depths that correspond to the minimum cost-benefit ratio or AC/AEG .

Chapter VIII This chapter provides the conclusions and suggestions for future works regarding the research activities reported in the current thesis. The recommendations are given focusing on what has been missing or were insufficient in the course of research hoping for follow-up research in the near future.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

A plethora of experimental and theoretical studies have been conducted on solar air heaters (SAHs) to enhance their functionality. Various modifications and enhancements have been made to the absorber plate, with one notable upgrade being the incorporation of fins to increase the heat transmission area. Different types of fins, including longitudinal fins, corrugated fins, and fins coupled with baffles, have all contributed to the improved performance of SAHs. Additionally, the performance of SAHs has been enhanced through recycling procedures. Moreover, the utilization of heat storage materials, particularly nano-enhanced phase change materials (nano-enhanced PCMs), has been explored, leading to selective packing bed configurations with improved performance.

2.2 SOLAR AIR HEATER (SAH)

As illustrated in Figure 2.1 solar air heaters are classified into two types: active and non-active (passive). In a passive solar air heater, buoyant force, wind pressure, or both can be used to naturally heat and circulate the air inside the unit. The greenhouse dryer, as well as the conventional and reverse absorber cabinet air heaters, all operate in passive mode. Many Mediterranean, tropical, and subtropical regions, particularly in Africa and Asia, as well as small agricultural villages, continue to use passive drying (Udomkun et al. 2020). In solar active systems, the movement of solar energy in the form of warm air from the collecting area to the drying beds is accomplished by means that are external to the system. These techniques include fans and pumps. As a consequence of their use, all active solar dryers are examples of forced convection dryers. In a conventional active solar dryer, motorised fans or ventilators are used to

circulate the air, and solar energy is the only source of heat (Etim et al. 2020). These dryers have widespread use in large-scale commercial drying operations where they provide an essential function. They are used in combination with conventional dryers that run on fossil fuels to increase drying control. This is accomplished by lowering the influence that fluctuations in sun insolation have on the drying air temperature (Balasuadhakar et al. 2016).

Figure 2.1 Classification of solar air heaters (SAHs).

Source: Olivkar et al. (2022)

2.2.1 Components of Solar Air Heater

The glass cover, absorber plate, and insulation are the three basic components of a solar air heater as shown in Figure 2.2. As sun energy travels through the transparent cover of the solar air heater, it is absorbed by the absorber plate, which then transmits heat to the working fluid (air).

Figure 2.2 Schematic layout of Solar Air Heater (SAH).

a. Glass cover

The glass cover transfers maximum sun energy to the absorber plate. It serves three key functions: (i) transmits incoming solar energy to the absorber plate with the lowest loss, (ii) minimises convective and radiant heat loss from the absorber, and (iii) protects the absorber plate from the outside environment. Reflection (r), absorption (α), and transmission (τ) are also essential. Maximum efficiency requires minimum reflection and absorption and strong transmission. When choosing cover plate material, consider strength, durability, UV resistance, and cost. Common glazing materials include glass and polymers (Maheswari et al. 2022; Sivakumar et al. 2022; Tyagi et al. 2018).

b. Absorber plate

An absorber plate is a flat plate constructed of high-thermal-conductivity, high-tensile-strength, non-corrosive materials (e.g., copper). The absorber plate transfers solar radiation to the solar air heater's operating fluid. Steel, galvanised iron, aluminium, and thermoplastics make up the solar heater. Thin metal (Cu or Al) may be insulated

on non-flow sides to make absorber plates. Material absorption affects solar radiation absorption. Thus, black absorber plates improve absorption (Tyagi et al. 2018).

c. Insulation

It is vital, for improved performance of the solar air heater, to prevent heat losses from the absorbing plates, either by conduction or convection. Insulation, which offers the strongest heat resistance, helps reduce this loss to a minimum. Fiber glass, mineral wool, and glass wool are the types of insulation that are used most often nowadays.

2.3 DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER (DP-SAH)

The typical SAH has a low thermal efficiency because the convective coefficient between the heat-collecting surface and the working fluid is quite low. As a result, raising the convection coefficient to a higher value becomes absolutely necessary in order to raise the thermal performance of the system. In order to effectively improve the performance of a conventional solar air heater, it is necessary to reduce the losses from the heater surface by providing the appropriate insulation and to increase the convective coefficient between the heat collecting surface and the working fluid by enhancing the heat transfer area, which can be increased by double pass design. These two steps can be accomplished by providing the proper insulation and by reducing the losses from the heater surface (Ghritlahre et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2016).

The counter or return flow double-pass sun air heater and the parallel pass double duct solar air heater are the two primary classifications of double-pass solar air heaters. Both of these classifications are determined by the direction of fluid flow (Alam et al. 2017). The construction has glass, an absorber plate, and a bottom plate that is insulated. This is the case in both scenarios. There are two air flow channels, one between the glazing and the absorber plate and the other between the absorber and the bottom insulated plate. Both of these channels are located between the glazing and the absorber plate. The air flows in the opposite direction above and below the absorber plate in the counter flow type as illustrated in Figure 2.2 (a) and (b), while the air flows in the same direction above and below the absorber plate in the parallel flow as illustrated in Figure 2.3 (c).

Figure 2.3 (a) and (b) Schematic diagram of counter flow.(c) Schematic diagram of parallel flow.
Source: Chamoli et al. (2012)

2.3.1 Performance Enhancement Techniques for Double Pass Solar Air Heater

In order to improve the performance of double-pass solar air heaters (DP-SAHs), which are equipped with performance enhancement techniques such as using packed bed materials (PBMs), extended surfaces, corrugated/grooved absorbing surfaces, and obstacles in the flow channel, a number of different experimental and theoretical investigations have been considered.

a. Double-pass solar air heater with packed bed materials

The low thermal efficiency of SAH can be attributed to two primary factors: the first is the low convection coefficient between the heater plate and the working fluid (air) as a result of the air's poor thermal conductivity, and the second is related to the thickness of the absorption plate, which can be improved by using a packed bed absorbing surface. Both of these factors are related to the low thermal conductivity of the air. Packed bed materials, also known as PBMs, are utilised in SAH and provide as a medium for storing thermal energy. A packed bed is a volume of the porous medium that is achieved by packing particles of a certain substance into a container. The material used for packaging creates more turbulence, which speeds up the pace at which heat is transferred (Bouadila et al. 2013; Chouksey et al. 2022; Karthikeyan et al. 2021; Türkakar 2021).

b. Double-pass solar air heater with extended surface

Poor heat transmission between the absorber plate and air results in thermal losses to the environment. Increasing the heat transfer coefficient and fitting fins in the solar air heater flow channel may decrease this loss and boost the SAH's efficiency. These fins impede airflow, which increases turbulence and heat transmission. They have a huge heat transfer area. This kind of air heater has a high coefficient of friction, which is vital when selecting SAH (Thakkar et al. 2018).

c. Double-pass solar air heater with artificial roughness

The laminar sub-layer that is formed along the wall of the heat-absorbing surface is another factor that contributes to the poor heat transfer that occurs between the

absorber surface and the air in the SAH duct. In order to improve the pace at which heat is transferred, it is required to break through this layer, which offers the barrier to the passage of heat. According to Khimsuriya et al. (2022), the presence of artificial roughness in the form of repetitive ribs on the absorber plate disrupts the laminar sub-layer in the fluid and causes turbulence in the fluid running right near the surface of the absorber. Artificial roughness, on the other hand, causes an increase in the pressure drop. Because of this, the design of the SAH must achieve its aims of optimizing the convection coefficient and reducing the rise in pressure drop.

d. Double-pass solar air heater with obstacles in the flow channels

It is a well-known fact that obstacles that are connected to the heat absorber plate may improve the rate of heat transfer. This is accomplished by expanding the area that is capable of transferring heat and increasing the severity of the turbulence. However, the pressure loss through the SAH also rises when the area of the barriers linked to the heat absorber plate becomes larger (Ahn et al. 2020). As a result, a number of researches have been carried out on the shape of the barriers in order to improve the overall performance of the heat transfer by raising the rate of heat transfer while simultaneously reducing the amount of pressure drop.

2.4 ADVANCED ABSORBER DESIGN

Many studies have examined DP-SAH performance improvements. Using fins and heat storage materials may increase DP-SAH performance. Fins enhance heat transfer area and solar air heater efficiency. Fin height, number, and arrangement were explored experimentally or theoretically.

2.4.1 Fins

The primary purpose of using fins is to enhance the area of heat transfer, which will ultimately result in an improvement in the heater's overall efficiency. Because of this, the implications of fin height, number, and arrangement on performance were either experimentally or theoretically investigated, or both. Fins of several sorts have be

shown to improve performance such as staggered fins, corrugated fins, longitudinal fins and fins attached with baffles.

a. Staggered fins

Staggered fins have been investigated as an enhancement for the double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) configuration. By incorporating staggered fins in the DP-SAH, the heat transfer surface area is increased, leading to improved performance. Staggered fins create turbulence in the airflow, which enhances convective heat transfer and promotes efficient heat exchange between the air and the absorber plate. This configuration has shown promising results in increasing the thermal efficiency of DP-SAH systems and optimizing their overall performance.

Fudholi et al. (2013a) conducted a study that specifically examined the thermal performance of rectangular finned absorber plates. The objective of their research was to determine the optimal conditions for the collector. Their findings revealed that the thermal efficiencies achieved were as high as 77%. On the other hand, Assadeg et al. (2023) conducted a study utilizing the same rectangular fins; however, researchers experimented with different sizes and distances between the fins. Their research aimed to explore the impact of these variations on the performance of the heater as shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 Absorber plate of DP-SAH with staggered rectangular fins.

Source: (Assadeg et al. 2023)

b. Corrugated fins

In a theoretical analysis, the potential for enhancing the efficiency of the solar air heater was explored by incorporating herringbone-corrugated fins beneath the absorber plate, as depicted in Figure 2.5. These fins were oriented parallel to the fluid flow channel to facilitate improved heat transfer.

Figure 2.5 Solar air heater with herringbone-corrugated fins.

Source: (Kumar et al. 2017)

c. Longitudinal fins

Murali et al. (2020) performed on a double-pass solar air heater and rectangular longitudinal fins on one side of the absorber plate. Both the air heater with fins placed in the lower channel and the air heater with fins placed in the upper channel have their performance characteristics given, including outlet temperature, absorber plate temperature, and output power. We also looked at how the mass flow rate of air affected the efficiency of an air heater that included fins in both the lower and the upper channel. According to the findings, an air heater that has its fins situated in the lower channel is more effective than an air heater that has its fins situated in the higher channel. Ashwini (2017) studied a new jet plate solar air heater that has

continuous longitudinal fins below the absorber plate is researched as illustrated in Figure 2.6. The performance qualities are shown with the aid of relevant parameters. In compared to the previous studies that were discussed, an increase in thermal efficiency ranging from 3% to 14.7% was recorded for the Reynolds number ranging of 3000 to 15000. In addition, an increase in heat transfer enhancement on the order of 28–39 % is accomplished.

Figure 2.6 Jet plate solar air heater with longitudinal fins.

Source: Ashwini (2017)

d. Attaching baffles

Saravanakumar et al. (2020) conducted a theoretical analysis on the exergetic performance and parameter optimization of an arc-shaped rib roughened solar air heater combined with fins and baffles as shown in Figure 2.7. It has been found that the suggested SAH has a maximum exergy efficiency of 5.2% while operating in optimal circumstances. Based on the plots of the mathematical model, it is clear that the highest exergy can be reached by setting the number of fins to 8, the length of the baffle to 0.2 m, the width of the baffle to 0.015 m, and the mass flow rate to 0.012 kg/s. Parsa et al. (2021) investigated a numerical parametric optimization of turbulent convective heat transfer in a solar air heater duct with new staggered cuboid baffles positioned on the absorber plate as shown in Figure 2.8. Parsa et al. (2021) studied also numerical findings and show that the optimal design and suggested outperforming the state-of-the-art

Figure 2.7 Solar air heater (SAH) with fins and baffles.

Source: (Saravanakumar et al. 2020)

solutions. It is also shown that the efficiency and thermo-hydraulic performance factor are most sensitive to the relative baffle height (c/H) and relative baffle pitch (s/H). As an additional note, the optimal baffled solar air heater has a thermo-hydraulic performance factor of 3.43, 2.80 and 2.38 at Reynolds numbers 5080, 7620, and 10160, respectively.

Figure 2.8 Schematic of solar air heater duct with staggered baffles above the absorber.

Source: (Parsa et al. 2021)

2.5 INTEGRATED STORAGE SYSTEM

The most negative aspect of solar air heaters with external heat storage units is energy loss over the transit path, as shown in Figure 2.9. To compensate for the loss, the system must be well-insulated over the full path length, resulting in greater startup costs, higher maintenance costs, and an increase in the total size of the unit. These disadvantages are solved by the solar air heater with integrated storage unit, which lowers the system cost (Abi Mathew et al. 2021; Kalaiarasi et al. 2020).

Bouadila et al. (2013) developed a solar air heating system with an integrated energy storage unit made up of packed bed latent heat storage. The solar air heater achieves 45% average daily efficiency thanks to spherical capsules holding storage material placed inside the heater. During the discharge time, the storage unit aids in maintaining a temperature of 17 °C. Aboul-Enein et al. (2020) investigated a solar air heating system with and without an integrated heat storage unit while keeping it in an inclined position. The heat storage unit was installed under the absorber plate, which is intended to allow any storage material to be placed with ease. Experiments using water, granite, and sand as sensible heat storage medium were carried out in this system. The temperature of the exit air is mostly determined by operational characteristics such as air mass flow rate and heat storage material spacing. The study found that as heater width and length increase, the output air temperature rises until a critical point is reached, beyond which no changes are seen. As illustrated in Figure 2.10, Bouadila et al. (2014) studied a solar air heater with a packed bed latent heat storage unit comprised of spherical PCM capsules. By adjusting the mass flow rate of the working fluid and for different global solar radiation times, the charging and discharging of heat from the heat storage unit were investigated. The first and second laws of thermodynamics are used to compute energy and exergy efficiency. According to the findings, energy and exergy efficiency of up to 45% and 25%, respectively. Mohanraj et al. (2018) built a solar air drier with a thermal energy storage system for copra drying. In order to generate a greenhouse effect, the absorber is equipped with 5 mm thick glass. This results in a greater air temperature. Between the glass cover and the absorber, a 25-mm space was maintained. As a sensible heat

Figure 2.9 The process of thermal energy collection and storage (a). with non-integrated process (b) with integrated process.

Source: Haldorai et al. (2019).

Figure 2.10 Schematic diagram of solar air heater with integrated latent heat storage.

Source: Bouadila et al. (2013).

storage medium, sand with aluminum scrap was employed, and it was inserted between the absorber and the insulator with a spacing of 100 mm. Experiments were carried out throughout both full and partial sunlight hours. The solar drier was also utilized to dry chilli from 72.8% moisture content to 9.2% moisture content, with a 21% thermal efficiency.

A double-pass solar air heater with an integrated latent heat-based thermal energy storage unit was developed and researched by Krishnananth et al. (2013). The latent heat storage substance in the PCM unit is paraffin wax. This solar system was studied in great depth in several configurations. The greatest results were obtained when the storage medium was placed beneath the absorber plate. The comparison of a solar air heater with and without a thermal storage unit reveals that the system with the storage unit has greater efficiency and maintains a higher outlet air temperature for a longer length of time. Ramani et al. (2012) reported on the thermal performance of a double-pass solar air heater in another investigation. The solar heater was tested with and without a porous medium in the absorber plate as shown in Figure 2.11. In the second air passage, the investigation was conducted on a system with a double-pass counter-flow configuration. The volumetric heat transfer coefficient was used to construct a mathematical model for the solar heater setup using porous material. The efficiency of a solar heater with porous media is 30 to 35 % more than that of a heater without porous material or media. Omojaro et al. (2012) tested a solar air heater with a single and double pass configuration and an integrated steel wire mesh absorber plate. The maximum temperature difference obtained from this study is 37 °C and 41.6 °C for the single and double pass air heater respectively for air mass flow rate of 0.012 kg/s.

2.6 NANO-ENHANCED PCM

Various researchers have investigated and explored the latent heat storage system employing phase change material (PCM). PCMs have a potential thermal storage property that allows them to collect and release a considerable amount of latent heat during phase transition. The temperature of these materials remains constant during The phase transition process, as demonstrated in Figure 2.12. Latent heat, Q_{latent} (kJ)

and sensible heat Q_{sensible} (kJ) are demonstrated in equations (2.1) and (2.2), respectively.

Figure 2.11 Schematic diagram of solar air heater with and without porous media

Source:(Ramani et al. 2012).

$$Q_{\text{latent}} = m \times H_L \quad \dots(2.1)$$

$$Q_{\text{sensible}} = m \times C_p \times \Delta T \quad \dots(2.2)$$

m is mass (kg), H_L is specific latent heat (kJ/kg), C_p is specific heat (kJ/kg. °C) and ΔT is temperature difference.

PCM is categorized in general depending on the state change that occurs throughout the phase transition process (solid-liquid; liquid-gas; solid-solid). Organics (paraffin and fatty acids), inorganics (salts, hydrates, and metals), and eutectics are the three types of solid-liquid PCM (Fallahi et al. 2017; Phan et al. 2022; Singh & Patel 2022). Eutectic PCM is a homogeneous combination of two or more kinds of PCM

compounds that melts and freezes, in the same way, every time (Chandel et al. 2017). The purpose of eutectic PCM synthesis is to increase the latent heat and specific melting temperature. Organic/organic, inorganic/organic, and inorganic/inorganic eutectic PCMs are examples of eutectic PCMs (Souayfane et al. 2016) The melting temperature of the eutectic combination of lauric acid and myristic acid is claimed to be lower than that of the separate components/compounds (Keleş et al. 2015).

Figure 2.12 Variation in PCM temperature during heating and cooling operations (ideal case)

Source: Leong et al. (2019).

organic PCM has a lower heat conductivity. Paraffin wax has a thermal conductivity of 0.24 W/m.K (Gorbacheva et al. 2021; Jiang et al. 2018; Leong et al. 2022). This property inhibits the stored energy (heat) in the PCM from being released onto the environment for beneficial purposes. During the heat charging process, a similar state is encountered. The efficacy of PCM will be harmed by longer heat charging and discharging times. Adding highly thermally conductive nanoparticles (Lin et al. 2016; Liu et al. 2021; Mohamed et al. 2017) to PCM can improve its thermal conductivity. As demonstrated in Figure 2.14, PCM mix with nanoparticles is known as Nano-PCM or nano-enhanced PCM. Nanoparticles such as carbon nanotubes, graphite,

graphene, silicon carbide metal and metal oxide can be dispersed in PCM (Kibria et al. 2015). It's worth mentioning that adding nanoparticles to PCM changes not only its thermal conductivity but also its other properties, such as latent heat capacity, sub-cooling, phase change temperature and duration, density, and viscosity. In their experimental investigation.

Figure 2.13 Concept of nano-PCM or nano-enhanced phase change material

Source: (Leong et al. 2019).

According to Babapoor et al. (2016), the addition of various types of nanoparticles to phase change materials (PCM) significantly alters their thermal characteristics. Thus, the purpose of this chapter is to assess the influence of nanoparticles on the thermo-physical properties of PCM, including thermal conductivity, latent heat, subcooling, phase change duration and temperatures, density, and viscosity. Additionally, the impact of prolonged heat cycles on the thermal characteristics will be investigated. Furthermore, this chapter will comprehensively examine the optimal properties of nano-enhanced PCM, explore their applications, address potential challenges, and provide insights into future directions for nano-enhanced PCM..

2.6.1 Thermo-Physical Properties of Nano-Enhanced PCM

Thermo-physical characteristics of nano-enhanced PCM are covered in this section, including (a). Thermal conductivity, (b) Latent heat capacity, (c) Sub-cooling, phase change duration and phase change temperatures, (d) Density, (e) Viscosity and Thermo-physical properties after thermal cycles. Table 2.1 provides a summary of the

thermo-physical characteristics of nano-enhanced PCMs that have been researched by a number of researchers and are accessible in the literature.

a. Thermal conductivity

Nanotechnology advancements have enabled the fabrication of tiny particles (10^{-9}). Metal, metal oxide, carbon nanotube (single-walled carbon nanotube-SWCNT, multiwalled carbon nanotube-MWCNT), graphene, and graphite are among the nanoparticles. Because of their large surface area to volume ratio, nanoparticles are claimed to have different characteristics from bulk solids (Darabdhara et al. 2019; Deepa et al. 2022) MWCNT has a thermal conductivity of around 3000 W/m.K (Al-Janabi et al. 2021).

Single-layer graphene has a thermal conductivity of up to 5300 W/m.K (Fang et al. 2019). Nanoparticles have a higher thermal conductivity than phase change materials. Paraffin, for example, has a thermal conductivity of 0.305 W/m.K (melting temperature of 60–62°C) (Yu et al. 2022). As a result, adding these highly thermally conductive nanoparticles to the PCM is predicted to boost heat transfer. According to Rufuss et al. (2018), adding 3 wt. % titanium dioxide (TiO₂), copper oxide (CuO), and graphene oxide (GO) to paraffin enhanced thermal conductivity by 25.0 %, 28.8 %, and 101.2 %, respectively. Particle concentration, particle dispersion, particle size, shape, and type, surfactant, and temperature are all elements that can alter thermal conductivity of nano-enhanced PCM. The parameters that impact the thermal conductivity of nano-enhanced PCM are summarised in Figure 2.14.

The addition of nanoparticles to PCM is intended to increase the material's thermal conductivity. A significant amount of nanoparticles must be introduced to generate a heat-conductive network (Magendran et al. 2019). The heat transfer process within the PCM is aided by this thermal conductive network. Zhang et al. (2017) support this their experiment on the thermal characteristics of short carbon fibers/erythritol PCM. The thermal conductivity of PCM including highly thermal conductive nanoparticles is not guaranteed to be higher than that of PCM containing less thermally conductive nanoparticles. The homogeneous distribution of particles in PCM should also be--considered. Apart from using mechanical methods such as

sonication, particle surface modification and surfactant addition can also help improve particle dispersion in PCM. Carbon nanotubes are often subjected to particle surface modification. Sulfuric and nitric acids are used to cleanse the surface of carbon nanotubes in this technique. Surfactants are lengthy chemical molecules with hydrophilic and lipophilic groups on both sides. They alter the surface characteristics of the particles while also inhibiting the development of particle clusters (Mingzheng et al. 2012). Several studies have found that increasing the quantity of nanoparticles in nano enhanced PCM improves thermal conductivity (Fikri, Pandey, et al. 2022; Nematpourkeshteli et al. 2022; Yang et al. 2022). Nanoparticles, as noted previously, exhibit different characteristics than bulk solids due to their large surface area to volume ratio. Theoretically, a smaller particle size results in a higher ratio. Zhang et al. (2017) looked at the impact of two distinct aspect ratios of carbon nanofiber on erythritol thermal conductivity. The diameter of these two carbon nanofibers is comparable, but their lengths are different For high aspect ratio carbon nanofibers, this property resulted in decreased thermal resistance and the creation of a thermal conductive network. As a consequence, when erythritol was combined with a high aspect ratio carbon nanofiber, the thermal conductivity was greater than when erythritol was combined with a small aspect ratio fibre. The aspect ratio of nanoparticles is also influenced by their form nanoparticles can be made in the shape of a sphere, a cubic, or a rod (cylinder).

Figure 2.14 Thermal conductivity of nano-enhanced PCM is affected by a number of factors.

Table 2.1 Thermo-physical properties of nano-enhanced PCMs.

Reference	Nano-enhanced PCM	Thermo-Physical Properties of Nano-Enhanced PCM.		
		Thermal conductivity	Latent heat capacity	Sub-cooling, phase change duration, Phase change temperature
Kalbande et al. (2022)	Pure paraffin wax and its composite with CuO-MWCNT.	Nano-enhanced PCM exhibited 6.125% higher thermal conductivity than that of pure paraffin wax.	Highest latent heat for freezing and melting were observed in nanoparticles.	Nanoparticles reduce melting temperature. Particle concentration increases.
Kumar et al. (2021)	Paraffin wax, copper oxide (CuO and aluminium are considered as nanoparticle.	Thermal conductivity of nano-enhanced phase change material (NePCM) are found to increase by 100%.	Addition of nanoparticle is only beneficial at low concentration.	Melting temperature of paraffin wax is only slightly affected by addition of nanoparticles.
Martín et al. (2019)	silicon dioxide nanoparticles (nSiO ₂) addition (0.5 wt.%, 1.0 wt.% and 1.5 wt.%).	Nano-enhanced PCM exhibited highest thermal conductivity compared to all tested samples.	Addition of nanoparticle reduce supercooling.	Addition of nanoparticles affect melting and solidification temperature of phase change material.
Liu et al. (2018)	Paraffin, octadecanol (OA), stearic acid, Two types of reduced graphene oxide and silver particles (0.5, 1, 2,3,5 and 10 wt.%).	Thermal conductivity of PCM increases with concentration of particles.	Latent heat of fusion of PCM decreases with addition of particles.	Melting point increases with the increase of particles in paraffin.
Salyan et al. (2018)	D-Mannitol Copper oxide (0.1, 0.2, 0.5 wt.%)	Thermal conductivity of paraffin wax (1.308 W/m.K) increases with addition of copper oxide (0.5 wt.%, 1.637 W/m.K)	Latent heat (melting) of paraffin wax (281.89 kJ/kg) decreases with addition of copper oxide. (At 0.5 wt.%, 273.20 kJ/ kg).	Phase change temperature of paraffin wax is almost similar after added with copper oxide.

The cubic form has the most surface area of the three. The synthesis of cubic form nanoparticles, on the other hand, is expensive and time-consuming (Ambreen et al. 2020). More study is needed to investigate the influence of nanoparticle size and shape on the thermal conductivity of nano-enhanced PCM, particularly the solid type, despite the fact that a large number of studies have shown that liquid supplemented with smaller nanoparticles has a greater thermal conductivity.

b. Latent heat capacity

During the heating or cooling of a nano-PCM, two forms of energy (heat) must be taken into account: latent and sensible heat. Latent heat is used during the melting process to overcome the intermolecular forces of a material. During the solidification process, heat is dissipated, allowing the molecules to reorganise themselves in an ordered fashion. In contrast, sensible heat alters the temperature of the substance. Specifically, there is latent heat of fusion (from solid to liquid) and latent heat of vaporisation (from liquid to gas) (liquid to gas or vice-versa). Since traditional or nano-enhanced PCM applications are often restricted to solid and liquid states, researchers are solely concerned with the latent heat of fusion.

The high latent heat of phase transition materials is their most promising behaviour. It is suggested that thermal conductive nanoparticles be included into phase change material to compensate for the material's poor thermal conductivity. However, "foreign substance" additions shouldn't compromise phase change materials' latent heat. To this end, studies of nano-enhanced PCM are not only concentrating on its thermal conductivity, but also its latent heat behaviour. Researchers have also ascribed the change in latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM to the following two factors: (Bahiraei et al. 2017; Ibrahim et al. 2022; Kumar et al. 2021; Sami et al. 2017).

- An improvement in the latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM will occur as a result of a change in the interaction between the molecules of PCM and the nanoparticles.
- If there is a high loading of nanoparticles, the latent heat will be reduced because there will be too much replacement of phase change material with nanoparticles.

Researchers have also discovered that the incorporation of nanoparticles into phase change material results in an increase in the latent heat of the material. Researchers from Singh, Verma, et al. (2022) found that the latent heat (melting) of SWCNT, MWCNT, and carbon nanofiller (CNF) based nano-enhanced paraffin wax steadily increases as particle loading rises up to 1.0 vol %. An increase of 12.98 % is seen for SWCNT, 10.08 % is seen for MWCNT, and 6.80 % is seen for CNF correspondingly. In a study that was published not too long ago. Hayat et al. (2022) found that the latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM is superior to that of pure PCM when up to 2 wt % of α -alumina is added to paraffin wax and microcrystalline wax.

c. Sub-cooling, phase change duration and phase change temperatures

The presence of sub-cooling or super-cooling in PCM-based thermal energy storage systems is considered undesirable as it can potentially reduce the efficiency of the material (Fikri, Samykano, et al. 2022; Shamseddine et al. 2022). The sub-cooling effect plays a crucial role in the cooling process and serves as an alternative to conventional heating methods (Amudhalapalli et al. 2022). When the sub-cooling effect is significant, the PCM may encounter challenges in releasing the retained heat even at its melting point.

The dissipation of latent heat commences when the temperature falls below the solidifying point. To address this issue, the utilization of heterogeneous nucleation can be employed, wherein "foreign" components such as nanoparticles are introduced to facilitate the crystallization process and mitigate the problem.

Nanoparticles serve as nucleation agents in PCM, as observed in studies conducted by (D'oliveira et al. 2022; Garay Ramirez et al. 2014; Kumar et al. 2022; Lin et al. 2016; Shen et al. 2021; Venkitaraj et al. 2019). These studies have demonstrated that the presence of nanoparticles leads to a shorter duration for the entire melting and solidification process in nano-enhanced PCM. Additionally, as mentioned earlier, nano-enhanced PCM exhibits significantly higher thermal conductivity compared to regular PCM. This enhanced thermal conductivity facilitates easier heat absorption and release within the material.

d. Density

According to a basic mixing model, when the concentration of nanoparticles rises, the density of nano-enhanced should rise as well. When volume is restricted in a PCM storage system, high-density PCM is the optimum option (Mjallal et al. 2018; Xu et al. 2017), since it allows for more mass transfer during the phase change process. However, only a few studies have focused on the density of nano-enhanced PCM. Warzoha et al. (2012) discovered experimentally the density of paraffin with 8wt.% of graphite nanofibers increases by 1.48 % when compared to pure paraffin wax as well as when 20 vol.% of nanoparticles are added to nano-enhanced PCM, the density is greater than basic paraffin wax (Warzoha et al. 2014). Saeed et al. (2018) showed that adding graphene platelets to eutectic PCM increases its density.

e. Viscosity

Viscosity is a characteristic that describes a fluid's resistance to flow. When the viscosity of the fluid is high, more pump power is required to move it. The applications of PCM, even in liquid form, do not need it flowing from one location to another. During the solidifying or melting process, most of the PCM is stored in a specific storage like in the current study, the DP-SAH has kept the PCM in 23 cylindrical capsules. The viscosity of a liquid phase change material might affect the stability of spherical particles in a liquid. When a high-viscosity fluid is utilized, the particle sedimentation velocity drops, according to the Stokes law. In other meaning, nanoparticles have higher tendency to move downward due to gravitational force if the liquid has low viscosity.

The viscosity of a liquid phase transition material will be significantly increased if nanoparticles are added. The existence of nanoparticles in a liquid will cause it to flow irregularly. For example, the viscosity of nano-PCM rises with particle volume fraction and also with operating temperatures up to 90 °C, the viscosity of carbon-based nano-enhanced phase change material reduces according to He et al. (2012) and Bahiraei et al. (2017)

f. Thermo-physical properties after thermal cycles

Maintaining nano-enhanced PCM's thermal characteristics after melting and solidifying is critical. Cycles may alter nanoparticle dispersion. Stable nanoparticle dispersion in PCM improves cycle stability (B et al. 2021). Ibrahim et al. (2022) observed that the melting temperature and latent heat (melting) of paraffin with 3.0 wt.%. The same circumstance reduces heat conductivity. The research found that nano-enhanced PCM's thermal characteristics alter less than paraffin wax. Harikrishnan et al. (2017) employed 4000 heat cycles to test 1.0 wt.% SiO₂ in myristic acid. Sami and Etesami [32] found that melting and solidification phase transition temperatures increased by 2.09 and 1.63 %, respectively. Both melting and solidification latent heat reduce by 0.89 and 0.61%. According to the research, these deviations are minor. Suresh Kumar et al. (2017) also found a modest decrease in CuO-palmitic acid latent heat (melting and solidification).

2.6.2 Ideal Characteristics of Nano-Enhanced PCM

Wei et al. (2018) analyzed specific criteria and considerations for selecting the optimal PCM. The following are the desirable features of nano-enhanced phase change material as well as ideal property of nano-enhanced PCM is shown in Figure 2.15.

- High thermal conductivity - The capacity of a substance to carry heat is defined by its thermal conductivity. High thermal conductivity PCM is selected because it allows heat to be stored or released quickly. Zhu et al. (2018) agreed emphasising the need for quick heat transfer for effective thermal energy storage.
- Temperature for phase change that is appropriate for the application. This temperature must be the same as the application temperature. This ensures that heat is charged or discharged at the proper temperature. Paraffin wax has a wide temperature range for phase change. Researchers have employed melting temperatures of 53 °C - 57 °C and 25 °C for paraffin wax (Sobolčiak et al. 2016). The melting temperature of paraffin wax is also affected by the length of the hydrocarbon chain (Mu et al. 2016).

- Small volume change during phase transition - small volume change reduces the design complexity of the PCM storage system.
- Low sub-cooling temperature - Supercooling is another term for sub-cooling. Even when the liquid PCM approaches freezing (solidification) temperature, if the super-cooling is high, the liquid PCM will not start to solidify. It will only begin to freeze and crystallise when the temperature is well below freezing. When crystallisation (solidification) begins, latent heat is released. The impact of super-cooling is reduced when thermal conductivity is improved. When thermal conductivity is increased, better heat transfer inside the material can be attained (Lin et al. 2016)
- Higher latent heat - PCM with a higher latent heat storage capacity is preferred. Latent heat differs from sensible heat in that it refers to the energy necessary for a

Figure 2.15 The ideal properties of nano- enhanced phase change material (PCM).

phase change process in which no temperature variation is visible. The energy necessary to overcome intermolecular tensions during the melting process is known as latent heat. Meanwhile, the temperature of the material rises due to sensible heat.

Peippo et al. (1991) created a model to calculate the optimal temperature for phase change material (PCM). Their model takes into account a number of variables, such as heat absorbed and for charging / discharging periods.

- High density, especially when used in a small storage system.
- High thermal diffusivity- The used PCM has high thermal diffusivity as possible.
- Safe - The chosen PCM must not be corrosive, hazardous, or flammable.
- Low cost - To reduce the investment cost and payback period, the PCM should be as inexpensive as possible.
- The used PCM must have rapid crystallisation and low vapour pressure.
- High stability - The PCM must have a high level of chemical stability. Throughout the repeated heating and cooling procedures, the characteristics of PCM must stay unaltered.

2.6.3 Applications of Nano-Enhanced PCM

Researchers study nano-enhanced PCM's uses. It integrates nano-enhanced PCM with building materials, heat exchangers, heat sinks, heat pipes, solar water systems, solar air heaters (SAH) and solar stills. This integration reduces a building's cooling demand, uses passive cooling, recovers heat, and improves thermal efficiency (Al-Jethelah et al. 2018; Amudhalapalli et al. 2022; Colla et al. 2017; D'oliveira et al. 2022). (Khan et al. 2019).

Effective building energy consumption, particularly the air-conditioning system, benefits the environment. Energy conservation reduces global warming. It also enhances energy security and environmental sustainability(Baskar et al. 2022). Similar to traditional PCM, nano-enhanced PCM may promote energy-efficient building envelopes. High latent materials like as PCM or nano-enhanced PCM may be used to increase building thermal mass (Wang et al. 2022). Interior temperature variance and cooling demand will be decreased.

Hayat et al. (2022) found that nano-enhanced PCM wallboard reduces energy use and their investigation observes building envelope heat gains and losses. This strategy only works in regions with substantial daytime temperature differences.

Martín et al. (2019) used nano-enhanced PCM layers in a house's ceiling ventilation system. This system uses an air-based solar thermal heater for cooling and heating. Nano-enhanced PCM increased energy storage compared to pure PCM. Researchers are now investigating the potential for integrating nano-enhanced PCM into a variety of thermal systems, including photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) systems, solar air heaters, and others. The primary objective of using this method is to raise the overall energy efficiency of these thermal systems. For example, if the temperature of the PV cells is allowed to rise, the efficiency of the PV/T system will decrease. It is possible to employ nano-enhanced phase change material to maintain the optimal operating temperature of the panel while at the same time absorbing the surplus heat that is produced by solar irradiance. Sharma et al. (2014) found that adding nano-enhanced PCM to the finned plate reduced photovoltaic system temperature. This system's passive cooling was nano-enhanced PCM. Micro-finned plates with nano-enhanced PCM had the largest temperature decrease. Despite using a typical PCM coupled with a heat exchanger in a residential refrigerator.

Bakhshipour et al. (2017) found a decrease in power usage and an improvement in refrigeration COP compared to a system without PCM. Chaiyat (2015) invented split unit air-conditioning with a PCM bed to lower evaporator coil air temperature. This strategy lowered electricity use by 9% with a 4.12-year payback. (Takudzwa Muzhanje et al. 2022) recently linked a nano-enhanced PCM heat exchanger to an AC condenser. Their investigation suggested this strategy achieves improved performance and energy savings. Nano-enhanced PCM is also employed in passive electrical cooling. High temperature causes device failure. Combining nano-enhanced PCM with traditional cooling technologies like heat pipe (Hayat et al. 2020) and finned heat sink (Al-Omari et al. 2022; Bayat et al. 2018; Kothari et al. 2021) reduces device temperature and saves energy. Table 2.2 provides a summary of the many different applications that nano-enhanced PCM may be used for.

2.6.4 Challenges and Direction of Nano-Enhanced PCM

Most current studies on nano-enhanced phase change materials have focused on the material's thermal characteristics and its applications, most notably thermal energy for

storage in buildings and solar air heaters. Research has shown that nano-enhanced PCM has better heat conductivity than the original. This is a desirable quality in nano-enhanced PCM, since it will help reduce the impact of undesirable effects like subcooling. The latent heat behaviour of nano-enhanced PCM, however, seems to be the greatest amount of latent heat. Researchers need to resolve the inconsistencies in the results. More material is needed, particularly for the long-term thermal stability of phase change materials. Optimal PCM particle concentration should be determined to optimise thermal conductivity and latent heat characteristics. Repeated melting and solidifying operations may impact nanoparticle dispersion, crystalline structure of nano-enhanced phase change material, and thermal characteristics. Repulsive and attraction force cause PCM particle aggregation. During heating, the attraction force weakens and repulsive force increases. This decreases nanoparticle aggregation. Higher temperature increases repulsion. When liquid PCM solidifies, nanoparticles tend to agglomerate and silt. To alleviate this issue, shorten solidification time. If the solidification period is short, nanoparticles cannot move closer together or lower owing to gravity attraction. Researchers should do in-depth research on this topic. However, since the particles utilised are nano-scale, researchers should also emphasise the safety of nano-enhanced PCM on human health and the environment. To justify the use of nano-enhanced phase change material, a techno-economic study should be performed.

2.7 RECENT DEVELOPMENT ON (DP-SAH) AND RESEARCH GAP

In recent years, there have been notable advancements and developments in the field of Double-Pass Solar Air Heaters (DP-SAH). These advancements have aimed to enhance the performance, efficiency, and overall effectiveness of solar air heating systems. Table 2.3 represents the summary of recent development on double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with storage systems. Based on this table, there is no study has been conducted for increasing the thermal efficiency of the DP-SAH by adding nanomaterials to PCM (nano-enhanced PCM) as storage system along with staggered finned absorber as well. This combination has the potential to enhance heat transfer efficiency, increase thermal storage capacity, and improve overall system performance.

Table 2.2 The summary of nano-enhanced PCM and applications in recent researches.

Reference	Phase change material (PCM)	Nanoparticle type	Applications	Finding
Abdullah et al. (2022)	Paraffin wax	Copper oxide (CuO)	Solar stills for desalination of water application.	The new design of the finned trays solar still led to enlarge the evaporation of surface area of the finned (TSS) by 238% higher than conventional solar still (SS).
Karaağaç et al. (2021)	Paraffin wax	Aluminium oxide (Al ₂ O ₃)	A concentrated photovoltaic-thermal solar dryer (CPV/TSD) for mushroom drying.	it has been found that the thermal energy transferred to the nano-enhanced PCM prevents the decrease in greenhouse temperature for the first 100 min.
Algarni et al. (2020)	Paraffin wax	Nano-copper	Evacuated tube solar collectors with finned U-tube for domestic heating application.	The system can provide hot water up to 50 °C for about 2 hours longer than typical evacuated tube solar collector systems with a specific mass flow of 0.08 L/min.
Ali et al(2019) .	Paraffin wax	nano graphene (NG)	a cooling system for safety helmets that absorbs and stores heat to make the wearer feel cool and comfortable.	NG/paraffin composite PCM demonstrated a maximum of 146% increased thermal conductivity and a maximum of 3% reduced latent heat compared to conventional PCM. The composite PCM helmet can give thermal comfort for more than four hours at 35 °C.
Khan et al(2018) .	Paraffin wax	Aluminium nitride (AlN), Aluminium oxide (Al ₂ O ₃), Graphene nano-platelets (GnP).	Latent heat system with a shell and tube heat exchanger. In the heat exchanger's shell, nano-enhanced PCM was poured.	Al ₂ O ₃ , AlN, and GnP-based nano-PCM had higher charging rates than pure paraffin by 28.1%, 36.4%, and 44.5%, respectively.

Table 2.3 The summary of Recent development on double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH)

No.	Author	PCM Shape (Type)	Design configuration	Major finding
1	Sharol et al. (2022)	Square tubes (Paraffin wax)		<p>Thermal efficiency (DPSAH-CMA) of 68.23% for mass flow rate 0.005 kg/s at higher solar radiation of 900 W/m². The maximum outlet temperature of 46.2 °C</p>
2	Ismail et al. (2022)	-		<p>Lava rock as the porous media. Thermal efficiency (DPSAH) of 64% for mass flow rate 0.035 kg/s at higher solar radiation of 800 W/m². The temperature output range between 41.7 °C and 48.3 °C</p>
3	Sudhakar et al. (2021)	Spherical balls (Paraffin wax)		<p>Thermal efficiency (DPSAH) of 42.2%. The experiments were conducted with air mass flow rate of 0.009 kg/s. The outlet temperature of air between 43 °C and 55 °C</p>

to be continued...

...continuation

4 Salih et al. (2019)

Rectangular
(Paraffin wax)

Thermal efficiency (DPSAH) of 70.95%. The investigations were carried out at various airflow speed of (0.6, 0.9, 1.2, 1.5, and 1.8) kg/min and three solar irradiance intensities of 625, 725, and 825 W/m². The maximum output temperature 42.95 °C

5 Mahmood (2019)

Cavity
(Paraffin wax)

Thermal efficiency (DPSAH) of 56%. Experiments were carried out with and without using phase change material at a constant air mass flow rate of (0.0375 kg/sec). The maximum temperature 42°C

6 Sajawal et al. (2019)

Finned Tubes
(Paraffin wax)

Thermal efficiency (DP-SAHA) of 71.9%. A constant draft axial flow fan is used with the air mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s. The outlet temperature of air between 38 °C and 45 °C

2.8 POINT OF DEPARTURE

This research presented a critical review that can be summarized with some comments on solar air heating systems with storage units including the space heating systems, greenhouses with various thermal storage materials. Solar air heaters integrated with various storage materials or nanomaterials and heat transfer studies on air as a heat transfer fluid. Furthermore, the scientific comments from this review are as follows:

- The recent researches concentrated on the phase change materials (PCMs) especially organic paraffin wax as the thermal storage materials because these materials have higher thermal energy storage capacity.
- For a better thermal performance of the solar air heaters, a phase change material with high latent heat and with large surface area for heat transfer is required.
- Some recent studies focused on filling the porous media in the second channel in the double-pass air heater increased the outlet temperature of the system. The storage capacity such kind of the heaters were low and the thermal discharge was taken short time; this was the case due to the fact that the porous media is a sensible heat storage medium and cannot be compared with the latent heat storage medium.
- The researchers directed their works on the integration between the solar energy collection and the thermal storage such as solar air heaters to reduce the heat loss, the volume, and the system cost. Furthermore, no study has been conducted for increasing the thermal efficiency of the DP-SAH by adding nanomaterials.
- The environmental impact and economic aspects have not been covered well and there is a clear shortage of information. Moreover, nano-enhanced PCM storage in SAH have been investigated using simulations more than with experimental measurements, which justifies the need for more practical work to be carried out. However, most experimental studies were conducted outdoors, and so indoor experiments should also be conducted.
- Significant research in the field of SAHs is required regarding the thermal absorber design, material used, coating, insulation types, cost minimize, conserve energy, performance testing and control.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides a details of the systematic methodology employed to achieve the objectives outlined in Chapter I. The methodology encompasses theoretical and experimental approaches aimed at optimizing the impact of nano-enhanced PCM storage systems and fin designs on the conventional double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH). The configuration of the fins and the shape of the container housing the nano-enhanced PCM directly influence the thermal performance of the DP-SAH, and this chapter elucidates the research methods employed to enhance the thermal and thermo-hydraulic efficiencies of the proposed heater. A significant portion of this chapter is dedicated to an overview of the pilot study procedures and outcomes, as well as a description of the research design and activities pertaining to the theoretical and experimental setup. Figure 3.1 provides an overview of the analysis technique employed for the DP-SAH, featuring staggered fins in the absorber and a capsule containing nano-enhanced PCM. The figure encapsulates both the theoretical and experimental investigations conducted to achieve the research objectives.

3.2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.2.1 Phase 1: Overview

In this phase, an overview of critical, constructive analysis of the literature on solar air heaters through summary, classification, analysis, and comparison was conducted. The researchers reviewed the applications of nano-enhanced PCM on various kinds of solar heaters. It was found that nanotechnology reduced manufacturing costs in the

Figure 3.1 Overview of the DP-SAH with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM capsules analysis technique

field of economics as a result of using a low temperature process. Nanotechnology offers various advantages that can contribute to cost reduction in manufacturing processes. These advantages include:

- **Enhanced energy conversion efficiency:** Nanotechnology offers opportunities to improve the energy conversion efficiency of solar thermal systems. For example, nano-enhanced PCM or nano-coatings can enhance heat transfer efficiency, leading to higher overall system performance. This increased efficiency can reduce the required size and number of solar thermal heaters.
- **Increased durability and lifespan:** Nanomaterials can enhance the durability and longevity of solar air heaters, such as coatings or absorber surfaces, by providing improved resistance to corrosion, degradation, and environmental factors. By extending the lifespan of these components.
- **Improved material efficiency:** Nanomaterials can be used to enhance the efficiency of solar thermal collectors and absorbers by improving light absorption, heat transfer, and thermal insulation properties. By incorporating nano-materials into the design and fabrication of these components, manufacturers can achieve higher performance with reduced material usage, resulting in cost savings.

3.2.2 Phase 2: Theoretical Analysis

In this phase, theoretical studies were conducted to develop a model of the Double Pass Solar Air Heater (DP-SAH) with different upper channel depths (30, 50, 70, and 100 mm). The simulation tool, coupled with energy balance equations, was utilized to assess the heat transfer enhancement achieved by incorporating nanotechnology-enhanced PCM capsules with staggered fins. Figure 3.2 shows thermal resistance network for the DP-SAH.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the computer iteration method using MATLAB for the DP-SAH. The analysis involved estimating various conditions to initiate the iteration process. These conditions encompassed solar irradiance levels ranging from 400 W/m² to 1000 W/m², ambient temperature, and operational parameters such as mass flow rates varying from 0.01 kg/s to 0.05 kg/s. In order to simplify the analysis, other

Figure 3.2 The thermal resistance network for the proposed heater

parameters such as the thermal conductivity across the fins and absorber were assumed to be constant. The assumed temperature values were utilized to explore a range of heat transfer coefficients and thermo-physical properties. To obtain a solution, matrices $[M]$, $[T]$, and $[C]$ were generated using the assumed values. Subsequently, matrix $[M]$ was inverted, enabling the prediction of the mean temperature of the heater's components. The design of the fins and PCM aimed to maximize the utilization of the absorber plate and bottom plate surface area without compromising the pressure inside the air heater.

The back and edge insulation thickness of about 25 mm made from solid wood. Absorber plate and back or bottom plate made from aluminium and painted in black colour. The thickness of the glass cover is 5 mm and the absorber and back plate are 3.0 mm. The fin size is 100 mm \times 30 mm \times 3 mm and the nano-enhanced PCM

capsule's diameter is 42 mm. The cold air enters the upper duct from the blower and exits from lower the channel after the heating process inside the DP-SAH.

Figure 3.3 Computer iteration method using MATLAB.

3.2.3 Phase 3: Experimental Analysis

The experimental study involved several steps aimed at obtaining performance results for the DP-SAH with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM capsules. The

experiment was designed to examine the effects of mass flow rate, solar irradiance, temperature rise, and upper channel depth on the thermal performance of the DP-SAH. Additionally, the impact of integrating nano-enhanced PCM capsules with the DP-SAH during the charging and discharging process on system performance was investigated. The evaluation criteria for the research activities are outlined in Figure 3.4. To further validate the performance of the proposed heater, it was compared to three other configurations such as conventional DP-SAH, DP-SAH with fins and DP-SAH with nano-enhanced PCM. Different volume fraction values of nanoparticles (0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 vol.%) were selected for this study based on previous research findings (Al-Waeli, Chaichan, et al. 2017).

Figure 3.4 Block diagram of overall research activities performed in this research.

illustrates the details of the processes of synthesis and analysis that were presented. In order to determine the concentration ratio that results in the best nano-enhanced PCM, it is essential to generate several samples with variable concentrations. Each sample is subjected to a series of tests at varying temperatures to determine its thermo-physical properties such as thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, density, and viscosity. The sample with optimum properties is selected for large-scale production.

3.3 THE NANO-ENHANCED PCM SYNTHESIS METHOD

The two-step method is used to synthesize nano-enhanced PCM (Al-Waeli, Sopian, et al. 2017). To create the optimum volume fraction must be discovered for nano-enhanced PCM. Hence, different volume fractions are proposed which are 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 vol. %. The enhancement in thermo-physical properties is done using different thermo-physical property tests as shown in Figure 3.5. Different scanning methods for the characterization of the material are conducted such as Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). More details about the synthesis and the analysis may also be available in Chapter V. Figure 3.6

Figure 3.5 Nano-enhanced PCM synthesis technique

Figure 3.6 procedure synthesis of nano-enhanced PCM

3.4 THE ACCURACY ANALYSIS FOR MODEL VALIDATION METHOD

In general, error analysis is defined as the study and evaluation of uncertainty in measurement. It should be noted that previous experiences have proved no measurement, even carefully made, can be completely free of uncertainties because all the structures and equipment used for measuring might also have some errors; henceforth, the ability to calculate these errors and keep them at minimum level is considered important in the scientific studies. To compare the theoretical data with the experimental data, some basic formulas can be of use here.

3.4.1 The Sum of Square Error (SSE)

This is the most commonly used lack-of-fit indicator in statistical fitting procedures (Basunia et al. 2001; Queiroz et al. 2001; Sun 1999). It can be given as follows:

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^N (Val_{exp,i} - Val_{theo,i})^2 \quad \dots(3.1)$$

$Val_{exp,i}$ is the experimental value, $Val_{theo,i}$ is the predicted (numerical) value and N is the number of observations

3.4.2 The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

Is a frequently used measure of the difference between the actual observed values and predicted ones by a model or an estimator such as the one explained by Demir et al. (2004), Doymaz (2005) and Wang et al. (2007) and can be calculated by this formula:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Val_{exp,i} - Val_{theo,i})^2}{N}} \quad \dots(3.2)$$

or can be written as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{SSE}{N}} \quad \dots(3.3)$$

N represents the amount of data

3.5 EXPERIMENTAL ERROR AND UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS METHOD

In this empirical study, the measuring devices used were calibrated and an error analysis was conducted. Despite the careful attention given to the measurements, it is important to ensure the accuracy of the data and prevent measurement errors from affecting the experiments.

The sources of errors in this study are numerous and the analysis can be complex. To simplify the analysis, a combination of fixed error (bias) and random error (precision) is required to establish a reasonable limit for the errors. The precision, represented by a single number, should have a straightforward interpretation, such as the largest error expected under logical circumstances, and it should be useful without requiring a complex explanation. The error analysis, as defined by Alkilani (2013), should be conducted to address these considerations.

$$Q = \dot{m}_{air} c_{P-air} (T_o - T_i) \quad \dots(3.4)$$

$$\frac{\delta Q}{Q} \times 100\% = \left[\frac{\delta \dot{m}_{air}}{\dot{m}_{air}} + \frac{2\delta T}{(T_o - T_i)} \right] \times 100\% \quad \dots(3.5)$$

The error analysis in this empirical research was the mass flow rate of the air's error which was 2.8%, the temperature rise was in limit error of 0.3%, and the area of the heater according to the measurements was 2.2%, the pressure drop error of about 0.4%. Consequently, the total error of the system was 5.4%.

CHAPTER IV

MATHEMATICAL MODELING

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The schematic of the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM storage system is shown in Figure 4.1. The fundamental components of this system include: (i) the glass cover, (ii) the absorber plate, (iii) the fins, (iv) the nano-enhanced PCM capsules, (v) the back-plate, (vi) the heater housing, and (vii) the insulations. The cold air enters the system through the upper channel formed by the glass cover and absorber plate, and subsequently passes through the lower channel formed by the back plate and absorber plate containing fins and nano-enhanced PCM capsules.

Figure 4.1 The schematic of the (DP-SAH) with staggered fins absorber and nano- enhanced PCM storage system.

The lower channel of the system is comprised of fins attached to the back of the absorber plate and nano-enhanced PCM capsules positioned on the back plate. To prevent leakage and minimize heat loss, the back plate and sides of the proposed heater are effectively insulated and sealed. Both the upper and lower channels facilitate the flow of air to extract heat from the absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, and back plate. This chapter focuses on the theoretical modeling of the double-pass solar air heater incorporating fins and nano-enhanced PCM. A steady-state one-dimensional mathematical model was developed, which encompasses steady-state energy balance equations that establish relationships among the surface wind heat transfer coefficient and the heat transfer coefficients between the moving air streams and the surfaces comprising the upper and lower channels.

4.2 ENERGY BALANCE ON THE DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS AND NANO- ENHANCED PCM

In order to simplify the analysis, the energy balance equations (conservation of energy) for the glass cover, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, back plate, and working fluid (air) are formulated (Duffie et al. 2013) based on the following assumptions:

- The thermal performance of a studied heater is a steady state condition.
- The sky is considered as a black body for long wavelength irradiance at an equivalent sky temperature.
- Dust and dirt on the studied heater and shading of its absorbing-plate are negligible.
- Operating temperatures of the studied heater components, and mean air temperatures in the air channels are all assumed to be uniform.
- The side losses are negligible and leakage of air to or from the studied heater is negligible.
- The drop of temperature through the glass cover, absorber plate and bottom plate are negligible.
- The effects of static and dynamic friction in the channels are neglected.
- The temperature of the cylindrical container surface is almost equal to the back plate.

- The thermal conductivity of the macro-encapsulated nano-PCM is neglected, meaning that the temperature of the nano-enhanced PCM is assumed to be equal to the surface temperature of the cylinder.
- The temperatures of the fluids vary mainly in the direction of the flow i.e. along the x-axis for the air flow and the average bulk temperature of the fluid for each segment was then determined using the arithmetic average equation.

In order to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the performance of the new design, energy-balance equations are employed to model the design and simulate its energy performance based on a specified set of input data. This chapter presents the energy-balance equations for the double-pass solar air heater incorporating fins and nano-enhanced PCM. Figure 4.2 illustrates a schematic sectional view of the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM, which serves as the focal point of this study.

Figure 4.2 The schematic of heat transfer coefficients of the DP-SAH with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM.

The physical equations governing the performance of the studied double-pass solar air heater system is formulated using the energy balance equations of the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM components. The mean air temperature is.

$$T_f = (T_o + T_i)/2 \quad \dots(4.1)$$

The temperatures of inlet and outlet fluid are denoted using T_i and T_o , respectively. The heat transfer coefficients are detailed in Figure 4.2 from which the steady-state, one-dimensional, energy balance equations are derived and are written as follows:

Firstly, the heat energy balance for the glass cover (g) is represented by equation (4.2):

$$U_t (T_g - T_a) + h_1 (T_g - T_{f1}) = h_{rpg} (T_p - T_g) + \alpha_g I_T \quad \dots(4.2)$$

U_t , h , α and I_T represent the top loss coefficient, heat transfer coefficient, absorptivity and solar irradiance, respectively. While, small letters g, a, f1, p and b denote glass, ambient, fluid first air channel, absorber plate and back plate, respectively. Secondly, the heat energy balance for the first air channel is provided in equation (4.3):

$$q_1 = h_1 (T_g - T_{f1}) + h_2 (T_p - T_{f1}) \quad \dots(4.3)$$

Thirdly, the heat energy balance for the absorber plate is provided in equation (4.4):

$$h_{rpg} (T_p - T_g) + h_2 (T_p - T_{f1}) + h_{rpb} (T_p - T_b) + h_3 (T_p - T_{f2}) + \frac{N_{fin}}{A_H} Q_{fin} = \alpha_g \tau_g I_T \quad \dots(4.4)$$

τ_g , N_{fin} and Q_{fin} represent the transmissivity of the glass cover, the number of fins and the heat transfer rate of the fin, respectively. While the heat energy balance for the second air channel is shown in the equation below:

$$q_2 = h_3 (T_p - T_{f2}) + h_5 (T_b - T_{f2}) + \frac{N_{fin}}{A_H} Q_{fin} + \frac{N_{Nano}}{A_H} Q_{Nano} \quad \dots(4.5)$$

The heat energy balance for the back plate is presented in equation (4.6):

$$h_{rpb} (T_p - T_b) = h_5 (T_b - T_{f2}) + U_b (T_b - T_a) + \frac{N_{Nano}}{A_H} Q_{Nano} \quad \dots(4.6)$$

h_{rpb} , N_{Nano} and Q_{Nano} denote the radiative coefficient from absorber plate to back plate and nano-enhanced PCM capsules, the number of nano-PCM capsules and the heat transfer rate of the nano-PCM capsules respectively.

$$q_1 = 2 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air} (T_{f1} - T_i) / W_H L_H \quad \dots(4.7)$$

$$q_2 = 2 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air} (T_{f2} - 2T_{f1} + T_i) / W_H L_H \quad \dots(4.8)$$

c_{p-air} , \dot{m}_{air} , W_H and L_H represent Constant pressure- specific heat of the air, mass flow rate of working fluid, Width and Length of the heater respectively. Convection heat transfer energy of the nano-enhanced phase change material capsule Q_{Nano} is calculated from the following equation :

$$Q_{Nano} = \left[\rho_{Nano} \times c_{p-Nano} \times V_{Nano} (T_{Nano} - T_{f2}) + m_{Nano} \times H_L \right] / \Delta t \quad \dots(4.9)$$

c_{p-Nano} , ρ_{Nano} , V_{Nano} , m_{Nano} , H_L and T_{Nano} denote constant pressure-specific heat of nano-PCM, density of nano-PCM, volume of nano-enhanced PCM capsule, mass of nano-PCM, latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM and temperature of nano-enhanced PCM capsule respectively. The calculation of the heat transfer through the conduction rate of fins from equations. (10) and (11) are used (Fudholi et al. 2013a; Ho et al. 2011):

$$Q_{fin} = \left[2 h_4 k_p A_{fin} L_{fin} \right]^{1/2} (T_p - T_{f2}) \tanh(KH_{fin}) \quad \dots(4.10)$$

$$K = \left(\frac{2 h_4 L_{fin}}{k_p A_{fin}} \right)^{1/2} \quad \dots(4.11)$$

4.3 HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENTS

In this study, the heat transfer coefficients have been chosen from a wide range of literature sources that cover various shapes and configurations. The summarized heat transfer coefficients are provided below.

4.3.1 Wind Induced External Heat Transfer Coefficient for a Flat Surface

The problem of heat transfer from the heater cover is one of the least understood of heat transfer phenomena. Mcadams (1954) suggested a correlation for the convective heat transfer coefficient of a plate as:

$$h_w = 5.7 + 3.0 v_w \quad \dots(4.12)$$

v_w is the wind speed in m/s. It is possible that the effect of free convection and radiation be included in equation (4.12). For this reason, Watmuff et al. (1977) reported and Duffie et al. (2013) recommended that the equation should be:

$$h_w = 2.8 + 3.0 v_w \quad \dots(4.13)$$

The heat transfer coefficient due to wind can be determined from the correlation developed by Sparrow et al. (1979).

$$Nu_w = 0.0158 Re^{0.8} \quad \dots(4.14)$$

Stultz (1979) suggested the following equation for the heat transfer coefficient of wind-induced flow

$$h_w = 1.247 [(T_g - T_a) \cos \beta]^{\frac{1}{3}} + 2.658 v_w \quad \dots(4.15)$$

β is the slope and T_g and T_a are the cover and ambient temperature respectively. Generally, the value obtained using McAdam's correlation was rough twice that given by the other three correlations. Unless otherwise stated. McAdam's correlation is employed in the current study.

4.3.2 Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient Between Parallel Plates

The force convective heat transfer coefficient depends on the Reynolds number of the flow. The flow can be divided into three regimes namely: the laminar flow regime ($Re < 2300$), the transition flow regime ($2300 < Re < 6000$), and the turbulent flow regime ($Re > 6000$).

a. Laminar Flow Regime (Re < 2300)

Heaton et al. (1964) proposed the following empirical correlation for the local Nusselt number for laminar flow between two parallel flat plates with one side insulated and the other subjected to constant heat flux

$$N_u = 5.4 + \frac{0.00190 \left[Re Pr \left(\frac{D_h}{L_H} \right) \right]^{1.71}}{1 + 0.00563 \left[Re Pr \left(\frac{D_h}{L_H} \right) \right]^{1.17}} \quad \dots(4.16)$$

For non-circular ducts, the tube diameter is replaced by the hydraulic or equivalent diameter as:

$$D_h = \frac{4 A_H}{Perimeter} = \frac{4 W_H d}{2 (W_H + d)} \quad \dots(4.17)$$

For the flow between parallel flat plates, the equivalent diameter is twice the separation distance between the plates.

b. Transition Flow Regime (2300 < Re < 6000)

Hausen (1943) presented the following empirical correlation for the average Nusselt number between the beginning of the heated section and position L for the flow in a tube.

$$N_u = 0.116 \left(R_e^{\frac{2}{3}} - 125 \right) Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[1 + \left(\frac{D_h}{L_H} \right)^{2/3} \right] \left(\frac{\mu_{air}}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14} \quad \dots(4.18)$$

μ is evaluated at the film temperature and μ_w is evaluated at the wall temperature.

c. Turbulent Flow Regime (Re > 6000)

Tan et al. (1970) recommended that for flat plate solar air heater, the heat transfer in the fully developed turbulent flow regime should be obtained from the relationship

$$N_u = 0.018 R_e^{0.8} Pr^{0.4} \quad \dots(4.19)$$

For $9500 < Re < 22000$

For situations involving a substantial property variation, the Sieder et al. (1936) equation may be employed

$$N_u = 0.027 Re^{0.8} Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu_{air}}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14} \quad \dots(4.20)$$

For flow in smooth pipes where $Re > 10000$ and $L_H/D_{th} > 60$. A more accurate correlation that is also applicable to rough ducts was developed by Petukhov (1970).

$$N_u = \left(\frac{Re Pr}{X} \right) \left(\frac{f}{8} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{air}}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14} \quad \dots(4.21)$$

$10^4 < Re < 5 \times 10^8$, $X = 1.07 + 12.7 \left(Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1 \right) \left(f/8 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, $n = 0.11$ (heating with uniform T_w), $n = 0.25$ (cooling with uniform T_w) and $n = 0$ (uniform wall heat flux). The friction factor for smooth tubes in the above equation can be obtained from

$$f = (1.82 \log(Re) - 1.64)^{-2} \quad \dots(4.22)$$

d. Entrance Region ($L_H/D_{th} < 60$)

In the entrance region of a flow, a higher heat transfer coefficient is typically anticipated. Tan et al. (1970) conducted studies on the impact of thermal entrance region on turbulent forced convective heat transfer within an asymmetrically heated, rectangular duct with uniform heating. They derived an expression for the mean Nusselt Number, which characterizes the average convective heat transfer rate in the system.

$$N_u = 5.4 \left(1 + \frac{S D_h}{L_H} \right) \quad \dots(4.23)$$

S is represented as follows

$$3.57 < \frac{L_H}{D_h} \leq 60 \quad S = 14.3 \log \left(\frac{L_H}{D_h} \right) - 7.9 \quad \dots(4.24a)$$

$$\frac{L_H}{D_h} > 60 \quad S = 17.53 \quad \dots(4.24b)$$

It should be noted here that $S \approx 0$ when $L_H / D_h \approx 3.57$. This range of the Reynolds Number covered in their studies was from 9500 to 22000. Nusselt (1931) recommended the use of:

$$N_u = 0.036 R_e^{0.8} \text{Pr}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{D_h}{L_H} \right)^{0.055} \quad \dots(4.25)$$

at the entrance region for $10 < L_H / D_h < 400$

4.3.3 Radiative Heat Transfer Coefficient

To retain the simplicity of linear equation it is convenient to define radiation heat transfer coefficient. The rate of heat transfer by radiation between two arbitrary surfaces is given as follows:

$$Q_1 = -Q_2 = \frac{\sigma(T_2^4 - T_1^4)}{\frac{1 - \varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_1 A_1} + \frac{1}{A_1 F_{12}} + \frac{1 - \varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_2 A_2}} \quad \dots(4.26)$$

The heat transfer coefficient is defined as :

$$Q = A_1 h_r (T_2 - T_1) \quad \dots(4.27)$$

From equations (4.26) and (4.27), the radiative heat transfer coefficient is

$$h_r = \frac{\sigma (T_2^2 + T_1^2) (T_2 + T_1)}{\frac{1 - \varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_1} + \frac{1}{F_{12}} + A_1 \left(\frac{1 - \varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_2 A_2} \right)} \quad \dots(4.28)$$

Two special cases of equation (4.28) are of particular interest for this study: radiative heat transfer between two parallel plates and heat transfer from cover to the sky.

a. Radiative Heat Transfer Coefficient Between Parallel Plates

For radiative heat transfer between two infinite parallel plates such as the case for a flat plate heater where A_1 and A_2 are equal and the view factor F_{12} is unity, the following equation is obtained

$$h_{r12} = \frac{\sigma (T_2^2 + T_1^2) (T_2 + T_1)}{\frac{1}{\varepsilon_1} - \frac{1}{\varepsilon_2} - 1} \quad \dots(4.29)$$

b. Radiative Heat Transfer Coefficient from Glass to the Sky

The second special case is for a small convex object (surface 1) surrounded by a large enclosure (surface 2, blackbody $\varepsilon_2=1$). Under these, the Area ratio A_1 and A_2 are equal and the view factor F_{12} is unity and equation (4.28) become:

$$h_{r12} = \varepsilon_1 \sigma (T_2^2 + T_1^2) (T_2 + T_1) \quad \dots(4.30)$$

To predict the performance of a solar heater it will be necessary to evaluate the radiation exchange between a surface and the sky. The sky can be considered as a blackbody at an equivalent sky temperature T_{sky} , so the actual net radiative heat transfer between the horizontal flat plate and the sky is given as:

$$h_{r12} = \varepsilon A \sigma (T^4 - T_{sky}^4) (T_2 + T_1) \quad \dots(4.31)$$

To calculate T_{sky} several correlations are developed. Swinbank (1963) recommends the following relationship:

$$T_{sky} = 0.0552 T_a^{1.5} \quad \dots(4.32)$$

Berdahi et al. (1984) used extensive data from the United States to relate the effective sky temperature to dew point temperature, dry bulb temperature, and hour from midnight by the following equation:

$$T_{sky} = T_a \left[0.711 + 0.0056 T_{dp} + 0.000073 T_{dp}^2 + 0.013 \cos(15t) \right]^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad \dots(4.33)$$

Duffie et al. (2013) suggested the following simple relationship between the temperature of the sky (T_{sky}) and ambient temperature (T_a)

$$T_{sky} = T_a - 6 \quad \dots(4.34)$$

4.3.4 Overall Top Heat Transfer Coefficient

The overall top heat loss coefficient may be obtained from

$$U_t = \left(\frac{1}{h_w + h_{rGS}} \right) \quad \dots(4.35)$$

where h_w is the convective heat transfer coefficient from the glass cover to wind and h_{rGS} is the radiative heat transfer coefficient from the glass cover to the sky.

4.3.5 Conduction from the Bottom of the Surface

The bottom heat loss coefficient is

$$U_b = \frac{1}{\sum_1^n \left(\frac{x_{bi}}{k_{bi}} \right) + \frac{1}{h_w}} \quad \dots(4.36)$$

x_{bi} is the thickness of the insulation, k_{bi} is its thermal conductivity and h_w is the convective heat transfer coefficient from the heater to the surrounding.

4.4 THERMO-PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

The thermo-physical properties of air are assumed to vary linearly with temperature because of the low-temperature range to be encountered. The temperature is in K) equations for viscosity (μ_f), density (ρ_f), thermal conductivity (k_f) and specific heat are as follows by (Fudholi et al. 2018); Ong (1995)

The viscosity of air is expressed as:

$$\mu_{air} = [1.983 + 0.00184(T - 300)] \times 10^{-5} \quad \dots(4.37)$$

The air density is expressed as:

$$\rho_{air} = 1.1774 - 0.00359 (T - 300) \quad \dots(4.38)$$

The thermal conductivity of air is expressed as:

$$k_{air} = 0.02624 + 0.0000758 (T - 300) \quad \dots(4.39)$$

Specific heat of air is expressed as:

$$c_{p-air} = 1005.7 + 0.000066 (T - 300) \quad \dots(4.40)$$

4.5 SOLUTION OF MATRIX

In current study, the equations (4.2)-(4.10) above can be written in a 5×5 matrix $i \leq 5$ and $j \leq 5$ from energy balance equations.

$$[M_{ij}] [T_j] = [B_j] \quad \dots(4.42)$$

For M_{ij} represents the temperature coefficients M_{11} to M_{55} and C_j are constants C_1 to C_5 in all heat balance equations

$$C_1 = U_t T_a + \alpha_g I_T \quad \dots(4.43)$$

$$C_2 = \left[\frac{-2 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air}}{W_H L_H} \right] T_i \quad \dots(4.44)$$

$$C_3 = \alpha_g \tau_g I_T \quad \dots(4.45)$$

$$C_4 = -C_2 \quad \dots(4.46)$$

$$C_5 = U_b T_a \quad \dots(4.47)$$

$$M_{11} = h_1 + h_{rpg} + U_t \quad \dots(4.48)$$

$$M_{22} = - \left[h_1 + h_2 + \left(\frac{2 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air}}{W_H L_H} \right) \right] \quad \dots(4.49)$$

$$M_{33} = h_2 + h_3 + h_{rpg} + h_{rpb} + \frac{N_{fin}}{A_H} [2 h_4 k_p A_{fin} L_{fin}]^{1/2} \tanh(KH_{fin}) \quad \dots(4.50)$$

$$M_{34} = - \left[h_3 + \frac{N_{fin}}{A_H} [2 h_4 k_p A_{fin} L_{fin}]^{1/2} \tanh(KH_{fin}) \right] \quad \dots(4.51)$$

$$M_{42} = \frac{4 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air}}{W_H L_H} \quad \dots(4.52)$$

$$M_{43} = -M_{34} \quad \dots(4.53)$$

$$M_{44} = - \left[h_3 + h_5 + \frac{2 \dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air}}{W_H L_H} + \frac{N_{fin}}{A_H} [2 h_4 k_p A_{fin} L_{fin}]^{1/2} \tanh(KH_{fin}) \right] - \frac{N_{Nano}}{A_H} [\rho_{Nano} \times c_{p-Nano} \times V_{Nano} - m_{Nano} \times H_L] / \Delta t \quad \dots(4.54)$$

$$M_{45} = h_5 + \frac{N_{Nano}}{A_H} [\rho_{Nano} \times c_{p-Nano} \times V_{Nano} + m_{Nano} \times H_L] / \Delta t \quad \dots (4.55)$$

$$M_{54} = M_{45} \quad \dots(4.56)$$

$$M_{55} = - [h_5 + h_{rpb} + U_b] - \frac{N_{Nano}}{A_H} [\rho_{Nano} \times c_{p-Nano} \times V_{Nano} - m_{Nano} \times H_L] / \Delta t \quad \dots(4.57)$$

The elements of matrix can be presented from M_{11} to M_{55} and C_1 to C_5 for T_g , T_{f1} , T_p , T_{f2} and T_b as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & -h_1 & -h_{rpg} & 0 & 0 \\ h_1 & M_{22} & h_2 & 0 & 0 \\ -h_{rpg} & -h_2 & M_{33} & M_{34} & -h_{rpb} \\ 0 & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} & M_{45} \\ 0 & 0 & h_{rpb} & M_{54} & M_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_g \\ T_{f1} \\ T_p \\ T_{f2} \\ T_b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots(4.58)$$

The various convective heat transfer coefficient as well as various radiative heat transfer coefficients depend on the value of the glass, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, back plate and air temperature at any point along the channel. It is, therefore, necessary to assume a value for the set of solution data and then check the validity of this set by iteration. The iteration is continued until the difference between two successive values of the temperatures is less than 0.1%.

4.6 PRESSURE DROP AND FRICTION FACTOR

The required fan power to maintain a constant flow rate is a function of the flow velocity, air properties and hydraulic diameter of the air passage channel and length of the heater (L_H). The pressure drop across each flow channel is obtained by using the following relationship (Hollands et al. 1981):

$$\Delta P = \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{air}}{A_{ap}} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\rho_{air}} \left(\frac{L_H}{D_h} \right)^3 f \quad \dots(4.59)$$

A_{ap} is the air passage area of the air ($L_H \times d$) and f is the friction factor for different Reynolds numbers are determined from the following equations:

For $Re < 2550$

$$f = \frac{24}{Re} + 0.9 \left(\frac{d}{L_H} \right) \quad \dots(4.60)$$

For $2550 < Re < 10^4$

$$f = 0.0094 + 2.92 Re^{-0.15} \left(\frac{d}{L_H} \right) \quad \dots(4.61)$$

For $10^4 < Re < 10^5$

$$f = 0.059Re^{-0.2} + 0.73 \left(\frac{d}{L_H} \right) \quad \dots(4.62)$$

The total pressure drops (ΔP) for the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM can be calculated from the following:

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_{ch1} + \Delta P_{ch2} \quad \dots(4.63)$$

4.7 THERMAL EFFICIENCY

The thermal or energy efficiency of the double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM is as follows:

$$\eta_{en} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air} \int (T_o - T_i) dt}{A_H \int I_T dt} \quad \dots(4.64)$$

\dot{m}_f is the air mass flow rate, c_{p-air} is the specific heat of the air, A_H is the area of the studied heater T_o and T_i is the outlet and inlet temperature, and I_T is the solar irradiance. When conditions remain constant throughout a specified time period (Duffie et al. 2013), the efficiency reduces to:

$$\eta_{en} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} c_{p-air} (T_o - T_i)}{I_T \times A_H} = \frac{Q_u}{I_T \times A_H} \quad \dots(4.65)$$

Q_u is useful energy gain, I_T is solar irradiance and A_H is Area of the proposed heater equal to $(L_H \times W_H)$.

4.8 THERMO-HYDRAULIC EFFICIENCY

The thermo-hydraulic efficiency (η_{th}) of the proposed double solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM can be expressed as (Matheswaran et al. 2018):

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{(Q_u - W_{fan})}{I_T \times A_H} \quad \dots(4.66)$$

W_{fan} is fan power required for forcing the working fluid throughout the proposed heater can be calculated from the following relation:

$$W_{fan} = \frac{P_p}{\eta_{fan} \times \eta_{motor}} \quad \dots(4.67)$$

η_{fan} is the fan efficiency and η_{motor} is the motor efficiency is taken equal to 0.9. The pumping power can be defined as:

$$P_p = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} \Delta P}{\rho_{air}} \quad \dots(4.68)$$

4.9 EXERGY ANALYSIS

Exergy analysis is carried out to provide a rational and meaningful assessment of the system performance by utilizing the second law of thermodynamics. The main advantage of the exergy analysis is that it provides detailed information on energy losses occurring in the process; allowing manufacturers to optimize the performance of the proposed heater.

Saidur et al. (2012) reviewed and classified solar energy applications based on the second law of thermodynamics and emphasized the importance of such analysis, while Yazdanifard et al. (2018) presented a comprehensive review of exergy analysis of photovoltaic-thermal technology.

Understanding the exergy of this heater helps in assessing its performance and aids in the process of comparing it to other double-pass solar air heaters. However, such a comparison can be made by equalizing the Reynolds number, and motor losses, or by comparing the heater to another with an equal heater area. The evaluation criteria used in this study are exergy efficiency and Improvement Potential (IP).

Gool (1997) proposed a concept, termed maximum improvement in the exergy efficiency, which is achieved when exergy destruction is minimized for the system. According to Gool (1997), this term is described in equation (4.69). The improvement potential (IP) can be useful in the analysis of various economic sectors or processes.

$$IP = (1 - \eta_{ex}) \dot{E}x_d \quad \dots(4.69)$$

η_{ex} and $\dot{E}x_d$ are exergy efficiency and exergy destruction, respectively. The exergy efficiency can be written based on the second law of thermodynamics as the ratio of the absorbed exergy of air divided by the exergy of solar irradiance on the double-pass solar air heater:

$$\eta_{ex} = \frac{\dot{E}x_{o,p}}{\dot{E}x_i} = 1 - \frac{\dot{E}x_d}{\dot{E}x_i} \quad \dots(4.70)$$

The parameters of this equation are defined as:

$$\dot{E}x_d = \dot{E}x_i + \dot{E}x_w - \dot{E}x_o \quad \dots(4.71)$$

$$\dot{E}x_o = \dot{m}_{air} \left[c_{p-air} (T_o - T_i) - T_a \left(c_{v-air} \ln \left(\frac{T_o}{T_i} \right) - R \ln \left(\frac{\rho_{o-air}}{\rho_{i-air}} \right) \right) \right] \quad \dots(4.72)$$

$\dot{E}x_{o,p}$ is exergy output considering the pressure drop of the proposed heater is computed by:

$$\dot{E}x_{o,p} = \dot{E}x_o - \dot{E}x_w \quad \dots(4.73)$$

$$\dot{E}x_w = \frac{T_a}{T_i} W_{fan} \quad \dots(4.74)$$

$$W_{fan} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} \times \Delta P}{\rho \times \eta_{fan}} \quad \dots(4.75)$$

η_{fan} is the fan motor efficiency is taken equal to 90%. The input exergy ($\dot{E}x_i$) is calculated by:

$$\dot{E}x_i = A_H \times I \times \left[1 - \frac{4}{3} \times \left(\frac{T_a}{T_s} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \times \left(\frac{T_a}{T_s} \right)^4 \right] \quad \dots(4.78)$$

T_a and T_s represent the ambient temperature and solar intensity temperature. For the solar intensity is assumed to be 6000K.

CHAPTER V

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter details the design, fabrication, instrumentation, data acquisition system, facilities, and laboratory equipment required for testing the DP-SAH utilizing staggered fins and multiple capsules nano-enhanced PCM. The laboratory test is important because several parameters are easily controlled to study the effect of the other parameters on the DP-SAH thermal storage performance, the lab test can be used for monitoring the nano-enhanced PCM behaviour during discharging processes. The parameters involved in this laboratory test include the air mass flow rates, solar irradiance levels and temperatures (inlet, outlet, environment, glass cover, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM, back plate and air along the heater). The experimental study will be discussed under the following subheadings:

- The studied solar air heater setup.
- The encapsulation process for nano-enhanced PCM.
- Equipment and experimental works.
- Measurement tools

5.2 DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER SETUP

Figure 5.1 represents the proposed DP-SAH in 3-D drawing and Figure 5.2 shows a photograph of DP-SAH. The glass cover, top duct, absorber, bottom duct, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, back plate, and insulation are all shown in the diagrams. The air will enter the top duct and move towards the lower duct before returning to the exit, as shown in the diagrams. Convection will absorb the heat from the absorber plate, and heat loss will be avoided by utilizing a glass cover and maintaining a tight

fit. The heat from the absorber will be absorbed by the fins linked to the rear of the absorber plate via conduction, allowing more heat to flow into the air. As air travels through the bottom air duct, the nano-enhanced PCM capsules absorb heat. Table 5.1 lists the materials used to construct the heater, as well as its dimensions and specifications.

Figure 5.1 3-D drawing of double pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM.

Figure 5.2 Photograph of double pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM.

5.2.1 Nano-enhanced PCM Capsules

The design and dimensions of the nano-enhanced PCM capsules are depicted in Figure 5.3, while a photograph of the capsules is presented in Figure 5.4. In this study, Paraffin Wax is chosen as the PCM due to its high heat capacity, allowing it to absorb and release significant amounts of energy during the charging and discharging cycle while maintaining relatively constant temperatures. Paraffin wax enables performance optimization by providing thermal energy during periods of cloudiness and at night, making it suitable for applications that require thermal energy storage, such as air conditioning or space heating. The parameters of the tested Paraffin Wax are outlined in Table 5.2. To enhance the thermal conductivity of the PCM, nanoparticles are incorporated into it. In this study, silicon carbide (SiC) is utilized as the nanoparticle to enhance the phase change material (Paraffin Wax). The specifications of the silicon carbide (SiC) nanoparticle used are detailed in Table 5.3.

Table 5.1 Specification of the DP-SAH with fins and nano-enhanced PCM components (Assadeg et al. 2021; Assadeg et al. 2023).

Component	Materials	Parameter	Value	Unit
Top Glass	glass	Thickness	5	mm
Upper Channel	-	Height	Adjustable	mm
		Width	0.3	m
		Length	1.0	m
Absorber	Aluminum	Thickness	3.0	mm
Lower Channel	-	Height	100	mm
		Width	0.3	m
		Length	1	m
Fins	Aluminum	Number	23	-
		Height	30	mm
		Width	3	mm
		Length	100	mm
Nano-PCM capsules	Stainless Steel	Number	23	-
		Length	29.2	cm
		Diameter	42	mm
		Thickness	2.0	mm
Back-plate	Stainless Steel	Thickness	3	mm
Insulation	Rock wool	Thickness	25	mm

Figure 5.3 Configuration of nano-enhanced PCM capsules with a diameter of 4.2 cm and 29.2 cm length.

Figure 5.4 Photograph of nano-enhanced PCM capsules with a diameter of 4.2 cm and 29.2 cm length.

Table 5.2 The thermo-physical properties (characteristics) of the used paraffin wax.

Material Properties	Unit	Range
Melting point	°C	45
Latent heat	kJ/kg	195
Thermal conductivity	W/m. °C	0.21
Liquid state density	Kg/m ³	831
Liquid state-specific heat	kJ/kg. °C	2.1
Solid state density	Kg/m ³	930
Solid state-specific heat	kJ/kg. °C	2.1

Table 5.3 The specifications of the pure nanoparticle (SiC).

Item	Unit	Specification
Manufacturer	-	US Research Nanomaterial, Inc.
Appearance	-	Grayish white powder
PH value	-	3-7 at 20 °C
Grain size	nm	45-65 nm
Density	kg/m ³	3220
Thermal conductivity	W/m.K	370-490
Melting point	°C	2730
Molar point	g/mole	40.1
Zeta potential	mV	27.8
Lose on drying	% ≤	0.21
Purity	+ %	99
Crystal and Type	-	Cubic

5.2.2 Staggered rectangular fins

The fins' purpose is to enhance the surface of heat flow, allowing heat to be transferred from the absorber plate to the fins via conduction and then to working fluid (the air) via convection. Figure 5.4 shows the design, dimensions, and configuration of the fins as well as the Photograph of the fins in experimental setup as shown in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5 Configuration of fins on the lower duct with height 30 mm and length 100 mm each.

Figure 5.6 Photograph of fins on the lower duct with height 30 mm and length 100 mm each.

5.3 SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISATION OF NANO-ENHANCED PCM

There are two methods of synthesizing nano-enhanced PCM which are the one-step method and the two-step method. One-step method: In this approach, the nanoparticles are directly synthesized or dispersed within the PCM during its fabrication process. Typically, the PCM and nanoparticles are mixed together, and the heat or mechanical energy is applied to disperse the nanoparticles uniformly within the PCM matrix. This method offers the advantage of simplicity and ease of implementation as it combines the PCM synthesis and nanoparticle dispersion into a single step. This study will utilize the two-step method which involves forming the nanoparticles and then dispersing them in the melted PCM (melted paraffin wax in the current study), as appose to making and dispersing them in the melted PCM concurrently (Jawad et al. 2020). Once these nanoparticles are dispersed an aggregation companied by clustering which will appear as a reaction. The nanoparticles are synthesized in dry form (powder) then they are dispersed in the melted PCM.

The two-step method is chosen because it is cheaper as it is easier to provide nanoparticles from the market. Due to the reaction that happens between nanoparticles and melted PCM, sedimentation of the particles will happen at the bottom of the container (Li et al. 2022; Sharma et al. 2011; Sharma et al. 2014). This means that obtaining a homogeneous dispersion requires high shear and ultrasound techniques.

This requires the use of an ultrasonic device. The nanoparticle volume fraction (\emptyset) is calculated through the following equation:

$$\emptyset\% = \left(\frac{m_p/\rho_p}{m_p/\rho_p + m_{PCM}/\rho_{PCM}} \right) \quad \dots(5.1)$$

$\emptyset\%$ is the nanoparticle volume fraction in percentage; m_p is the weight of nanoparticles and ρ_p is the density of nanoparticles, while m_{PCM} and ρ_{PCM} are the weight of melted PCM and density of melted PCM respectively. The equation illustrates how weight and density are significant factors for both the nanoparticle and the melted PCM. The weight of the two was determined using an analytical balance (AND-EJ610) as shown in Figure 5.7. First, the measurement is taken with the glass container left empty, and then the nanoparticles are added to the measurement. This will assist in providing more accurate quantification of the nanoparticles and melted PCM. Once weights were identified, nanoparticles were added to the melted paraffin wax (PCM). More comprehensive details pertaining to the analytical balance device, encompassing its precision and other pertinent information, can be found in Appendix I: sub-section (1). The telsonic ultrasonic CT-12, ultrasonic shaker as shown in Figure 5.8 was then used. The device was programmed to run for one hour with perfect shaking, which ensured minimal sedimentation and optimal dispersion, as well as the formation of a uniform and stable suspension. Further information regarding the telsonic ultrasonic CT-12 device, including its accuracy and other relevant details, in Appendix I: sub-section (2).

Figure 5.7 Analytical balance (AND-EJ610) used to quantify nanoparticles and melted PCM.

Figure 5.8 The telsonic ultrasonics CT-12, ultrasonic bath 12 litter.

The nanoparticle was measured at temperatures ranging from 25°C to 60°C at volume concentrations of (0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 vol.%). A Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM) and an X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) were used. FESEM and XRD analyses were carried out at UKM University's Makmal Morfologi Crim laboratory and Makmal Pencirian Fizikal laboratory, respectively. FESEM is commonly used to determine the size of these nanoparticles. While XRD is a non-destructive analytical technique used to determine the crystal structure, chemical composition, and physical properties of materials and thin films. A FESEM microscope has a field emission source that releases electrons. In a zig-zag pattern, these electrons scan an object. FESEM was done on 50 millilitres of the sample after the nano-enhanced PCM were created. Figures 5.9 and 5.10 demonstrate the FESEM of SiC and nano-enhanced PCM (SiC-enhanced Paraffin wax), respectively. The SiC-enhanced paraffin wax sample was also subjected to an Electron Dispersion X-ray (EDX) picture and an Electron Dispersion Spectroscopy (EDS). EDX and EDS are simple but effective procedures for determining the morphological composition of substances with less than one cubic micron in size. This equipment is attached to a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to help acquire elemental information from the sample under inspection. This approach is non-destructive and has a 0.1% sensitivity to heavier elements than carbon. The tests of XRD (X-ray diffraction), FESEM (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy), EDX (Electron-Dispersive X-ray

Spectroscopy), and EDS (Electron -Dispersive Spectroscopy) should be conducted for several reasons:

- **XRD:** X-ray diffraction helps determine the crystal structure and composition of materials. It provides information about the crystalline phases present, crystallinity, lattice parameters, and grain size, which are essential for material characterization.
- **FESEM:** Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy allows for high-resolution imaging of the sample surface. It provides detailed information about the surface morphology, topography, and the presence of any defects or irregularities.
- **EDX:** Electron-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy is used to identify and quantify the elemental composition of the sample. It detects characteristic X-ray emissions from different elements present in the material, providing information about its chemical composition.
- **EDS:** Electron-Dispersive Spectroscopy is similar to EDX and is often used interchangeably. It is also used to analyze the elemental composition of a sample by detecting characteristic X-ray emissions.

By performing these tests, researchers can gather valuable information about the material's structure, composition, surface characteristics, and elemental makeup. This information is crucial for understanding the material's properties, assessing its quality, and evaluating its suitability for specific applications. Figures 5.11, 5.12 and 5.13 show the EDX, EDS, and XRD results for (0.5 vol. %) of the nano-enhanced PCM sample, respectively.

Figure 5.9 FESEM image of the Silicon carbide (SiC) nanoparticle sample

Figure 5.10 FESEM image of the nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) sample

Figure 5.11 EDX image of nano- enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) sample

Figure 5.12 EDS image of nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) sample.

Figure 5.13 XRD image of nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) sample.

5.4 THERMO-PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF NANO-ENHANCED PCM

The thermo-physical property tests of the nano-PCM are shown in this section. Several tests were carried out on the nano-PCM samples. The heat transfer coefficient of these samples was determined by these procedures. As a result, several characteristics must be examined, including thermal conductivity, density, and viscosity of the nano-enhanced PCM, all of which necessitate the use of various equipment. These factors were measured using a KD2-Pro thermal properties analyzer, a DH-300L Leading Factory Liquid Density Tester, and a Brookfield (LVDV III ultra-programmable) viscometer.

5.4.1 Thermal Conductivity of nano-enhanced PCMs

Based on Fourier's law, the thermal conductivity of a material characterises its ability to conduct heat. In order to determine the thermal conductivity of the samples, a KD2 Pro thermal analyzer (Decagon Device, USA) was utilised. This device uses transient hot-wire technique principles (THWM).

The THWM method for measuring thermal conductivity uses a wire that functions as both a heating element and a thermometer. The power is rapidly applied, and the period of measurement is brief. Consequently, this strategy is deemed temporary. The device's measurement range is around 0.02-2.00 W/m.K with an accuracy of 0.001%. The instrument is calibrated using a Glycerin sample (included with the instrument) to measure its thermal conductivity at 20°C, which is 0.282 W/m.K. A vessel carrying the nanofluid/nano-PCM sample is placed in a temperature-controlled bath. The thermocouple within the vessel then monitors the sample's temperature. The thermal conductivity of Silicon Carbide (SiC) nanoparticle was measured at temperatures ranging from 25°C to 60°C at volume concentrations of (0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 vol. %). The results were collected three times and then averaged to provide an accurate value. The KD2 Pro thermal properties analyzer is shown in Figure 5.14. Additional information about the KD2 Pro thermal properties analyzer device, including its accuracy and other pertinent details, can be found in Appendix I: sub-section (3).

Figure 5.14 KD2 Pro thermal property analyzer device used for thermal conductivity measurements.

5.4.2 Density of nano-enhanced PCMs

The volumetric mass density of the nano-enhanced PCM represents its mass over its volume. It is proportional to the volume ratio of nanoparticles. A DH-300L Leading Factory Density Tester as shown in Figure 4.15 is used to measure the nano-enhanced PCM's density in grams per milli-litre (g/mL). The density ranges this device can

measure is about 10 g/mL with an accuracy of $\pm 10^{-6}$ g/mL at nano-enhanced PCM's temperature range of (25-60) °C and volume concentration (0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 vol. %). Density was measured three times and then averaged to achieve a more accurate value. Figure 5.15 shows the DH-300L Density Tester to measure the nano-enhanced PCMs' density. Additional information about the KD2 Pro thermal properties analyzer device, including its accuracy and other pertinent details presented in Appendix I: subsection (4).

Figure 5.15 The DH-300 L Density Tester to measure the density of nano-enhanced PCM.

5.4.3 Viscosity of nano-enhanced PCMs

Viscosity is an essential flow characteristic of heat transfer fluids. It illustrates the thermofluidic behaviour of various fluids. Figure 4.16 depicts a Brookfield programmable viscometer (Model: LVDV-III ultra-programmable) interfaced with a personal computer is used to measure and save data on nanofluids' and nano-PCMs' viscosity at various volume concentrations and temperatures. At a range of 24.46 to 293.5 sec^{-1} and 20 to 100 RPM, the samples were evaluated for shear resistance during charging and discharging processes. This experiment employs a temperature range of (25-60) °C and volume concentrations of 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 vol.% for nano-enhanced PCM. The viscosity was tested three times and then averaged in order to obtain a more precise value. Figure 5.16 depicts the ultra-programmable LVDV-III device used for measuring the viscosity of nano-enhanced PCMs. Additional

information about the ultra-programmable LVDV-III device, including its accuracy and other pertinent details, can be found in Appendix I: sub-section (5).

5.5 MASS PRODUCTION OF NANO-ENHANCED PCM

The purpose of carrying out thermo-physical property tests (0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 vol.%) on each and every produced sample is to achieve a better understanding of the optimal concentration ratio that should be applied during the relatively large-scale

Figure 5.16 LVDV-III ultra-programmable device used in viscosity measurement.

production of SiC-Paraffin wax for the nano-enhanced PCM capsules. This will allow for a more accurate evaluation of the optimal concentration ratio. This strategy is utilized to avoid squandering time and resources by testing out individual samples of the studied heater.

5.6 EXPERIMENTAL WORK OF DOUBLE PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS AND NANO-ENHANCED PCM

The experiments on the double-pass air heater are held indoors in the Heat Transfer Laboratory at the National University of Malaysia. The schematic diagram and view of the main experimental rig are shown in Figure 5.17. The setup is composed of a supporting pole, which is used to carry the studied heater. The system also includes a centrifugal blower model GTG GCIL 200 with a voltage controller, Digital voltage regulators, laptop, and a data acquisition system. The Halogen lamp with 118 mm long and a heat flux of 500 W is used for the solar simulator.

Figure 5.17 The schematic diagram and view of the main experimental rig.

5.6.1 Experimental Method

The glass cover of the heater and the exposed envelope of the pyrometer are thoroughly cleaned and dried before starting the experiment. The DP-SAH was

operated at varying conditions such as inlet air temperature, mass flow rate and solar irradiance level. The inlet air temperature varied from 27 to 30°C. The mass flow rates varied from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s. The solar irradiance levels varied from 400 to 1000 W/m². The lower channel's depth of the heater is fixed at 100 mm and upper channel's depth is changeable from 30 to 100 mm.

The cold air enters the heater through the upper channel formed by the glass cover and absorber plate, and subsequently passes through the lower channel formed by the back plate and absorber plate containing fins and nano-enhanced PCM capsules.

a. The charging process (melting)

During the charging process, a set of measurements were conducted to capture various temperature parameters and monitor the system's behaviour. These measurements included the glass temperature, absorber temperature, fin temperature, air temperature at both the upper and lower channels, nano-enhanced PCM temperature, and back-plate temperature. Each of these measurements were taken at specific time intervals, precisely every 10 minutes ($t = 10 \text{ min}$), to ensure a consistent and systematic data collection approach. The glass temperature measurement provided insights into the heat transfer and distribution across the heater's surface. By monitoring the absorber temperature, the researcher could assess the absorption of solar energy and its effect on the charging process. The fin temperature measurement allowed for the evaluation of heat dissipation and thermal performance within the system.

Additionally, the air temperature measurements at the upper and lower channels provided valuable information about the temperature variations and heat transfer within these regions. Monitoring the nano-enhanced PCM temperature offered insights into the phase change behaviour and energy storage characteristics of the material. Finally, the back-plate temperature measurement allowed for an assessment of the overall thermal behaviour and heat transfer within the system. Throughout these measurements, a solar simulator was utilized to provide a controlled and consistent source of solar radiation. The solar simulator ensured that the experimental conditions closely mimicked real-world solar exposure.

b. The discharging process (solidification).

During the discharging process, measurements were taken once the nano-enhanced PCM inside the capsules reached the melted phase, which occurred at approximately 55°C. This specific temperature threshold served as a reference point for initiating the measurement process. By waiting for the PCM to reach the desired melted state, The researcher could capture data when the discharging process was actively underway. It is worth noting that the solar simulator which provided controlled solar radiation, was turned off during the discharging experiment.

5.7 MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS

Several different sensors are utilized in order to obtain the measurements for both of these entities. These measurements are taken before, during, and after the system is run. In the third phase of the study, numerous characteristics such as air speed, ambient temperature, solar irradiance, temperatures of the various elements of the system, fluid flow, and so on must be determined. These data are collected and saved on a computer. The sections that follow provide information regarding the key components of the measuring systems as well as their significance to the study.

5.7.1 Data Acquisition System

It is common to practise to refer to the data acquisition system as the measurement system. It can the sensors that are attached to it and record and store the data from those sensors. An anbai-Applent Instruments AT4542 Multi-channel Temperature metre was used. In order to gather the information required for the investigation, the data logger of this system is linked to a personal computer (PC). The thermocouple that was utilised was of the K-type. The data gathering is done in an automated fashion once per minute to ensure the highest possible level of precision. This data-collecting system is connected to all of the remaining components in this section. Figure 5.18 and Figure 5.19 show Data Acquisition device (anbai-AT4542) and its program interface, respectively. More details of the Data Acquisition device such as its accuracy and others properties are presented in Appendix I : sub-section (6)

Figure 5.18 The Data Acquisition device (anbai-AT4542).

Figure 5.19 Program interface for Data logger (anbai-AT4542).

5.7.2 Solar Irradiance Measurement

The solar irradiance intensity levels are measured using an indoor pyranometer. This sensor corresponds to the total solar irradiance and outputs a microampere-DC-signal. Figure 5.20 shows the solar power meter model (TES 132) used in the current study. Additional information about the device, including its accuracy and other pertinent details, can be found in Appendix I: sub-section (7).

Figure 5.20 Solar Power Meter model TES 132.

5.7.3 Air Speed Measurement

The main device used to measure the air velocity was called an anemometer with model Lutron AM-4206 which is displayed in Figure 5.21. Anemometer linked to the data logger to record the maximum and minimum data while accuracy $\pm 3\%$. The anemometer had LCD with four digits that could simultaneously display the air velocity and the temperature. The mass flow rates can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{m}_{air} = \rho_{air} \times A_f \times \vartheta_{air} \quad \dots(5.2)$$

ρ_{air} is density of the air, A_f is cross-sectional area of the air flow channel and ϑ_{air} is velocity of the incoming air measured by anemometer. More details of the air speed measurement device such as its accuracy and others properties are presented in Appendix I : sub-section (8).

Figure 5.21 Anemometer model Lutron AM-4206.

5.7.4 Temperature Measurement

The thermocouple of type K is used to record the system's temperature. After calibrating this sensor and its temperature probe using the reference PT 100 Platinum Resistance Temperature Detector (RTD). After the calibration procedure, this sensor is utilised to measure various system components. Figure 5.22 shows the K-type thermocouple that is used in current study.

Figure 5.22 K-type thermocouple used in proposed heater.

5.8 SOLAR SIMULATOR DESIGN

A solar simulator with three-phase lamp arrays was employed to generate artificial solar radiation. The solar simulator is equipped with 48 halogen lamps with 500-W each and produced by LaiBa. Figure 5.23 illustrates the design of a solar simulator. Solar simulators are classified into class A, B, or C based on three parameters: spectral content, spatial homogeneity, and temporal stability. Class A, B, and C are given to solar simulators based on their spectral content, spatial homogeneity, and temporal stability and Table 5.4 outlines the essential prerequisites for each class (Eng 2022; Ooshaksaraei et al. 2017; Samiudin et al. 2016). Figure 5.24 to Figure 5.27 show the solar simulator mapping in 2-D for 400, 600, 800 and 1000 W/m². From the figures, higher solar irradiance can be observed at the centre of the solar mapping.

Figure 5.23 Schematic of solar simulator setup.

Table 5.4 Solar simulator classifications and specifications.

Classification	Spectral Match (each interval)	Irradiance Spatial Non-uniformity	Temporal Instability
Class A	0.175-1.25	$\leq 2\%$	$\leq 2\%$
Class B	0.6-1.4	$\leq 5\%$	$\leq 5\%$
Class C	0.4-2.0	$\leq 10\%$	$\leq 10\%$

Table 5.5 illustrates the solar simulator setting for average 400, 600, 800 and 1000 W/m^2 . According to the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC 60904-7 standard, the non-uniformity is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Non-uniformity} = \left(\frac{I_{T(\max)} - I_{T(\min)}}{I_{T(\max)} + I_{T(\min)}} \right) \quad \dots(5.3)$$

Table 5.5 Solar simulator setting.

Solar Simulation Setting					
	$I_T = 400 \text{ (W/m}^2)$	$I_T = 600 \text{ (W/m}^2)$	$I_T = 800 \text{ (W/m}^2)$	$I_T = 1000 \text{ (W/m}^2)$	
radiation	max	431	642	831	1042
	average	400	600	800	1000
	min	356	548	756	948
non-uniformity(%)	9.53	7.90	4.73	4.72	

Figure 5.24 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 2-D

Figure 5.25 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 2-D

Figure 5.26 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 2-D

Figure 5.27 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 2-D

Considering to Table 5.4, in terms of the irradiance spatial non-uniformity, the current solar simulator is classified as a class B for irradiance between 800-1000 W/m² and a class C for irradiance between 400-600 W/m².

5.9 CALIBRATION OF THE INSTRUMENTS AND TOOLS

During the calibration process, the measurement system is subjected to known input values, and the resulting output readings are recorded under controlled conditions. These known input values are commonly referred to as standards. In this particular research, the solar simulator irradiation and irradiation controllers were calibrated for irradiance levels of 400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m². The thermocouple signal relied on the Seebeck effect, which occurs when two different metal wires are connected in a loop to form two junctions. When these junctions are maintained at different temperatures, an electrical current is generated and flows through the loop. However, the resulting voltage signal is very weak, typically in the millivolt range. Furthermore, this voltage can be affected when transmitted over long distances through connectors. It is important to note that this voltage is expected to have a linear relationship with temperature changes. Considering these factors, a calibration process for the thermocouple required two temperature points. The freezing and boiling temperatures of water at atmospheric pressure were widely known and easily accessible, making them suitable for calibration in the Solar Thermal Laboratory.

CHAPTER VI

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the theoretical and experimental results obtained from simulations and corresponding experimental work. The focus is on analyzing the outlet temperature of the solar air heater during the charging / discharge process of the nano-enhanced Phase Change Material (PCM). The study also examines the air temperature along lower channel of the DP-SAH during charging process. Additionally, the impact of operating conditions, including mass flow rate, solar irradiance, and inlet temperature, on the thermal discharge process is discussed. The chapter also provides the optimum design conditions for the double-pass solar air heater based on experimental results. Several key parameters that influence the outlet air temperature and performance of the nano-enhanced PCM in the double-pass solar air heater during the discharge process are analyzed. These parameters include the mass and configuration of the nano-enhanced PCM, the air mass flow rate, upper channel depth, heater length, and surrounding conditions such as solar irradiance and ambient temperature. It is important to note that the DP-SAH configuration and capsule geometry remained constant throughout the study.

This chapter is structured into four main sections. The first section focuses on analyzing the experimental air temperature along the lower channel of the (DP-SAH) during the charging process. The second section investigates the impact of mass flow rate and solar irradiance on the outlet temperature. In the third section, the influence of mass flow rate, temperature rise, and solar irradiance levels on thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies is examined. Additionally, the effect of nanoparticles ratio on solidification time (discharging time) is presented.

6.2 THE AIR TEMPERATURE ALONG THE NANO-ENHANCED PCM STORAGE CAPSULES

The air temperature rises significantly along the lower channel of the DP-SAH with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM storage capsules. The air enters the lower channel at $N=0$ with an inlet temperature (T_N) and exits at capsule 23 ($N=23$) with the outlet temperature of the heater ($T_N=T_o$) as depicted in Figure 6.1. To analyze the air temperature, measurements were taken at a specific time ($t=10$ min) during the charging process along the DP-SAH. Temperature readings were recorded at different mass flow rates for every 5 capsules ($N=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 23$). Additionally, six sensors were positioned at each of the 5 capsules to capture the air temperature along the lower channel of the heater.

Figure 6.1 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a number of nano-enhanced PCM storage capsules (N).

Figures 6.2 to 6.5 present experimental data illustrating the increase in air temperature along the lower channel at different mass flow rates and solar irradiance levels (400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m^2 respectively). In Figure 6.2, the air initially enters the lower channel of the DP-SAH at capsule 0 ($N = 0$) with a temperature of $T_{N=0} = 28.2^\circ C$. As it progresses to capsule 5 ($N = 5$) with a mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s, the temperature rises moderately to $29.5^\circ C$. The temperature then continues to increase gradually until reaching capsule number 20 ($N = 20$). At capsule number 20, the temperature rise reaches a saturation point, resulting in an outlet temperature of $32^\circ C$ at capsule number 23 ($N = 23$). For mass flow rates of 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 kg/s, the corresponding outlet air temperatures were recorded as $31.1^\circ C$, $30.7^\circ C$,

30.1°C, and 29.1°C respectively. Figures 6.3, 6.4, and 6.5 provide a comparison of the air temperature increases (T_N) along the lower channel. In all cases, the air temperature reaches a saturation point at capsule number 20 ($N = 20$). This can be attributed to a decrease in heat transfer between the nano-enhanced PCM capsules and the fluid flow. The experimental and theoretical air temperatures (T_N) along the lower channel are recorded in Tables 6.1 to 6.4 for various mass flow rates and solar irradiance levels of 400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m² respectively. Furthermore, the maximum outlet air temperature ($N=23$) was recorded as 43°C for a mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s and full solar irradiance of 1000 W/m²

Figures 6.6 to 6.25 illustrate the impact of the number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules on the air temperature along the lower channel. The experiments were conducted with mass flow rates ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s and under operating solar irradiance levels of 400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m². Both experimental and theoretical results are presented in the figures. A comparison was made using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The maximum RMSE observed was 0.723°C, as depicted in Figure 6.17. On the other hand, the minimum RMSE recorded was 0.428°C, as shown in Figure 6.21. Figure 6.6 presents the experimental and theoretical results obtained at a solar irradiance level of $I_T = 400$ W/m². The figure shows a close agreement between the experimental and theoretical data. For instance, at nano-enhanced PCM capsule 20 ($N=20$), the experimental and theoretical air temperatures (T_N) are recorded as 31.8°C and 32.3°C, respectively. In Figures 6.7, 6.8, 6.9, and 6.10, with the same solar irradiance level, the theoretical air temperatures ($T_{N=23}$) are estimated as 31.8°C, 31.2°C, 30.8°C, and 30°C for mass flow rates of 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 kg/s, respectively. Figures 6.11 to 6.25 depict the air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel for mass flow rates ranging from 0.02 to 0.05 kg/s and solar irradiance levels of 600, 800, and 1000 W/m². The air temperature (T_N) exhibits an inverse relationship with mass flow rate and a direct relationship with the number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules (N). The figures demonstrate a close agreement between the theoretical and experimental results. However, it should be noted that the theoretical air temperature curves consistently appear higher than the corresponding experimental curves for all mass flow rates. This discrepancy can be attributed to the assumptions made in the mathematical model, as discussed in Chapter IV.

Figure 6.2 The experimental air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.3 The experimental air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.4 The experimental air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.5 The experimental air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Table 6.1 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T=400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Solar Irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$										
N	0.01kg/s		0.02 kg/s		0.03 kg/s		0.04 kg/s		0.05 kg/s	
	T_N (°C) (Exp)	T_N (°C) (Theo)								
0	28.2	28.7	27.8	28.3	27.6	28.1	27.5	28.1	27.2	27.8
5	29.5	30	29	29.6	28.5	29.1	28	28.5	27.5	28
10	30.5	31	30	30.5	29.5	30.2	29.5	30	28.3	29.2
15	31	31.5	30.5	31.1	30	30.5	29.9	30.4	28.7	29.2
20	31.8	32.3	31	31.7	30.5	31	30	30.5	29	29.8
23	32	32.5	31.1	31.8	30.7	31.2	30.2	30.8	29.1	30

Table 6.2 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T=600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Solar Irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$										
N	0.01kg/s		0.02 kg/s		0.03 kg/s		0.04 kg/s		0.05 kg/s	
	T_N (°C) (Exp)	T_N (°C) (Theo)								
0	30.2	30.8	29.8	30.4	29.6	30.2	29.5	30	29.2	29.8
5	32	32.5	31.5	32	31	31.5	30.5	31.1	30	30.5
10	33	33.6	32.5	33.1	32	32.5	31.5	32	30.8	31.3
15	33.5	34	33	33.6	32.5	33.1	32	32.5	31.2	31.7
20	34.3	34.9	33.5	34	33	33.7	32.5	33	31.5	32
23	34.5	35	33.6	34.2	33.1	33.8	32.5	33.2	31.5	32.1

Table 6.3 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T=800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Solar Irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$										
N	0.01kg/s		0.02 kg/s		0.03 kg/s		0.04 kg/s		0.05 kg/s	
	T_N (°C) (Exp)	T_N (°C) (Theo)								
0	32.6	33	32.1	32.5	31.8	32.4	31.6	32	30.7	31.2
5	34.5	35.1	34	34.5	33.5	34	33	33.5	32.5	33
10	35.5	36	35	35.5	34.5	35	34	34.5	33	33.5
15	36	36.5	35.5	36	35	35.5	34.5	35.1	33.5	34
20	36.8	37.4	36	37	35.5	36	35	35.6	34	34.5
23	37	37.5	36.1	37.2	35.7	36.2	35.2	35.7	34.1	34.7

Table 6.4 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T=1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Solar Irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$										
N	0.01kg/s		0.02 kg/s		0.03 kg/s		0.04 kg/s		0.05 kg/s	
	T_N (°C) (Exp)	T_N (°C) (Theo)								
0	37.5	38	37	37.5	36.7	37.3	36.5	37	35.6	36.1
5	40.4	40.8	39.9	40.4	39.4	40	38.9	39.5	38.4	39
10	41.4	41.9	40.9	41.5	40.4	40.9	39.9	40.4	39.2	39.7
15	41.9	42.5	41.4	41.9	40.9	41.4	40.4	40.9	39.6	40.2
20	42.8	43	41.9	42.5	41.4	41.8	40.9	41.3	39.9	40.7
23	43.0	43.2	42	42.6	41.5	41.9	41	41.4	40	40.9

Figure 6.6 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.7 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.8 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.03 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.9 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.04 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.10 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.11 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.12 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.13 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.03 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.14 The variations of instantaneous air temperature along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.04 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.15 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.16 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.17 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.18 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.03 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.19 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.04 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.20 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.21 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.22 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.23 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.03 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.24 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.04 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.25 The air temperature (T_N) along the lower channel at a constant mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

6.3 THE EFFECT OF THE MASS FLOW RATE ON THE TEMPERATURE RISE

The temperature rise of the double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) is determined by the difference between the outlet and inlet temperature ($T_o - T_i$). This temperature difference is influenced by the mass flow rates of the working fluid.

Figure 6.26 illustrates the impact of mass flow rate on the temperature rise, both experimentally and theoretically, at a solar irradiance level of 400 W/m^2 . The experimental results demonstrate a reasonably good agreement with the predicted values, as indicated by a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.353°C . Similarly, Figure 6.27 showcases the effect of mass flow rates ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s at a solar irradiance level of 600 W/m^2 , with an RMSE of 0.569°C . A comparison between Figures 6.28 and 6.29 reveals that the temperature rise decreases as the mass flow rate increases within the range of 0.01 - 0.05 kg/s . Moreover, Figures 6.27 and 6.28 demonstrate that an increase in solar irradiance leads to an overall rise in temperature for all mass flow rates.

Figure 6.26 The effect of mass flow rate on the temperature rise at solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.27 The effect of mass flow rate on the temperature rise at solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.28 The effect of mass flow rate on the temperature rise at solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figure 6.29 The effect of mass flow rate on the temperature rise at solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

Figures 6.30 to 6.34 provide a comparative analysis of the theoretical and experimental results, showcasing the variations in the outlet air temperature over time during the discharge process. These figures examine different mass flow rates and an inlet temperature (T_i) set at 27°C . The lowest root mean square error (RMSE) recorded was 2.677°C , observed at a mass flow rate of 0.02 kg/s . Conversely, the highest RMSE of 3.512°C was observed at a mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s .

Figure 6.35 depicts the variations in the outlet temperature of the studied double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) over time during the discharge process. The mass flow rate ranges from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s . In this experimental study, it is observed that the discharge time increases as the mass flow rate decreases from 0.05 kg/s to 0.01 kg/s . Specifically, the discharge time for the maximum mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s is 50 minutes, whereas for the minimum flow rate of 0.01 kg/s , it extends to 250 minutes. In the context of drying applications, the discharging time is 125 minutes when the mass flow rate is set to 0.035 kg/s .

Figure 6.30 The variations of outlet air temperature versus the time at a constant mass flow rate 0.01 kg/s and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

Figure 6.31 The variations of outlet air temperature versus the time at a constant mass flow rate 0.02 kg/s and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

Figure 6.32 The variations of outlet air temperature versus the time at a constant mass flow rate 0.03 kg/s and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

Figure 6.33 The variations of outlet air temperature versus the time at a constant mass flow rate 0.04 kg/s and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

Figure 6.34 The variations of outlet air temperature versus the time at a constant mass flow rate 0.05 kg/s and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

Figure 6.35 The experimental variations of outlet air temperature at various mass flow rates and inlet temperature $T_i = 27$ °C.

6.4 THE EFFECT OF THE SOLAR IRRADIANCE ON THE TEMPERATURE RISE

Figures 6.36 and 6.37 demonstrate the influence of solar irradiance on the temperature rise at different mass flow rates for two different upper channel depths: 3 cm and 10 cm. These figures also present the experimental and theoretical values for various mass flow rates. The experimental and theoretical results align closely with each other, displaying consistent trends. The temperature rise is directly proportional to the solar irradiance. As observed in Figures 6.36 and 6.37, the (DP-SAH) exhibits higher temperature increases when operating under high solar irradiance conditions. Furthermore, the DP-SAH operating at lower mass flow rates has greater temperature increases at the same solar irradiance level. Therefore, given the known mass flow rate and solar irradiation, these figures allow for the calculation of the temperature increase in the heater. For instance, in Figure 6.36, at a solar irradiance level of 1000 W/m^2 , the theoretical temperature rises are calculated as 19.5°C , 7.6°C , and 4.7°C for mass flow rates of 0.01 kg/s , 0.03 and 0.05 kg/s respectively. Furthermore, at a solar

Figure 6.36 The effect of solar irradiance level on the temperature rise at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 3 \text{ cm}$ and lower channel $d_2 = 10 \text{ cm}$).

Figure 6.37 The effect of solar irradiance level on the temperature rise at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=10$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

irradiance level of 600 W/m^2 , the theoretical temperatures are 11.5 , 4.4 and 2.7 °C for mass flow rates of 0.01 , 0.03 and 0.05 kg/s respectively. Figure 6.36 illustrates that the slope of the theoretical lines is steeper for lower mass flow rates compared to higher mass flow rates. This indicates that at lower mass flow rates, the temperature rise is more pronounced with each increase in solar irradiation. For example, when the mass flow rate is set to 0.05 kg/s, an increase in solar irradiance from 600 to 1000 W/m^2 results in a temperature rise of the DP-SAH ranging from 2.7 to 4.7 °C. In contrast, at a mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s, an increase in solar irradiance from 600 to 1000 W/m^2 leads to a more substantial temperature rise, ranging from 7.5 to 15 °C. This comparison demonstrates that higher temperature increases are observed at lower mass flow rates when solar irradiance levels are elevated.

In Figure 6.37, at a solar irradiance level of 1000 W/m^2 , the theoretical temperature rises are recorded as 15 °C, 6.8 °C, and 4.2 °C for mass flow rates of 0.01 kg/s, 0.03 kg/s, and 0.05 kg/s, respectively. Furthermore, at a solar irradiance level of

600 W/m², the temperature rises are measured as 7.5°C, 3.8°C, and 2.3°C for mass flow rates of 0.01 kg/s, 0.03 kg/s, and 0.05 kg/s, respectively. Hence, it can be reasonably anticipated that the double-pass solar air heater will exhibit similar temperature rise patterns when operating under these conditions.

Comparing the experimental and theoretical data from Figure 6.36 and Figure 6.37, it is evident that the temperature rise increases for all three mass flow rates are lower in the case of a larger channel depth. This is because as the channel depth increases, there is reduced heat transfer occurring between the absorber panel and the fluid flowing in the channel. Additionally, assuming a constant mass flow rate, the velocity of the fluid is significantly reduced within the double-pass solar air heater as the channel depth increases.

6.5 THE EFFECT OF THE MASS FLOW RATE ON THE EFFICIENCIES

Figures 6.38, 6.39, 6.40, and 6.41 depict the influence of mass flow rate on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies of the double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH). These figures consider the case where the upper channel depth (d_1) is 3 cm and the lower channel depth (d_2) is 10 cm, operating at solar irradiance levels of 400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m², respectively. The experimental and numerical results are also presented. In general, it can be observed that higher mass flow rates in the DP-SAH lead to increased thermal and thermo-hydraulic efficiencies. However, the exergy efficiency follows a different trend. It increases from 0 to 0.01 kg/s and then decreases from 0.02 to 0.05 kg/s. For instance, in Figure 6.38, at a solar irradiance of 400 W/m², an inlet temperature of 27°C, and a mass flow rate of 0.035 kg/s, the experimental and theoretical thermal efficiencies are recorded as 69.1% and 70.9%, respectively. The corresponding theoretical thermo-hydraulic efficiency is 65.5%, while the theoretical exergy efficiency is 18%. Additionally, under the same operating conditions, the experimental thermo-hydraulic efficiency is measured as 64%. In Figures 6.39 through 6.41, it is evident that both the experimental and theoretical efficiencies generally increase for all mass flow rate levels, except for the exergy efficiency which exhibits a decreasing trend, as previously mentioned. Specifically, at a mass flow rate of 0.035 kg/s, the experimental thermal efficiencies for solar

Figure 6.38 The effect of mass flow rate on thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm with Solar irradiance $I_T=400$ W/m²).

Figure 6.39 The effect of mass flow rate on thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm with Solar irradiance $I_T=600$ W/m²).

Figure 6.40 The effect of mass flow rate on thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm with Solar irradiance $I_T=800$ W/m²).

Figure 6.41 The effect of mass flow rate on thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm with Solar irradiance $I_T=1000$ W/m²).

irradiance levels of 600, 800, and 1000 W/m² are measured as 74.5%, 75%, and 77% respectively.

The corresponding theoretical thermal efficiencies under the same design and operational conditions are calculated as 75.5%, 77.3%, and 78.5%. Additionally, the experimental thermo-hydraulic efficiencies at a mass flow rate of 0.035 kg/s for solar irradiance levels of 600, 800, and 1000 W/m² are recorded as 70%, 70.2%, and 71% respectively. Therefore, theoretically, it appears that increasing solar irradiance leads to an increase in thermo-hydraulic efficiencies.

6.6 THE EFFECT OF THE SOLAR IRRADIANCE ON THE EFFICIENCIES

Figures 6.42 through 6.47 illustrate the impact of solar irradiance on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies at upper channel depths of 3 cm and 10 cm, with mass flow rates of 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05 kg/s. The figures present both theoretical and experimental results. In Figure 6.42, it can be observed that as the mass flow rate increases, the thermal efficiency also tends to increase. At a mass flow rate of 0.01 kg/s, the thermal efficiency at 400 W/m² is lower compared to the thermal efficiency at 1000 W/m² when the upper channel depth is 3 cm and the lower channel depth is 10 cm. The experimental and theoretical results cover a range of solar irradiance levels from 400 to 1000 W/m² and mass flow rates from 0.01 kg/s to 0.05 kg/s. Based on the experimental results, the thermal efficiencies range from 53.1% to 79% for solar irradiance levels of 400 W/m² and 1000 W/m², respectively. For a higher mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s, the experimental and theoretical thermal efficiencies at 1000 W/m² are 79% and 80%, respectively. At the same mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s and a solar irradiance level of 800 W/m², the experimental and theoretical thermal efficiencies are 71% and 73%, respectively.

Figure 6.43 depicts the influence of solar irradiance on the thermo-hydraulic efficiency at different mass flow rates ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s. It can be observed that at higher solar irradiance levels, the thermo-hydraulic efficiency tends to be higher. For instance, at a mass flow rate of 0.05 kg/s, the experimental and theoretical thermo-hydraulic efficiencies are recorded as 68.6% and 71% respectively at a solar irradiance level of 800 W/m². Similarly, at a solar irradiance level of 400

W/m², the experimental and theoretical thermo-hydraulic efficiencies are 50.7% and 52% respectively. In Figure 6.44, the effect of solar irradiance on the exergy efficiency is shown for upper channel depths of 3 cm and 10 cm, with mass flow rates of 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05 kg/s. The experimental and theoretical results are also presented. At a mass flow rate of 0.03 kg/s, the experimental and theoretical exergy efficiencies are measured as 16.4% and 17.5% respectively at a solar irradiance level of 800 W/m². At a higher solar irradiance level of 1000 W/m², the experimental and theoretical exergy efficiencies are recorded as 16.8% and 20.4% respectively. Notably, there is a close agreement between the experimental and theoretical results in Figure 6.44 for exergy efficiency. Additionally, the exergy efficiency for this particular case ($d_1 = 3$ cm and $d_2 = 10$ cm) exhibits an increase as the solar irradiance levels increase. Figures 6.45 to 6.47 present the impact of solar irradiance on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies, respectively, for a double-pass solar air heater with an upper channel depth of 10 cm and a lower channel depth of 10 cm. The mass flow rates considered are 0.01 kg/s, 0.03 kg/s, and 0.05 kg/s. Both theoretical and experimental results are displayed in these figures.

Figure 6.42 The effect of solar irradiance on the thermal efficiency at different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 3$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

Figure 6.43 The effect of solar irradiance on the thermo-hydraulic efficiency at different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 6.44 The effect of solar irradiance on the exergy efficiency at different mass flow rates ((upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 6.45 The effect of solar irradiance on the thermal efficiency at different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=10$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 6.46 The effect of solar irradiance on the thermo-hydraulic efficiency at different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=10$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 6.47 The effect of solar irradiance on the exergy efficiency at different mas flow rates (upper channel $d_1=10$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

6.7 THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE RISE ON THE EFFICIENCIES

The effect of the temperature rise on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies can be seen in Figures 6.48 through 6.53. In addition, the figures illustrate the region in which the experiments have been conducted along with four lines that denote the maximum and minimum values for solar irradiance and mass flow rate of the air. One of the lines demonstrates a limit for the mass flow rate that is lower than 0.01 kg/s. The other line indicates a limit on the mass flow rate that is higher than 0.05 kg/s. The figures also include limit lines for the levels of solar irradiance. Therefore, the other two lines represent values for solar irradiance that is higher than 1000 W/m² and solar irradiance that is lower than 400 W/m².

The impact of the temperature rise on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiency at varied mass flow rates for the upper channel of 3 cm is shown in Figures 6.48, 6.49, and 6.50 respectively. Therefore, the combinations of temperature

rise, thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies may be determined for certain mass flow rates and levels of solar irradiance. The usage of the figures are presented with the help of the following example. The mass flow rate is kept at a constant value of 0.035 kg/s, and is operating at a solar irradiance of 900 W/m². Figure 6.48 shows that as a result, the expected temperature rise is 7 °C., and the thermal efficiency is around 77%. Based on Figure 6.49, the efficiency of the thermo-hydraulic is around 75%. The exergy efficiency is about 22%, as seen in Figure 6.50. Figures 6.51, 6.52 and 6.53 show the effect of the temperature rise on the thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies at various mass flow rates respectively for the upper channel of 10 cm. Continuing with the previous example, the temperature rise that is expected is 5 °C. The exergy efficiency is at 21%, while the thermal efficiency is at 75%, and the thermo-hydraulic efficiency is at 74%. When the upper channel height is decreased while maintaining the same mass flow rate, as shown in Figures 6.47 through 6.52, a rise in the exergy efficiency, as well as the thermal and thermo-hydraulic efficiencies, occurs. This is because there is an increase in the heat transfer coefficient that exists between the upper channel walls and the flow of the working fluid.

Figure 6.48 The effect of the temperature rise on the thermal efficiency at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=3$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 6.49 The effect of the temperature rise on the thermos-hydraulic efficiency at various mass flow ratee (upper channel $d_1 = 3$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

Figure 6.50 The effect of the temperature rise on the exergy efficiency at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 3$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

Figure 6.51 The effect of the temperature rise on the thermal efficiency at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 10 \text{ cm}$ and lower channel $d_2 = 10 \text{ cm}$).

Figure 6.52 The effect of the temperature rise on the thermo-hydraulic efficiency at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 10 \text{ cm}$ and lower channel $d_2 = 10 \text{ cm}$).

Figure 6.53 The effect of the temperature rise on the exergy efficiency at various mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 10$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

6.8 THE EFFECT OF NANOPARTICLES RATIO ON THE SOLIDIFICATION TIME

The additive ratio of nanoparticles (Silicon Carbide) increased from 0.1 % to 3 vol. % optimizing the suitable volume fraction so that it could be used in the nano-enhanced PCM. It can be seen from Figure 6.54 that the increase in the volume fraction led to an increase in the cooling rate and decreasing in discharging time. For 2 vol.%, the cooling rate increased but the solidification time became short and the nano-enhanced PCM seemed to behave as a sensible storage material which would reflect on the outlet temperature; consequently, the optimum result appeared with a volume fraction 0.5% which was used in current research.

Figures 6.55 and 6.56 show the temperature variations versus the time during the solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin Wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) capsules at various mass flow rates respectively. Figure 6.56 shows an improvement and stability during the melting point, while the discharging time reduced by 50 minutes for the nano-enhanced PCM.

Figure 6.54 Nano-enhanced PCM temperature variations versus the time during the solidification process at various silicon carbide (SiC) volume fractions at mass flow rate = 0.035 kg/s.

Figure 6.55 The temperature variations versus the time during solidification process for the PCM (pure Paraffin Wax) at various mass flow rates.

Figure 6.56 The temperature variations versus the time during solidification process for the nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at various mass flow rates.

The PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) temperature surged to around 55 °C; then the solar simulator was switched off to observe the discharge process. Moreover, the temperature of the solidification of the PCM and nano-enhanced PCM are monitored experimentally and provided in Figures 6.57, 6.58, 6.59, 6.60, and 6.61 for various mass flow rates from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s. Figure 6.57 shows the variations of the capsules temperature versus the time during the solidification process for the PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.01 kg/s and inlet temperature 27 °C. Accordingly, there was an improvement in the solidification time after adding nanoparticle to Paraffin wax, however; the total discharge time decreased due to the heat transfer was enhanced for nano-enhanced PCM capsules. Figures 6.58 through 6.61 show the variations of the capsules temperature versus the time during the solidification process for the PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate ranging from 0.02 to 0.05kg/s. The comparison between the PCM and nano-enhanced PCM at different mass flow rates led the same notion that there was an improvement in the thermal response time and in the solidification time as well.

Figure 6.57 The temperature of capsules versus the time during solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.01 kg/s.

Figure 6.58 The temperature of capsules versus the time during solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.02 kg/s.

Figure 6.59 The temperature of capsules versus the time during solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.03 kg/s.

Figure 6.60 The temperature of capsules versus the time during solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.04 kg/s

Figure 6.61 The temperature of capsules versus the time during solidification process for PCM (pure Paraffin wax) and nano-enhanced PCM (0.5 vol. %) at mass flow rate 0.05 kg/s.

CHAPTER VII

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

7.1 INTRODUCTION

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a framework used to assess the economic feasibility of a project or decision by comparing the costs and benefits associated with it. For low and intermediate-temperature application solar devices, the solar air heater (SAHs) generally account for more than 50% of the total cost of the devices (Fudholi et al. 2013b). It is, therefore, essential that, along with reasonably good efficiency, the solar heater should be cost-effective. Hence, this chapter presents the cost-benefit ratio of the double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM storage capsules. Evaluation of the annual cost (AC) and the annual thermal energy gain ($ATEG$) of the DP-SAH are performed. The ratio of $AC/ATEG$ or the cost-benefit ratio is presented for different combinations of design and operational parameters such as mass flow rates, various heater lengths and various upper channel depths to make it feasible for the user/designer to select optimum design features which correspond to minimum $AC/ATEG$ or cost-benefit ratio. The main objective of the optimization study is to be able to specify design parameters, a combination of which can extract maximum possible thermal energy out of available solar energy. If thermal studied heater is to be economically beneficial, they must have the capability of collecting maximum amount of solar energy at minimum possible cost.

7.2 ANNUAL THERMAL ENERGY GAIN

The annual energy available from the DP-SAH can be obtained from the follows (Fudholi et al. 2013b; Verma et al. 1992):

$$ATEG = \dot{m} C_p (T_o - T_i) \times t_{op} \quad \dots(7.1)$$

$$t_{op} = N_{hr} \times N_d \quad \dots(7.2)$$

t_{op} is operational time and N_{hr} is the number of hours per day during useful sunshine is available and N_d is the number of operating hours per sunny days in a year.

7.3 ANNUAL PUMPING COST

The annual pumping cost of the DP-SAH can be calculated as follows (Fudholi et al. 2013b):

$$APC = \left(\frac{\dot{m}_f \Delta P}{\rho} \right) t_{op} CE \quad \dots(7.3)$$

CE is the electricity cost, ρ is the density of the air and the pressure drop (ΔP) for each channel can be seen in Chapter IV:

7.4 ANNUAL SALVAGE VALUE

The annual salvage value can be calculated from the following expression:

$$ASV = SFF \times SV \quad \dots(7.4)$$

SV is the salvage value which is equal to 10% of capital investment and SFF is the salvage fund factor which can be defined as (Abuška et al. 2017; Shadi et al. 2020):

$$SFF = \frac{r}{(r + 1)^n - 1} \quad \dots(7.5)$$

7.5 ANNUAL COST (AC)

In order to determine the annual cost (AC) of the DP-SAH per unit area, the different cost factors have to be calculated. The annual cost of (AC) depends on annual capital cost (ACC), Maintenance cost (MC) which is 10% of (CI), annual pumping cost (APC) and annual salvage value (ASV). The annual cost (AC) of the DP-SAH can be calculated as follows:

$$AC = ACC + MC + APC - ASV \quad \dots(7.6)$$

The annual capital cost (ACC) can be calculated as follows :

$$ACC = CRF \times CI \quad \dots(7.7)$$

where,

$$CI = HAC + HSSC + HFC \quad \dots(7.8)$$

CI is the capital investment, HAC is the heater array cost, $HSSC$ is the heater support structure cost, HFC is the heater fabrication cost and CRF is the capital recovery factor can be defined as (Abuşka et al. 2017; Fudholi et al. 2013b; Shadi et al. 2020):

$$CRF = \frac{r (r + 1)^n}{(r + 1)^n - 1} \quad \dots(7.9)$$

7.6 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DP-SAH components price and relevant data for cost-effectiveness calculations are shown in Table 7.1. Numerical values of different parameters for the DP-SAH with fins and nano-enhanced PCM were computed corresponding to the annual average solar irradiance which was assumed to be 700 W/m^2 and annual ambient temperature of 300 K or 27°C . The glass cover cost is $\text{RM } 40/\text{m}^2$. The cost of 23 nano-enhanced PCM capsules is $\text{RM } 650$. The cost of the support structure is equal to $\text{RM } 35/\text{m}^2$ and the insulation cost $\text{RM } 30/\text{m}^2$. The cost of electricity to run the air pump in the studied heater is 0.221 RM/kWh . The maintenance cost is considered as 10% of the capital investment of the DP-SAH with staggered fins and nano-enhanced PCM capsules. The interest rate is considered as 10% as well as the expected lifetime of the DP-SAH is 10 years. The fabrication cost is assumed to be 10% of the capital investment of the DP-SAH. In this study, the heater lengths varied as 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3 m. The upper channel depths varied from 30 mm to 100 mm. The mass flow rate varied from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s. It can be seen from Figures 7.1 through 7.4 show that

Table 7.1 The DP-SAH components' prices and relevant data for cost-effectiveness calculations.

Component	Unit	Specification
Cost of glass cover	RM/m ²	40
Cost of nano-enhanced PCM capsules	RM	650
Cost of support structure	RM/m ²	35
Cost of insulation	RM/m ²	30
Cost of electricity	RM/kWh	0.221
Cost of fabrication	%	10 CI
Cost of maintenance	%	10 CI
Interest rate	%	10
Expected proposed heater life time	year	10
Annual average solar irradiance	W/m ²	700
Annual operational time	Day	312

the DP-SAH length increases, the annual thermal energy gain (*ATEG*) increases, too. In general, the *ATEG* is directly proportional to the length of the DP-SAH. Figure 7.5 shows the annual cost to annual thermal energy gain ratio (*AC/ATEG*) as a function of the channel depth by assuming that the thermal discharge process would occur one time per day. *AC/ATEG* increased with the increase of the channel depth for the heater lengths; 1 m, 1.5 m and 2 m while, approximately no change in *AC/ATEG* was observed for the heater lengths; 2.5 m to 3 m.

The optimum *AC/ATEG* is obtained at the channel depths between 3 to 5 cm depending on the heater length and mass flow rates. Any channel depth less than 3 cm is very close to the absorber plate and will block the inlet of the DP-SAH. Figure 7.6 shows the variations after increasing the mass flow rate from 0.01 to 0.02kg/s which displayed a ascending in *AC/ATEG* versus the channel depth compared to the results in Figure 7.5. Yet, curves of the DP-SAH lengths 2.5 m and 3m in Figure 7.6 were approximately closed to each other. Figure 7.7 through 7.9 show the variations of mass flow rates from 0.03, 0.04 and 0.05 kg/s. which showed an increase of *AC/ATEG* versus the channel depth between 3 to 5 cm while for other cases of heater depths up to 10 cm were almost constant and very close to each other.

Figure 7.1 The Variation in the annual thermal energy gain (*ATEG*) with respect to the heater length with different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 3$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

Figure 7.2 The Variation in the annual thermal energy gain (*ATEG*) with respect to the heater length with different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1 = 5$ cm and lower channel $d_2 = 10$ cm).

Figure 7.3 The Variation in the annual thermal energy gain (*ATEG*) with respect to the heater length with different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=7$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 7.4 The Variation in the annual thermal energy gain (*ATEG*) with respect to the heater length with different mass flow rates (upper channel $d_1=10$ cm and lower channel $d_2=10$ cm).

Figure 7.5 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the upper channel depth at different heater lengths (mass flow rate = 0.01 kg/s).

Figure 7.6 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the upper channel depth at different heater lengths (mass flow rate = 0.02 kg/s).

Figure 7.7 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the upper channel depth at different heater lengths (mass flow rate = 0.03 kg/s).

Figure 7.8 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the upper channel depth at different heater lengths (mass flow rate = 0.04 kg/s).

Figure 7.9 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the upper channel depth at different heater lengths (mass flow rate = 0.05 kg/s).

In Figure 7.10 illustrates that at different the heater lengths and different channel depths for double-pass solar air heater with staggered fins and nano-enhanced PCM at a mass flow rate of 0.035 kg/s. The upper channel depths varied from 3 cm to 10 cm and the heater lengths varied from 1 to 3 m.

The $AC/ATEG$ decreased at the beginning until the upper channel depth was equal to 5 cm and then reached stability for the higher upper channel depths. Figure 7.11 and Figure 7.12 show the effect of the mass flow rate on $AC/ATEG$ for different channel depths at heater lengths equal to 1 and 3 m. In general, for the same heater length, as the mass flow rate increased from 0.01 to 0.02 kg/s,

The $AC/ATEG$ were approximately matched with each other; however, the mass flow rate greater than 0.02 kg/s up to 0.05 kg/s the $AC/ATEG$ was increased. The difference between heater depth of 3 cm with other depths is obvious for mass flow rate from 0.02 to 0.05 kg/s.

Figure 7.10 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the heater length with different upper channel depths at (mass flow rate = 0.035 kg/s).

Figure 7.11 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the mass flow rate with different upper channel depths at (The heater length $L=1.0\text{m}$).

Figure 7.12 $AC/ATEG$ as a function of the mass flow rate with different upper channel depth at (The heater length $L=3.0$ m).

CHAPTER VIII

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

8.1 INTRODUCTION

This dissertation presents the experimental and numerical performance of the double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered fins absorber and nano-enhanced PCM storage capsules. It is the most comprehensive study of such type of heater since it covers the followings: (a). simulation (b). experimental setup and (c). the cost-effectiveness. Based on the work presented in this dissertation, some concluding remarks and suggestions for further research in thermal solar heaters are discussed.

8.2 CONCLUDING REMARKS

8.2.1 Mathematical Modeling

A one- dimensional mathematical model to predict the performance of the proposed DP-SAH was achieved. A steady-state model for five equations that relates the upper and lower streams of the DP-SAH was developed. An iterative procedure and matrix inversion method are used. The various heat transfer coefficients as well as various radiative heat transfer coefficients depend on the value of the glass, absorber plate, fins, nano-enhanced PCM capsules, back plate, and air temperature at any point along the lower channel were theoretically calculated. The mathematical model is performed on the performance of the DP-SAH for various values of mass flow rates, heater lengths and the upper channel depths. The performance is represented in the thermal, thermo-hydraulic and exergy efficiencies of the heater. The upper channel depth is varied from 3 to 10 cm. The mass flow rate is varied from 0.01 to 0.05 kg/s . The solar irradiance level is varied from 400 to 1000 W/m² and the heater length is varied from 1 to 3 m.

8.2.2 The experimental setup

The novel double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered rectangular fins and cylindrical nano-enhanced phase change material (PCM) was designed, fabricated, and tested indoor. The overall uncertainty for temperature measurement is ± 0.5 °C. The overall uncertainty in the air mass flow rate measurement is ± 0.4 %. The solar irradiance measurement has an accuracy is ± 0.2 %

8.2.3 Comparison with Experimental Results and Theory

Increasing the mass flow rate improves the heater's thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies. Higher mass flow rates led to an increase in the heat transfer coefficients between the channels and the fluid flow. Increasing the heat transfer coefficients will reduce the absorber plate's average temperature. Consequently, this will improve thermal and thermo-hydraulic efficiencies. In contrast, increasing the depth of the channel will reduce thermal, thermo-hydraulic, and exergy efficiencies. In addition, when the depth of the upper channel increases, the heat transfer coefficients drop and reverse occurs. Design curves showing variations in the design and operational conditions are developed. The curves would be useful to the designer to observe the effect of temperature rise on the efficiencies, the effect of the solar irradiance on temperature rise and the efficiencies, and the effect of mass flow rate on the efficiencies. Rationally close agreements between the experimental data and theory have been obtained. Values of the absorptivity, emissivity, and transmissivity for various surfaces are assumed values taken from accepted figures and measure values. The predicted outlet temperature is within 1.5 to 2% compared to the experimental outlet temperature.

8.2.4 Cost Effectiveness of the Double-Pass solar air heater with fins and Nano-enhanced PCM

A simple cost-effectiveness model for the double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with fins and nano-enhanced PCM was developed. The model just concentrates on the heater design parameters such as mass flow rate, upper channel depth and the heater length. The cost-benefit ratio of the annual cost to annual thermal energy gain $AC/ATEG$ is presented for different combinations of the heater design parameters.

Therefore, the designer can select the optimum design which is depending on the application. It can observe that it is more cost-effective if the user operates the DP-SAH at a higher mass flow rate during the discharge process to extract more stored thermal energy. The optimum results for the DP-SAH are obtained at the length (1.0 m) and the optimum annual cost per annual energy gain $AC/ATEG$ for this type of heater is obtained at upper channel depth in the range of 3 to 5 cm.

8.3 SIGNIFICANT CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE RESEARCH

Based on the theoretical and experimental study made on the double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered rectangular fins and cylindrical nano-enhanced phase change material (PCM), several contributions are gained and summarized as follows:

- The SiC nanoparticle was prepared and employed to enhance the thermal properties of phase change material (paraffin wax). It was demonstrated in this work that nano-enhanced PCM has better thermal conductivity and latent heat during charging and discharging process, due to high thermal conductivity of nanoparticles which is attributed to Brownian motion.
- MATLAB programming served the research in predicting the optimum design and compared theoretically with other designs as follows: (1). Conventional Double-pass solar air heater; (2). Double-pass solar air heater with fins only; (3). Double-pass solar air heater with nano-enhanced PCM only; (4). Double-pass solar air heater with fins and nano-enhanced PCM.
- The novel double-pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with staggered rectangular fins and cylindrical nano-enhanced phase change material (PCM) was designed, fabricated, and tested indoor and compared the experimental results with those obtained from theoretical results as well.
- Applying the encapsulation technique through multiple cylindrical capsules filled with nano-enhanced phase change material (paraffin wax with silicon carbide) as thermal storage system, to enhance the energy exchange between cylindrical surfaces and airflow.
- The purpose of the cost-benefit ratio $AC/ATEG$ is to provide an effective cost estimation of a designed DP-SAH with fins and nano-enhanced PCM. It considers initial costs, operation, and maintenance cost.

8.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The current study still has many more ideas that need to be researched /investigated for possible improvement as well as modification. Hence, a few suggestions are raised in this section for further research. These suggestions are as follows:

- The geometry of thermal storage units plays a crucial role in determining their thermal performance in the DP-SAH. In this regard, investigating the effect of different geometry shapes on the charging (melting) and discharging (freezing) process can provide valuable insights into the optimal design of thermal storage units for the DP-SAH. One potential area of future research is to investigate the effect of different geometry shapes of thermal storage units in the lower duct of the heater. For instance, the use of rectangular, spherical, and hemispherical capsules could be explored to determine their impact on the charging and discharging process. The shape of the capsules can affect the surface area-to-volume ratio and the flow of air around the capsules, which in turn can affect the heat transfer rate and the overall thermal performance of the system.
- This study focuses on the implementation of organic phase change material (Paraffin wax). This is because organic PCMs are commonly used in heat exchange applications due to their favorable properties such as low cost, high latent heat storage capacity, and low environmental impact. However, future research can explore the use of non-organic PCM with the inclusion of nanoparticles to enhance their thermal conductivities. Non-organic PCMs, such as inorganic salts, have higher thermal conductivity than organic PCMs, which can lead to faster heat transfer rates. In addition, the inclusion of nanoparticles within non-organic PCM can further enhance the thermal conductivity of the material, leading to even higher performance of the DP-SAH. Thus, exploring the use of non-organic PCM with the inclusion of nanoparticles can be a promising direction for future research to improve the heat transfer performance of the DP-SAH and make it more suitable for commercial applications.
- Performing the same study of the double pass solar air heater (DP-SAH) with fins and nano-enhanced PCM for different melting points of the (paraffin wax) and/or different types of nanoparticles such as copper oxide (CuO), and aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃).

- The experimental data presented in this thesis were collected through indoor testing at Heat Transfer Laboratory in the UKM. Though, the indoor experiments are important and help the researcher to control any desired parameter. The work in the field (outdoor) represents the actual condition such as the real solar irradiance, clouds' shading, wind, dust, and variation of the inlet temperature. Therefore, it is suggested to collect these data under outdoor conditions and compare them with the indoor (lab) results. In addition, the effect of different operating conditions, such as solar irradiation, ambient temperature, and humidity, on the performance of the DP-SAH can be studied. This can help in optimizing the design of the system for different geographical locations.
- The design and configuration of the fins in solar air heaters play a significant role in determining their thermal performance. While the present study used staggered rectangular fins, exploring different fin designs and configurations can further improve the efficiency of the heater such as staggered lapping fins.

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APPENDIX A

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

A. Related Journal Papers

- Assadeg, J.**, Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Fudholi, A. & Sopian, K. 2021. Energetic and Exergetic Analysis of a New Double Pass Solar Air Collector with Fins and Phase Change Material. *Solar Energy* 226(260-271).
- Assadeg, J.**, Alwaeli, A. H., Sopian, K., Moria, H., Hamid, A. & Fudholi, A. 2020. Solar Assisted Heat Pump System for High Quality Drying Applications: A Critical Review. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research* 10(1): 303-316.
- Assadeg, J.**, Sopian, K., Ibrahim, A., Fudholi, A. & Alwaeli, A. H. 2023. Thermal and Thermo-hydraulic Performance of Finned Double-Pass Solar Air Collector Utilizing Cylindrical Capsules Nano-Enhanced PCM. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*. (Accepted)

B. Non-Related Journal Papers

- Abd Hamid, A. S., Ibrahim, A., **Assadeg, J.**, Ahmad, E. Z. & Sopian, K. 2020. Techno-Economic Analysis of a Hybrid Solar Dryer with a Vacuum Tube Collector for Hibiscus Cannabinus L Fibre. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research (IJRER)*, 10(4): 1608-1613.
- Assadeg, J.**, Sopian, K. & Fudholi, A. 2019. Performance of Grid-Connected Solar Photovoltaic Power Plants in the Middle East and North Africa. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering* 9(5): 3375.

D. SERI Colloquiums

- Assadeg, J.**, Sopian, K. & Fudholi, A. 2022. Thermal Performance of Finned Double-Pass Solar Air Collector Integrated with Nanoparticle Enhanced PCM Tubular Storage System. *10th Colloquium 2022*.
- Assadeg, J.**, Sopian, K. & Fudholi, A. 2021. Parametric Studies of Double Pass Solar Air collector with Fins and Phase Change Material (PCM). *9th Colloquium 2021*.

E. Patent

- Sopian, K., Ibrahim, A. & **Assadeg, J.** 2023. Double Pass Solar Air Heater with Discontinuous Fins Absorber and Nano Particle-Enhanced PCM Integrated Storage System (In Process)

APPENDIX B

MATLAB CODE - CONVENTIONAL DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER

```

function []= DPSAH(Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=0;
    Tf1new=0;
    Tpnew=0;
    Tf2new=0;
    Tbnew=0;
% The following code is print Table befor the programming
    disp('-----')
    fprintf('   Tg           Tf1           Tp           Tf2
Tb           \n')
    disp('-----')
while (abs(Tg-Tgnew)>0.001 && abs(Tf1-Tf1new)>0.001 && abs(Tp-
Tpnew)>0.001 &&abs(Tf2-Tf2new)>0.001 &&abs(Tb-Tbnew)>0.001)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=Tg;
    Tf1new=Tf1;
    Tpnew=Tp;
    Tf2new=Tf2;
    Tbnew=Tb;
% Values known from experiment
    Ts=6000;           % Temperature of solar intensity (K)
    Ti=298;           % Inlet temperature of air (K)
    Ta=298;           % Ambient temperature (K)
    m_air=0.05;       % mass flow rate of air (kg/s)
    IT=1000;          % Incident solar irradiance (W/m2)
    d1=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    d2=0.1;           % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    Vw=1;             % Wind speed (m/sec)
    Ub=1.6;           % Back loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    LH=1;             % Length of the Heater (m)
    WH=0.3;           % Width of The Heater (m)
    Eg=0.8;           % Emissivity of the glass cover
    tawg=0.92;        % Transmittivity of the glass cover
    Alfag=0.05;       % Absorptivity of the glass cover
    Ep=0.9;           % Emissivity of the absorber plate
    alfap=0.95;       % Absorptivity of the absorber plate
    Eb=0.9;           % Emissivity of the back plate
    sigma=5.67e-8;    % Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m2.K4)
% calculation of sky temperature
    Tsky=0.0552*Ta^1.5;
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 1 (m)
    Dh1=(2*WH*d1)/(WH+d1);
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 2 (m)
    Dh2=(2*WH*d2)/(WH+d2);
% calculation of Area of solar The Heater (m2)
    AH=WH*LH;
% calculation of Heat transfer coefficient due to wind (
W/m2.K)
    hw=2.8+3.3*Vw;

```

```

% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
hrpg = (sigma * (Tp + Tg) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tg ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep + 1
/ Eg - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and back plate (PCM capsules) ( W/m2.K)
hrppcm = (sigma * (Tp + Tb) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tb ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep +
1 / Eb - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
glass cover and sky ( W/m2.K)
hrgs = (sigma*Eg * (Tg + Tsky) * (Tg ^ 2 + Tsky ^ 2) *(Tg -
Tsky)) / (Tg - Ta);
% calculation of top loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
Ut=(1/(hw+hrgs))^-1;
% calculation of Air Density in channel 1 (kg/m3)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
row_air1=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air Density in channel 2 (kg/m3)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
row_air2=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 1 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
cp_air1=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 2 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
cp_air2=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 1 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
meo_air1=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 2 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
meo_air2=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on glass cover (N.s/m2)
meow=(1.983+0.00184*(Tg-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on absorber plate (N.s/m2)
meop=(1.983+0.00184*(Tp-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on back plate (N.s/m2)
meob=(1.983+0.00184*(Tb-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
k_air1=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
k_air2=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 1
V_air1=m_air/(row_air1*WH*d1);
Re1=(V_air1*Dh1*row_air1)/meo_air1;
Pr1=(meo_air1*cp_air1)/k_air1;
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 2
V_air2=m_air/(row_air2*WH*d2);
Re2=(V_air2*Dh2*row_air2)/meo_air2;

```

```

    Pr2=(meo_air2*cp_air2)/k_air2;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1 <6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meow)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
end
h1 = (Nu1 * k_air1) / Dh1;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1<6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
end
h2 = (Nu1 * k_air1 )/ Dh1;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h3 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and fins ( W/m2.K)
h4=h3;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

```

```

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meob)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h5 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of matrix can be presented from M11 to M55 and C1
to C5 for Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2 and Tb
C1= Ut*Ta+Alfag*IT;
C2=-(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C3=alfap*tawg*IT;
C4=(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C5=-Ta*Ub;
M11=h1+hrpg+Ut;
M22=-(h1+h2+(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH)));
M33=h2+h3+hrpg+hrppcm;
M34=-h3;
M42=(4*m_air*cp_air1)/(WH*LH);
M43=-M34;
M44=-(h3+h5+(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH)));
M45=h5;
M54=M45;
M55=-(h5+hrppcm+Ub);
M=[M11 -h1 -hrpg 0 0 ; h1 M22 h2 0 0 ; -hrpg -h2
M33 M34 -hrppcm;0 M42 M43 M44 M45;0 0 hrppcm M54 M55];
C=[C1;C2;C3;C4;C5];
T=inv(M)*C;
Tg=T(1);
Tf1=T(2);
Tp=T(3);
Tf2=T(4);
Tb=T(5);
fprintf(' %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f
\n',Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
end
disp('-----')

% calculation of Outlet temperature of air (K)
To=(2*Tf2-2*Tf1+Ti);
cp_air=(cp_air1+cp_air2)/2;
% calculation of Useful energy gain per hour (W)
Qu=m_air*cp_air*(To-Ti);
% calculation of Thermal Efficiency of Heater (%)
Effen=Qu/(IT*AH);

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 1
if(Re1<2550)
    f1=(24/Re1)+(0.9*(d1/LH));

```

```

else if (Re1>2550 && Re1 <10000)
    f1=0.0094+(2.92*Re1^(-0.15)*(d1/LH));
else if (Re1>10000 && Re1 <100000)
    f1= 0.059*Re1^(-0.2)+0.73*(d1/LH);
end
end
end

dP1=(mair/(LH*Dh1))^2*(1/rowair1)*(LH/Dh1)^3*f1;

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 2

if(Re2<2550)
    f2=(24/Re2)+(0.9*(d2/LH));
else if (Re2>2550 && Re2 <10000)
    f2=0.0094+(2.92*Re2^(-0.15)*(d2/LH));
else if (Re2>10000 && Re2 <100000)
    f2= 0.059*Re2^(-0.2)+0.73*(d2/LH);
end
end
end

dP2=(mair/(LH*Dh2))^2*(1/rowair2)*(LH/Dh2)^3*f2;

% calculation of Total pressure drop
DP=dP1+dP2;
% calculation of Pumping power and Fan power (W)
rowAVG=(rowair1+rowair2)/2;
Pp=(mair*DP)/rowAVG;
Wf=Pp/(0.90*0.90);
% calculation of The thermo-hydraulic efficiency(%)
Effth=(Qu-Wf)/(IT*AH);
% Exergy Analysis:
% calculation of Exergy of the work (fan) (W)
Exw=(Ta/Ti)*Wf;
% calculation of Outlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowoair=1.1774-0.00359*(To-300);
% calculation of inlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowiair=1.1774-0.00359*(Ti-300);
% calculation of average specific heat between outlet and inlet
of The Heater (J/kg.k)
T=(To+Ti)/2;
cpair=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
Exo=mair*(cpair*(To-Ti)-Ta*(719*log(To/Ti)-
8.314*log(rowoair/rowiair)));
% calculation of Exergy input (W)
Exi=AH*IT*(1-(4/3)*(Ta/Ts)+(1/3)*(Ta/Ts)^4);
% calculation of Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
Exop=Exo-Exw;
% calculation of Exergy destruction (W)
Exd=Exi+Exw-Exo;

```

```
% calculation of Exergy efficiency (%)
  Effex=1-(Exd/Exi);
% calculation of Improvement potential (W)
  IP=(1-Effex)*Exd;
fprintf('To=%fK      Ti=%fK      Qu=%f Watt  Effen =
%f\n',To,Ti,Qu,Effen);
fprintf('Wf=%fWatt      Effex = %f  IP=%fWatt
Effth=%f\n',Wf,Effex,IP,Effth);

end
```

APPENDIX C

MATLAB CODE- DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS

```

function []= DPSAHWF(Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=0;
    Tf1new=0;
    Tpnew=0;
    Tf2new=0;
    Tbnew=0;
% The following code is print Table befor the programming
    disp('-----')
    fprintf('  Tg          Tf1          Tp          Tf2
Tb          \n')
    disp('-----')
while (abs(Tg-Tgnew)>0.001 && abs(Tf1-Tf1new)>0.001 && abs(Tp-
Tpnew)>0.001 &&abs(Tf2-Tf2new)>0.001 &&abs(Tb-Tbnew)>0.001)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=Tg;
    Tf1new=Tf1;
    Tpnew=Tp;
    Tf2new=Tf2;
    Tbnew=Tb;
% Values known from the experiment
    Ts=6000;           % Temperature of solar intensity (K)
    Ti=298;           % Inlet temperature of air (K)
    Ta=298;           % Ambient temperature (K)
    m_air=0.05;       % mass flow rate of air (kg/s)
    IT=1000;          % Incident solar irradiance (W/m2)
    d1=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    d2=0.07;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    Nfin=23;          % Number of fins
    Vw=1;             % Wind speed (m/s)
    Ub=1.6;           % Back loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    LH=1;             % Length of the Heater (m)
    WH=0.3;          % Width of the Heater (m)
    Hfin=0.03;        % Height of the fin (m)
    Lfin=0.1;         % Length of fin (m)
    tfin=0.001;      % thickness of fin (m)
    Eg=0.8;           % Emissivity of the glass cover
    tawg=0.92;        % Transmittivity of the glass cover
    Alfag=0.05;       % Absorptivity of the glass cover
    Ep=0.9;           % Emissivity of the absorber plate
    alfab=0.95;       % Absorptivity of the absorber plate
    Eb=0.9;           % Emissivity of the back plate
    kp=211;           % Thermal conductivity of absorber plate (
W/m.K)
    sigma=5.67e-8;    % Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m2.K4)
% calculation of Sectional area of fin (m2)
    Afin=tfin*Hfin;
% calculation of sky temperature
    Tsky=0.0552*Ta1.5;
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 1 (m)

```

```

    Dh1=(2*WH*d1)/(WH+d1);
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 2 (m)
    Dh2=(2*WH*d2)/(WH+d2);
% calculation of Area of solar Heater (m2)
    AH=WH*LH;
% calculation of Heat transfer coefficient due to wind (
W/m2.K)
    hw=2.8+3.3*Vw;
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
    hrpg = (sigma * (Tp + Tg) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tg ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep + 1
/ Eg - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and back plate (nano-enhanced PCM capsules) (
W/m2.K)
    hrppcm = (sigma * (Tp + Tb) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tb ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep +
1 / Eb - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
glass and sky ( W/m2.K)
    hrgs = (sigma*Eg * (Tg + Tsky) * (Tg ^ 2 + Tsky ^ 2) *(Tg -
Tsky)) / (Tg - Ta);
% calculation of top loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    Ut=(1/(hw+hrgs))^-1;
% calculation of Air Density in channel 1 (kg/m3)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    rhoair1=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air Density in channel 2 (kg/m3)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    rhoair2=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 1 (J/kg.k)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    cpair1=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 2 (J/kg.k)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    cpair2=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 1 (N.s/m2)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    meoair1=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 2 (N.s/m2)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    meoair2=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on glass cover (N.s/m2)
    meow=(1.983+0.00184*(Tg-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on absorber plate (N.s/m2)
    meop=(1.983+0.00184*(Tp-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on back plate (N.s/m2)
    meob=(1.983+0.00184*(Tb-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    kair1=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    kair2=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);

```

```

% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 1
    V_air1=m_air/(row_air1*W_H*d1);
    Re1=(V_air1*Dh1*row_air1)/meo_air1;
    Pr1=(meo_air1*cp_air1)/k_air1;
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 2
    V_air2=m_air/(row_air2*W_H*d2);
    Re2=(V_air2*Dh2*row_air2)/meo_air2;
    Pr2=(meo_air2*cp_air2)/k_air2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/L_H))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/L_H))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1 <6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/L_H)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meow)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
end
    h1 = (Nu1 * k_air1) / Dh1;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/L_H))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/L_H))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1<6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/L_H)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
end
    h2 = (Nu1 * k_air1 )/ Dh1;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/L_H))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/L_H))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/L_H)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end

```

```

end
h3 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and fins ( W/m2.K)
h4=h3;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH)) ^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH)) ^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meob)^0.14;
else if (Re2>6000)
Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
end
end
end
h5 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

K=sqrt((2*h4*Lfin)/(kp*Afin));

% calculation of matrix can be presented from M11 to M55 and C1
to C5 for Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2 and Tb
C1= Ut*Ta+Alfag*IT;
C2=-(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C3=alfap*tawg*IT;
C4=(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C5=-Ta*Ub;
M11=h1+hrpg+Ut;
M22=-(h1+h2+(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH)));

M33=h2+h3+hrpg+hrppcm+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin);
M34=-(h3+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin));
M42=(4*m_air*cp_air1)/(WH*LH);
M43=-M34;
M44=-
(h3+h5+(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*ta
nh(K*Hfin));
M45=h5;
M54=M45;
M55=-(h5+hrppcm+Ub);
M=[M11 -h1 -hrpg 0 0 ; h1 M22 h2 0 0 ; -hrpg -h2
M33 M34 -hrppcm;0 M42 M43 M44 M45;0 0 hrppcm M54 M55];
C=[C1;C2;C3;C4;C5];
T=inv(M)*C;
Tg=T(1);
Tf1=T(2);
Tp=T(3);
Tf2=T(4);
Tb=T(5);

```

```

fprintf(' %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f
\n', Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2, Tb)
end
disp('-----')

% calculation of Outlet temperature of air (K)
To=(2*Tf2-2*Tf1+Ti);
cp_air=(cp_air1+cp_air2)/2;
% calculation of Useful energy gain per hour (W)
Qu=m_air*cp_air*(To-Ti);
% calculation of Thermal Efficiency of Heater (%)
Effen=Qu/(IT*AH);

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 1
if(Re1<2550)
    f1=(24/Re1)+(0.9*(d1/LH));
else if (Re1>2550 && Re1 <10000)
    f1=0.0094+(2.92*Re1^(-0.15)*(d1/LH));
    else if (Re1>10000 && Re1 <100000)
        f1= 0.059*Re1^(-0.2)+0.73*(d1/LH);
    end
end
end

dP1=(m_air/(LH*Dh1))^2*(1/row_air1)*(LH/Dh1)^3*f1;

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 2

if(Re2<2550)
    f2=(24/Re2)+(0.9*(d2/LH));
else if (Re2>2550 && Re2 <10000)
    f2=0.0094+(2.92*Re2^(-0.15)*(d2/LH));
    else if (Re2>10000 && Re2 <100000)
        f2= 0.059*Re2^(-0.2)+0.73*(d2/LH);
    end
end
end

dP2=(m_air/(LH*Dh2))^2*(1/row_air2)*(LH/Dh2)^3*f2;

% calculation of Total pressure drop
DP=dP1+dP2;
% calculation of Pumping power and Fan power (W)
rowAVG=(row_air1+row_air2)/2;
Pp=(m_air*DP)/rowAVG;
Wf=Pp/(0.90*0.90);
% calculation of The thermo-hydraulic efficiency(%)
Efffth=(Qu-Wf)/(IT*AH);
% Exergy Analysis:
% calculation of Exergy of the work (fan) (W)
Exw=(Ta/Ti)*Wf;
% calculation of Outlet Air Density (kg/m3)

```

```

    rowo_air=1.1774-0.00359*(To-300);
% calculation of inlet Air Density (kg/m3)
    rowi_air=1.1774-0.00359*(Ti-300);
% calculation of average specific heat between outlet and inlet
of The Heater (J/kg.k)
    T=(To+Ti)/2;
    cp_air=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
    Exo=m_air*(cp_air*(To-Ti)-Ta*(719*log(To/Ti)-
8.314*log(rowo_air/rowi_air)));
% calculation of Exergy input (W)
    Exi=AH*IT*(1-(4/3)*(Ta/Ts)+(1/3)*(Ta/Ts)^4);
% calculation of Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
    Exop=Exo-Exw;
% calculation of Exergy destruction (W)
    Exd=Exi+Exw-Exo;
% calculation of Exergy efficiency (%)
    Effex=1-(Exd/Exi);
% calculation of Improvement potential (W)
    IP=(1-Effex)*Exd;

fprintf('To=%fK      Ti=%fK      Qu=%f Watt  Effen =
%f\n',To,Ti,Qu,Effen);
fprintf('Wf=%fWatt      Effex = %f  IP=%fWatt
Effth=%f\n',Wf,Effex,IP,Effth);

end

```

APPENDIX D

MATLAB CODE- DOUBLE-PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH NANO-ENHANCED PCM

```

function []= DPSAHWNPCM(Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=0;
    Tf1new=0;
    Tpnew=0;
    Tf2new=0;
    Tbnew=0;
% The following code is print Table befor the programming
    disp('-----')
    fprintf('    Tg            Tf1            Tp            Tf2
Tb            \n')
    disp('-----')
while (abs(Tg-Tgnew)>0.001 && abs(Tf1-Tf1new)>0.001 && abs(Tp-
Tpnew)>0.001 &&abs(Tf2-Tf2new)>0.001 &&abs(Tb-Tbnew)>0.001)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=Tg;
    Tf1new=Tf1;
    Tpnew=Tp;
    Tf2new=Tf2;
    Tbnew=Tb;
% Values known from experiment
    Ts=6000;           % Temperature of solar intensity (K)
    Ti=298;           % Inlet temperature of air (K)
    Ta=298;           % Ambient temperature (K)
    m_air=0.05;       % mass flow rate of air (kg/s)
    IT=1000;          % Incident solar irradiance (W/m2)
    d1=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    d2=0.06;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    cp_Nano=2100;     % Nano heat capacity (J/kg.k)
    VNano=7.07e-4;    % Volume of nano-enhanced PCM capsule
    rowNano=930;      % Density of nano-enhanced PCM (kg/m3)
    NNano=23;         % Number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules
    DNano=0.042;      % Diameter of nano-enhanced PCM capsule(m)
    LNano=0.292;     % Length of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
    MNano=7;          % Mass of nano-enhanced PCM (kg)
    HL=2100;          % Latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM (j/kg)
    Vw=1;             % Wind speed (m/s)
    Ub=1.6;           % Back loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    LH=1;             % Length of the Heater (m)
    WH=0.3;           % Width of the Heater (m)
    Eg=0.8;           % Emissivity of the glass cover
    tawg=0.92;        % Transmittivity of the glass cover
    Alfag=0.05;       % Absorptivity of the glass cover
    Ep=0.9;           % Emissivity of the absorber plate
    alfap=0.95;       % Absorptivity of the absorber plate
    Eb=0.9;           % Emissivity of the back plate
    sigma=5.67e-8;    % Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m2.K4)
% calculation of radius of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
    RNano=DNano/2;
% calculation of surface area of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)

```

```

ANano=2*3.14*RNano*(RNano+LNano);
% calculation of sky temperature
Tsky=0.0552*Ta^1.5;
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 1 (m)
Dh1=(2*WH*d1)/(WH+d1);
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 2 (m)
Dh2=(2*WH*d2)/(WH+d2);
% calculation of Area of solar Heater (m2)
AH=WH*LH;
% calculation of Heat transfer coefficient due to wind (
W/m2.K)
hw=2.8+3.3*Vw;
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
hrpg = (sigma * (Tp + Tg) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tg ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep + 1
/ Eg - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and back plate (nano-enhanced PCM capsules) (
W/m2.K)
hrppcm = (sigma * (Tp + Tb) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tb ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep +
1 / Eb - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
glass and sky ( W/m2.K)
hrgs = (sigma*Eg * (Tg + Tsky) * (Tg ^ 2 + Tsky ^ 2) *(Tg -
Tsky)) / (Tg - Ta);
% calculation of top loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
Ut=(1/(hw+hrgs))^-1;
% calculation of Air Density in channel 1 (kg/m3)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
row_air1=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air Density in channel 2 (kg/m3)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
row_air2=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 1 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
cp_air1=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 2 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
cp_air2=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 1 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
meo_air1=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 2 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
meo_air2=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on glass cover (N.s/m2)
meow=(1.983+0.00184*(Tg-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on absorber plate (N.s/m2)
meop=(1.983+0.00184*(Tp-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on back plate (N.s/m2)
meob=(1.983+0.00184*(Tb-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
k_air1=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);

```

```

% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    k_air2=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 1
    V_air1=m_air/(row_air1*WH*d1);
    Re1=(V_air1*Dh1*row_air1)/meo_air1;
    Pr1=(meo_air1*cp_air1)/k_air1;
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 2
    V_air2=m_air/(row_air2*WH*d2);
    Re2=(V_air2*Dh2*row_air2)/meo_air2;
    Pr2=(meo_air2*cp_air2)/k_air2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1 <6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meow)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
    h1 = (Nu1 * k_air1) / Dh1;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1<6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
    end
end
    h2 = (Nu1 * k_air1 )/ Dh1;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meop)^0.14;

```

```

else if (Re2>6000)
    Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
end
end
end
h3 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and nano-enhanced PCM capsules
( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meob)^0.14;
else if (Re2>6000)
    Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
end
end
end
h5 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ( W/m2.K)
h6=h5;

% calculation of matrix can be presented from M11 to M55 and C1
to C5 for Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2 and Tb
C1= Ut*Ta+Alfag*IT;
C2=-(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C3=alfap*tawg*IT;
C4=(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C5=-Ta*Ub;
M11=h1+hrpg+Ut;
M22=-(h1+h2+(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH)));
M33=h2+h3+hrpg+hrppcm;
M34=-(h3);
M42=(4*m_air*cp_air1)/(WH*LH);
M43=-M34;
M44=-(h3+h5+(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))-
NNano/AH*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-mNano*HL)/dt);
M45=h5+NNano/AH*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-mNano*HL)/dt);
M54=M45;
M55=-(h5+hrppcm+Ub)-NNano/AH*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-
mNano*HL/dt);
M=[M11 -h1 -hrpg 0 0 ; h1 M22 h2 0 0 ; -hrpg -h2
M33 M34 -hrppcm;0 M42 M43 M44 M45;0 0 hrppcm M54 M55];
C=[C1;C2;C3;C4;C5];
T=inv(M)*C;
Tg=T(1);
Tf1=T(2);
Tp=T(3);
Tf2=T(4);

```

```

    Tb=T(5);
    fprintf(' %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f      %0.2f
\n',Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
end
disp('-----')

% calculation of Outlet temperature of air (K)
    To=(2*Tf2-2*Tf1+Ti);
    cp_air=(cp_air1+cp_air2)/2;
% calculation of Useful energy gain per hour (W)
    Qu=m_air*cp_air*(To-Ti);
% calculation of Thermal Efficiency of Heater (%)
    Effen=Qu/(IT*AH);

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 1
if(Re1<2550)
    f1=(24/Re1)+(0.9*(d1/LH));
else if (Re1>2550 && Re1 <10000)
    f1=0.0094+(2.92*Re1^(-0.15)*(d1/LH));
    else if (Re1>10000 && Re1 <100000)
        f1= 0.059*Re1^(-0.2)+0.73*(d1/LH);
    end
end
end

dP1=(m_air/(LH*Dh1))^2*(1/row_air1)*(LH/Dh1)^3*f1;

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 2
if(Re2<2550)
    f2=(24/Re2)+(0.9*(d2/LH));
else if (Re2>2550 && Re2 <10000)
    f2=0.0094+(2.92*Re2^(-0.15)*(d2/LH));
    else if (Re2>10000 && Re2 <100000)
        f2= 0.059*Re2^(-0.2)+0.73*(d2/LH);
    end
end
end

dP2=(m_air/(LH*Dh2))^2*(1/row_air2)*(LH/Dh2)^3*f2;

% calculation of Total pressure drop
    DP=dP1+dP2;
% calculation of Pumping power and Fan power (W)
    rowAVG=(row_air1+row_air2)/2;
    Pp=(m_air*DP)/rowAVG;
    Wf=Pp/(0.90*0.90);
% calculation of The thermo-hydraulic efficiency(%)
    Efffth=(Qu-Wf)/(IT*AH);
% Exergy Analysis:
% calculation of Exergy of the work (fan) (W)
    Exw=(Ta/Ti)*Wf;

```

```

% calculation of Outlet Air Density (kg/m³)
rowo_air=1.1774-0.00359*(To-300);
% calculation of inlet Air Density (kg/m³)
rowi_air=1.1774-0.00359*(Ti-300);
% calculation of average specific heat between outlet and inlet
of The Heater (J/kg.k)
T=(To+Ti)/2;
cp_air=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
Exo=m_air*(cp_air*(To-Ti)-Ta*(719*log(To/Ti)-
8.314*log(rowo_air/rowi_air)));
% calculation of Exergy input (W)
Exi=AH*IT*(1-(4/3)*(Ta/Ts)+(1/3)*(Ta/Ts)^4);
% calculation of Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
Exop=Exo-Exw;
% calculation of Exergy destruction (W)
Exd=Exi+Exw-Exo;
% calculation of Exergy efficiency (%)
Effex=1-(Exd/Exi);
% calculation of Improvement potential (W)
IP=(1-Effex)*Exd;

fprintf('To=%fK      Ti=%fK      Qu=%f Watt  Effen =
%f\n',To,Ti,Qu,Effen);
fprintf('Wf=%fWatt      Effex = %f  IP=%fWatt
Effth=%f\n',Wf,Effex,IP,Effth);

end

```

APPENDIX E

MATLAB CODE- DOUBLE PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS AND NANO-ENHANCED PCM

```

function []= DPSAHWFANPCM(Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=0;
    Tf1new=0;
    Tpnew=0;
    Tf2new=0;
    Tbnew=0;
% The following code is print Table befor the programming
    disp('-----')
    fprintf('    Tg            Tf1            Tp            Tf2
Tb            \n')
    disp('-----')
while (abs(Tg-Tgnew)>0.001 && abs(Tf1-Tf1new)>0.001 && abs(Tp-
Tpnew)>0.001 &&abs(Tf2-Tf2new)>0.001 &&abs(Tb-Tbnew)>0.001)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=Tg;
    Tf1new=Tf1;
    Tpnew=Tp;
    Tf2new=Tf2;
    Tbnew=Tb;
% Values known from experiment
Ts=6000;           % Temperature of solar intensity (K)
Ti=298;           % Inlet temperature of air (K)
Ta=298;           % Ambient temperature (K)
m_air=0.05;       % mass flow rate of air (kg/s)
IT=1000;          % Incident solar irradiance (W/m2)
d1=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
d2=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
Nfin=23;         % Number of fins
cp_Nano=2100;     % Nano-enhanced PCM heat capacity (J/kg.k)
VNano=7.07e-4;    % Volume of nano-enhanced PCM capsule
rowNano=930;      % Density of nano-enhanced PCM (kg/m3)
NNano=23;         % Number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules
DNano=0.042;     % Diameter of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
LNano=0.292;     % Length of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
MNano=7;         % Mass of nano-enhanced PCM (kg)
HL=2100;        % Latent heat of nano-enhanced PCM (j/kg)
Vw=1;            % Wind speed (m/s)
Ub=1.6;          % Back loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
LH=1;           % Length of The Heater (m)
WH=0.3;         % Width of The Heater (m)
Hfin=0.03;      % Height of the fin (m)
Lfin=0.1;       % Length of fin (m)
tfin=0.001;    % thickness of fin (m)
Eg=0.85;         % Emissivity of the glass cover
tawg=0.92;       % Transmittivity of the glass cover
Alfag=0.05;      % Absorptivity of the glass cover
Ep=0.96;         % Emissivity of the absorber plate
alfap=0.95;      % Absorptivity of the absorber plate

```

```

Eb=0.9;           % Emissivity of the back plate
kp=211;          % Thermal conductivity of absorber plate (
W/m.K)
sigma=5.67e-8;   % Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m2.K4)
% calculation of radius of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
RNano=DNano/2;
% calculation of Sectional area of fin (m2)
Afin=tfin*Hfin;
% calculation of surface area of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
ANano=2*3.14*RNano*(RNano+LNano);
% calculation of sky temperature
Tsky=0.0552*Ta1.5;
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 1 (m)
Dh1=(2*WH*d1)/(WH+d1);
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 2 (m)
Dh2=(2*WH*d2)/(WH+d2);
% calculation of Area of solar The Heater (m2)
AH=WH*LH;
% calculation of Heat transfer coefficient due to wind (
W/m2.K)
hw=2.8+3.3*Vw;
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
hrpg = (sigma * (Tp + Tg) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tg ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep + 1
/ Eg - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and back plate (nano-enhanced PCM capsules) (
W/m2.K)
hrppcm = (sigma * (Tp + Tb) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tb ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep +
1 / Eb - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
glass cover and sky ( W/m2.K)
hrgs = (sigma*Eg * (Tg + Tsky) * (Tg ^ 2 + Tsky ^ 2) *(Tg -
Tsky)) / (Tg - Ta);
% calculation of top loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
Ut=(1/(hw+hrgs))-1;
% calculation of Air Density in channel 1 (kg/m3)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
row_air1=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air Density in channel 2 (kg/m3)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
row_air2=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 1 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
cp_air1=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 2 (J/kg.k)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
cp_air2=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 1 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
meo_air1=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 2 (N.s/m2)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
meo_air2=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on glass cover (N.s/m2)

```

```

    meow=(1.983+0.00184*(Tg-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on absorber plate (N.s/m2)
    meop=(1.983+0.00184*(Tp-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on back plate (N.s/m2)
    meob=(1.983+0.00184*(Tb-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    k_air1=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    k_air2=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 1
    V_air1=m_air/(row_air1*WH*d1);
    Re1=(V_air1*Dh1*row_air1)/meo_air1;
    Pr1=(meo_air1*cp_air1)/k_air1;
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 2
    V_air2=m_air/(row_air2*WH*d2);
    Re2=(V_air2*Dh2*row_air2)/meo_air2;
    Pr2=(meo_air2*cp_air2)/k_air2;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1 <6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1(2/3)-
125)*Pr1(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)(2/3))*(meo_air1/meow)0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re10.8*Pr10.4;
    end
end
h1 = (Nu1 * k_air1) / Dh1;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/LH))1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/LH))1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1<6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1(2/3)-
125)*Pr1(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/LH)(2/3))*(meo_air1/meop)0.14;
    else if (Re1>6000)
        Nu1=0.018*Re10.8*Pr10.4;
    end
end
h2 = (Nu1 * k_air1 )/ Dh1;

```

```

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h3 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and fins ( W/m2.K)
h4=h3;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and nano-enhanced PCM capsules
( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meob)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h5 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ( W/m2.K)
h6=h5;
K=sqrt((2*h4*Lfin)/(kp*Afin));

% calculation of matrix can be presented from M11 to M55 and C1
to C5 for Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2 and Tb
C1= Ut*Ta+Alfag*IT;
C2=-(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C3=alfap*tawg*IT;
C4=(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C5=-Ta*Ub;
M11=h1+hrpg+Ut;
M22=-(h1+h2+(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH)));

M33=h2+h3+hrpg+hrppcm+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin);
M34=-(h3+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin));
M42=(4*m_air*cp_air1)/(WH*LH);

```

```

M43=-M34;
M44=(h3+h5+(2*m_air*cp_air2/(W_H*L_H))+N_fin/A_H*(2*kp*A_fin*L_fin*h4
^0.5*tanh(K*H_fin)-NNano/A_H*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-
mNano*H_L)/dt));
M45=h5+NNano/A_H*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-mNano*H_L)/dt);
M54=M45;
M55=-(h5+hrppcm+Ub)-NNano/A_H*((rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano-
mNano*H_L)/dt);
M=[M11 -h1 -hrpg 0 0 ; h1 M22 h2 0 0 ; -hrpg -h2
M33 M34 -hrppcm;0 M42 M43 M44 M45;0 0 hrppcm M54 M55];
C=[C1;C2;C3;C4;C5];
T=inv(M)*C;
Tg=T(1);
Tf1=T(2);
Tp=T(3);
Tf2=T(4);
Tb=T(5);
fprintf(' %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f
\n',Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
end
disp('-----')

% calculation of Outlet temperature of air (K)
To=(2*Tf2-2*Tf1+Ti);
cp_air=(cp_air1+cp_air2)/2;
% calculation of Useful energy gain per hour (W)
Qu=m_air*cp_air*(To-Ti);
% calculation of Thermal Efficiency of The Heater (%)
Effen=Qu/(I_T*A_H);

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 1
if(Re1<2550)
    f1=(24/Re1)+(0.9*(d1/L_H));
else if (Re1>2550 && Re1 <10000)
    f1=0.0094+(2.92*Re1^(-0.15)*(d1/L_H));
else if (Re1>10000 && Re1 <100000)
    f1= 0.059*Re1^(-0.2)+0.73*(d1/L_H);
end
end
end

dP1=(m_air/(L_H*Dh1))^2*(1/row_air1)*(L_H/Dh1)^3*f1;

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 2

if(Re2<2550)
    f2=(24/Re2)+(0.9*(d2/L_H));
else if (Re2>2550 && Re2 <10000)
    f2=0.0094+(2.92*Re2^(-0.15)*(d2/L_H));
else if (Re2>10000 && Re2 <100000)
    f2= 0.059*Re2^(-0.2)+0.73*(d2/L_H);
end
end

```

```

end
end

dP2=(m_air/(LH*Dh2))^2*(1/row_air2)*(LH/Dh2)^3*f2;

% calculation of Total pressure drop
DP=dP1+dP2;
% calculation of Pumping power and Fan power (W)
rowAVG=(row_air1+row_air2)/2;
Pp=(m_air*DP)/rowAVG;
Wf=Pp/(0.90*0.90);
% calculation of The thermo-hydraulic efficiency(%)
Effth=(Qu-Wf)/(IT*AH);
% Exergy Analysis:
% calculation of Exergy of the work (fan) (W)
Exw=(Ta/Ti)*Wf;
% calculation of Outlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowo_air=1.1774-0.00359*(To-300);
% calculation of inlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowi_air=1.1774-0.00359*(Ti-300);
% calculation of average specific heat between outlet and inlet
of The Heater (J/kg.k)
T=(To+Ti)/2;
cp_air=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
Exo=m_air*(cp_air*(To-Ti)-Ta*(719*log(To/Ti)-
8.314*log(rowo_air/rowi_air)));
% calculation of Exergy input (W)
Exi=AH*IT*(1-(4/3)*(Ta/Ts)+(1/3)*(Ta/Ts)^4);
% calculation of Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
Exop=Exo-Exw;
% calculation of Exergy destruction (W)
Exd=Exi+Exw-Exo;
% calculation of Exergy efficiency (%)
Effex=1-(Exd/Exi);
% calculation of Improvement potential (W)
IP=(1-Effex)*Exd;

fprintf('To=%fK      Ti=%fK      Qu=%f Watt  Effen =
%f\n',To,Ti,Qu,Effen);
fprintf('Wf=%fWatt      Effex = %f  IP=%fWatt
Effth=%f\n',Wf,Effex,IP,Effth);

end

```

APPENDIX F

MATLAB CODE- COST-BENEFIT RATIO ANALYSIS

```

function []= DPSAHWFANPCMEC (Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=0;
    Tf1new=0;
    Tpnew=0;
    Tf2new=0;
    Tbnew=0;
% The following code is print Table befor the programming
    disp('-----')
    fprintf('   Tg           Tf1           Tp           Tf2
Tb           \n')
    disp('-----')
while (abs(Tg-Tgnew)>0.001 && abs(Tf1-Tf1new)>0.001 && abs(Tp-
Tpnew)>0.001 &&abs(Tf2-Tf2new)>0.001 &&abs(Tb-Tbnew)>0.001)
% Guess Values of Temperatures for the unknown
    Tgnew=Tg;
    Tf1new=Tf1;
    Tpnew=Tp;
    Tf2new=Tf2;
    Tbnew=Tb;
% Values known from experiment
    Ts=6000;           % Temperature of solar intensity (K)
    Ti=298;           % Inlet temperature of air (K)
    Ta=298;           % Ambient temperature (K)

    m_air=0.05;       % mass flow rate of air (kg/s)
    IT=700;           % Incident solar irradiance (W/m2)
    LH=3.0;           % Length of The Heater (m)
    WH=0.3;           % Width of The Heater (m)

    d1=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    d2=0.03;          % Depth of the upper channel (m)
    N_fin=23;         % Number of fins
    cp_Nano=2100;     % Nano-enhanced PCM heat capacity (J/kg.k)
    VNano=7.07e-4;    % Volume of nano-enhanced PCM capsule
    rowNano=930;      % Density of nano-enhanced PCM (kg/m3)
    NNano=23;         % Number of nano-enhanced PCM capsules
    DNano=0.042;      % Diameter of nano-enhanced PCM capsule(m)
    LNano=0.292;      % Length of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
    Vw=1;             % Wind speed (m/s)
    Ub=1.6;           % Back loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    H_fin=0.03;       % Height of the fin (m)
    L_fin=0.1;        % Length of fin (m)
    t_fin=0.001;      % thickness of fin (m)
    Eg=0.85;          % Emissivity of the glass cover
    tawg=0.92;        % Transmittivity of the glass cover
    Alfag=0.05;       % Absorptivity of the glass cover
    Ep=0.96;          % Emissivity of the absorber plate
    alfap=0.95;       % Absorptivity of the absorber plate
    Eb=0.9;           % Emissivity of the back plate

```

```

    kp=211; % Thermal conductivity of absorber plate (
W/m.K)
    sigma=5.67e-8; % Stefan's Boltzmann constant (W/m2.K4)
% calculation of radius of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
    RNano=DNano/2;
% calculation of Sectional area of fin (m2)
    A_fin=t_fin*H_fin;
% calculation of surface area of nano-enhanced PCM capsule (m)
    ANano=2*3.14*RNano*(RNano+LNano);
% calculation of sky temperature
    Tsky=0.0552*Ta^1.5;
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 1 (m)
    Dh1=(2*W_H*d1)/(W_H+d1);
% calculation of Hydraulic diameter in channel 2 (m)
    Dh2=(2*W_H*d2)/(W_H+d2);
% calculation of Area of solar The Heater (m2)
    A_H=W_H*L_H;
% calculation of Heat transfer coefficient due to wind (
W/m2.K)
    hw=2.8+3.3*Vw;
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
    hrpg = (sigma * (Tp + Tg) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tg ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep + 1
/ Eg - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
absorber plate and back plate (nano-enhanced PCM capsules) (
W/m2.K)
    hrppcm = (sigma * (Tp + Tb) * (Tp ^ 2 + Tb ^ 2)) / (1 / Ep +
1 / Eb - 1);
% calculation of radiative Heat transfer coefficient between
glass cover and sky ( W/m2.K)
    hrsg = (sigma*Eg * (Tg + Tsky) * (Tg ^ 2 + Tsky ^ 2) * (Tg -
Tsky)) / (Tg - Ta);
% calculation of top loss coefficient ( W/m2.K)
    Ut=(1/(hw+hrsg))^-1;
% calculation of Air Density in channel 1 (kg/m3)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    row_air1=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air Density in channel 2 (kg/m3)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    row_air2=1.1774-0.00359*(T-300);
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 1 (J/kg.k)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    cp_air1=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air specific heat in channel 2 (J/kg.k)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    cp_air2=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 1 (N.s/m2)
    T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
    meo_air1=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity in channel 2 (N.s/m2)
    T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
    meo_air2=(1.983+0.00184*(T-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on glass cover (N.s/m2)
    meow=(1.983+0.00184*(Tg-300))*1e-5;

```

```

% calculation of Air viscosity on absorber plate (N.s/m2)
meop=(1.983+0.00184*(Tp-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of Air viscosity on back plate (N.s/m2)
meob=(1.983+0.00184*(Tb-300))*1e-5;
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
T=(Tg+Tp)/2;
k_air1=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of thermal conductivity of air in channel 1
(W/m.k)
T=(Tp+Tb)/2;
k_air2=0.02624+0.0000758*(T-300);
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 1
V_air1=m_air/(row_air1*W_H*d1);
Re1=(V_air1*Dh1*row_air1)/meo_air1;
Pr1=(meo_air1*cp_air1)/k_air1;
% calculation of Fluid Speed, Reynolds and Prandtl numbers in
channel 2
V_air2=m_air/(row_air2*W_H*d2);
Re2=(V_air2*Dh2*row_air2)/meo_air2;
Pr2=(meo_air2*cp_air2)/k_air2;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and glass cover ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/L_H))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/L_H))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1 <6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/L_H)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meow)^0.14;
else if (Re1>6000)
    Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
end
end
h1 = (Nu1 * k_air1) / Dh1;
% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the upper channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)
if(Re1<2300)

Nu1=5.4+(0.00190*(Re1*Pr1*(Dh1/L_H))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re1*Pr1*(
Dh1/L_H))^1.17);
else if (Re1>2300 && Re1<6000)
    Nu1=0.116*(Re1^(2/3)-
125)*Pr1^(1/3)*(1+(Dh1/L_H)^(2/3))*(meo_air1/meop)^0.14;
else if (Re1>6000)
    Nu1=0.018*Re1^0.8*Pr1^0.4;
end
end
h2 = (Nu1 * k_air1 )/ Dh1;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and absorber plate ( W/m2.K)

```

```

if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meop)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h3 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and fins ( W/m2.K)
h4=h3;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and nano-enhanced PCM capsules
( W/m2.K)
if(Re2<2300)

Nu2=5.4+(0.00190*(Re2*Pr2*(Dh2/LH))^1.71)/(1+0.00563*(Re2*Pr2*(
Dh2/LH))^1.17);
else if (Re2>2300 && Re2<6000)
    Nu2=0.116*(Re2^(2/3)-
125)*Pr2^(1/3)*(1+(Dh2/LH)^(2/3))*(meo_air2/meob)^0.14;
    else if (Re2>6000)
        Nu2=0.018*Re2^0.8*Pr2^0.4;
    end
end
end
h5 = (Nu2 * k_air2 )/ Dh2;

% calculation of convective Heat transfer coefficient between
air flowing in the lower channel and back plate ( W/m2.K)
h6=h5;
K=sqrt((2*h4*Lfin)/(kp*Afin));

% calculation of matrix can be presented from M11 to M55 and C1
to C5 for Tg, Tf1, Tp, Tf2 and Tb
C1= Ut*Ta+Alfag*IT;
C2=-(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C3=alfap*tawg*IT;
C4=(2*m_air*cp_air2/(WH*LH))*Ti;
C5=-Ta*Ub;
M11=h1+hrpg+Ut;
M22=-(h1+h2+(2*m_air*cp_air1/(WH*LH)));

M33=h2+h3+hrpg+hrppcm+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin);
M34=-(h3+Nfin/AH*(2*kp*Afin*Lfin*h4)^0.5*tanh(K*Hfin));
M42=(4*m_air*cp_air1)/(WH*LH);
M43=-M34;

```

```

M44=-
(h3+h5+(2*m_air*cp_air2/(*L_H))+N_fin/A_H*(2*kp*A_fin*L_fin*h4)^0.5*tanh
(K*H_fin))-NNano/A_H*(rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano/3600);
M45=h5+NNano/A_H*(rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano/3600);
M54=M45;
M55=-(h5+hrppcm+Ub)-NNano/A_H*(rowNano*cp_Nano*VNano/3600);
M=[M11 -h1 -hrpg 0 0 ; h1 M22 h2 0 0 ; -hrpg -h2
M33 M34 -hrppcm;0 M42 M43 M44 M45;0 0 hrppcm M54 M55];
C=[C1;C2;C3;C4;C5];
T=inv(M)*C;
Tg=T(1);
Tf1=T(2);
Tp=T(3);
Tf2=T(4);
Tb=T(5);
fprintf(' %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f %0.2f
\n',Tg,Tf1,Tp,Tf2,Tb)
end
disp('-----
-----')

% calculation of Outlet temperature of air (K)
To=(2*Tf2-2*Tf1+Ti);
cp_air=(cp_air1+cp_air2)/2;
% calculation of Useful energy gain per hour (W)
Qu=m_air*cp_air*(To-Ti);
% calculation of Thermal Efficiency of The Heater (%)
Effen=Qu/(IT*A_H);

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 1
if(Re1<2550)
    f1=(24/Re1)+(0.9*(d1/L_H));
else if (Re1>2550 && Re1 <10000)
    f1=0.0094+(2.92*Re1^(-0.15))*(d1/L_H);
else if (Re1>10000 && Re1 <100000)
    f1= 0.059*Re1^(-0.2)+0.73*(d1/L_H);
end
end
end

dP1=(m_air/(L_H*Dh1))^2*(1/row_air1)*(L_H/Dh1)^3*f1;

% calculation of the pressure drop in channel 2

if(Re2<2550)
    f2=(24/Re2)+(0.9*(d2/L_H));
else if (Re2>2550 && Re2 <10000)
    f2=0.0094+(2.92*Re2^(-0.15))*(d2/L_H);
else if (Re2>10000 && Re2 <100000)
    f2= 0.059*Re2^(-0.2)+0.73*(d2/L_H);
end
end
end

```

```

end

dP2=(m_air/(LH*Dh2))^2*(1/row_air2)*(LH/Dh2)^3*f2;

% calculation of Total pressure drop
DP=dP1+dP2;
% calculation of Pumping power and Fan power (W)
rowAVG=(row_air1+row_air2)/2;
Pp=(m_air*DP)/rowAVG;
Wf=Pp/(0.90*0.90);
% calculation of The thermo-hydraulic efficiency(%)
Effth=(Qu-Wf)/(IT*AH);
% Exergy Analysis:
% calculation of Exergy of the work (fan) (W)
Exw=(Ta/Ti)*Wf;
% calculation of Outlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowo_air=1.1774-0.00359*(To-300);
% calculation of inlet Air Density (kg/m3)
rowi_air=1.1774-0.00359*(Ti-300);
% calculation of average specific heat between outlet and inlet
of The Heater (J/kg.k)
T=(To+Ti)/2;
cp_air=(1.0057+0.000066*(T-300))*1e3;
% calculation of Exergy output ignoring pressure drop (W)
Exo=m_air*(cp_air*(To-Ti)-Ta*(719*log(To/Ti)-
8.314*log(rowo_air/rowi_air)));
% calculation of Exergy input (W)
Exi=AH*IT*(1-(4/3)*(Ta/Ts)+(1/3)*(Ta/Ts)^4);
% calculation of Exergy output considering pressure drop (W)
Exop=Exo-Exw;
% calculation of Exergy destruction (W)
Exd=Exi+Exw-Exo;
% calculation of Exergy efficiency (%)
Effex=1-(Exd/Exi);
% calculation of Improvement potential (W)
IP=(1-Effex)*Exd;
% Calculation of Economic Analysis
CE=0.221; % Cost of electricity
(RM/kWh)
r=0.1; % Interest rate (%)
n=10; % System life time
(years)
HAC=180; % Heater array cost (RM)
HSSC=84; % Heater support
structure cost (RM)
HFC=225; % Heater fabrication cost
(RM)
% Calculation of operational time
top=312*12;
% Calculation of Annual Thermal Energy Gain (kWh)
ATEG=Qu*top/1000;
% Calculation of Annual Pumping Cost (RM)
APC=(m_air*DP/rowAVG)*312*0.221;
% Calculation of capital investment (RM)
CI=HAC+HSSC+HFC;

```

```

% Calculation of Annual Salvage Value (RM)
SFF=r/((r+1)^n-1);
SV=0.1*CI;
ASV=SFF*SV;
% Calculation of capital recovery factor
CRF=(r*(r+1)^n)/((r+1)^n-1);
% Calculation of Annual capital cost (RM)
ACC=CRF*CI;
% Calculation of Maintenance cost (RM)
MC=0.1*CI;
% Calculation of Annual cost (RM)
AC=ACC+MC+APC-ASV;

fprintf('To=%fK      Ti=%fK      Qu=%f Watt  Effen =
%f\n',To,Ti,Qu,Effen);
fprintf('Wf=%fWatt      Effex = %f  IP=%fWatt
Effth=%f\n',Wf,Effex,IP,Effth);
fprintf('ATEG=%fkWh      AC=%fRM      AC/ATEG=%f\n',ATEG,AC,AC/ATEG);
end

```

APPENDIX G

DESIGNS AND DIMENSIONS- DOUBLE PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS AND NANO-ENHANCED PCM

PROJECT: AIR MANIFOLD

DIMENSION : MM

MATERIAL : STEEL

PROJECT: FIN

DIMENSION : MM

MATERIAL : ALUMINIUM

PROJECT: NANO-ENHANCED PCM CAPSULE

DIMENSION : MM

MATERIAL : STEEL

PROJECT: GLASS COVER

DIMENSION : MM

MATERIAL : GLASS & STEEL

PROJECT: FRAME
DIMENSION : MM
MATERIAL : STEEL

PROJECT: DOUBLE PASS SOLAR AIR HEATER WITH FINS AND NANO-ENHANCED PCM

MATERIAL : STEEL, ALUMINIUM AND GLASS

Glass panel with adjustable height to meet requirement of 30-100 mm channel height

APPENDIX H
THE SOLAR SIMULATOR MAPPING IN 3-D

Figure H.1 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 3-D

Figure H.2 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 3-D

Figure H.3 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 3-D

Figure H.4 Solar simulator mapping ($I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$) in 3-D

APPENDIX I

DETAILS OF TOOLS AND EQUIPMENT

1. Portable Precision Balance (**AND-EJ610**)

Model: EJ-610
UPC : 081159845964
Brand: A&D WEIGHING

The EJ "Newton" precision compact balances provide a wide range of features that may be customised to meet the requirements of a wide variety of weighing applications. Users have grown to anticipate a certain level of performance from A&D products, and the Newton delivers on that promise. The Newton is a balance that is powered by alkaline batteries, has a quick reaction time, and is reliable. Because of its mobility, it adds a new level of affordability to the practise of precise weighing.

Special Features:

- Battery Operated (4 AA)
- Large Easy to Read Backlit LCD Display
- Standard AC Adaptor
- GLP Output
- Comparator Mode Display
- Counting Mode
- Percentage Mode
- Fast Stabilization Time (1 sec)
- Underhook Weighing Option
- Anti-Theft Device Option
- Carry Case Option

Technical Details

Capacity	610 g
Readability	0.01 g
Pan Size	4.3"
Minimum Display	0.01 g
Repeatability	0.01 g
Linearity	+/- 0.02g
Sensitivity Drift	+/- 20 ppm / 10°C (10 °C -30 °C / 50 °F - 86 °F)
No. of Samples	5,10,25,50 or 100 pieces
Maximum Count	61,000 pcs
Minimum Unit Weight	0.01 g
Minimum % Display	0.1%
Minimum 100% Weight	1 g
Display Update	10 times per second
Units	Gram (g),Pound (lb),Ounce (oz),Ounce Troy (ozt),Carat (ct),Pennyweight (dwt), Grain (GN),Momme (mom),Tael (tl),Tola
Display	Backlit LCD
Power Source	Standard AC Adaptor / 4 AA Alkaline Batteries
Battery Operating Time	70 hrs w. backlight OFF on alkaline batteries
Operating Temperature	-10 deg C - 40 deg C / 14 deg F - 104 deg F
Scale Dimensions	8.5" x 7" x 2.25" / 216 x 178 x 57 mm
Scale Weight	approx 850 g
Calibration Weight	600 g

2. Ultrasonic Shaker (**TELSONIC ULTRASONICS CT-12**)

TPC Series in collaboration with Telsonic AG, Switzerland

Cavitation is the fast production and collapse of minute bubbles in liquid, and it is caused by ultrasonics, which are high-frequency vibrations. Cavitation is generated by ultrasonics, which are high-frequency vibrations. When bubbles are imploded using high pressure on the exposed surface of a component, contaminants such as dirt, dust, oil, grease, chips, wax, lapping paste, carbon, and other substances are dislodged and removed. It is useful for cleaning spots that are difficult to reach. In a cleaning system with many chambers and operations, a very high level of cleanliness may be reached by correctly orienting the components, filtering the cleaning liquid, washing the components, and finally drying the components using air and/or a vacuum.

Technical Details

Type		TPC-15H	TPC-25H	TPC-40H	TPC-120H	TPC-280H
Mains Voltage	V	230	230	230	230	230
Current consumption incl.	A _{max}	0.8	1.0	1.2	5.0	8.0
Ultrasonic output eff/peak	W _{max}	75/150	75/150	150/300	300/600	600/1200
Operating frequency	Khz	30	30	30	30	20/30/40
Digital Thermostats	20-80°C	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Digital Timer	1s-99min	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Heating power	W	120	150	150	800	1200
Tank capacity	L	1.5	2.5	4	12	28
Int. Dimensions	L	150	235	235	300	505
	W	135	135	135	235	300
	D	100	100	150	200	200
Ext. Dimensions	L	180	265	265	330	535
	W	165	165	165	270	330
	D	220	220	262	325	370
Outlet valve		No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Weight	Kg	3.0	3.5	4.5	9.0	18.0

3. Thermal Properties Meter (**KD2 Pro**)

Code: SL368
Other Standards : ASTM D5334-08
Tariff : 848079 00 0

Product description

The KD2-Pro is a thermal properties analyzer that may be used in the lab as well as in the field. The thermal diffusivity, specific heat (heat capacity), thermal conductivity, and thermal resistivity are all measured with the use of the transient line heat source technique. An in-depth understanding of the processes of heat and mass movement in soils and other porous materials is the foundation for an in-depth and sophisticated data analysis. Along with the ability to save data and a mode that automatically collects data, the KD2 Pro comes with three replaceable sensors that measure thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and specific heat (heat capacity). It enables unattended measurements, which may be programmed by the user, as well as on-board data storage with room for more than 4,000 measurements.

Specifications

Accuracy	±5 to ±10% Thermal Conductivity/Resistivity ±10% Specific Heat ±10% Thermal Diffusivity
Measurement Speed	1, 2, 5, & 10 min. read times (see user's manual for more information)
Data Storage	4,095 readings, flash memory
Compliance to Standards	IEEE Standard 442-1981 and ASTM Standard D5334-08
Operating Environment of Sensors	-50 to 150°C
Battery Source	4 x AA
Auto-Read Mode	Users can collect unattended data at user-defined intervals in the auto-read mode
Type	Ultra-low-power 16-bit micro-controller w/ 24-bit A/D converter
Display	Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) 7.5 cm x 4 cm
Case Dimensions	15.5 x 9.5 x 3.5 cm
Included Accessories	KS-1 Thermal Conductivity/Resistivity sensor (for liquids) TR-1 Thermal Conductivity/Resistivity sensor (for solids) SH-1 Dual-needle Thermal Properties sensor User's manual Pelican carrying case Readout stand Performance verification standards Thermal grease Drill bit for drilling pilot holes in materials Concrete pilot pin KD2 Pro download utility RS232 cable
Calibration	Each KD2 Pro comes factory calibrated and includes performance verification standards
Range of Measurements	K: 0.02 to 4 Wm ⁻¹ C ⁻¹ D: 0.1 to 1.0 mm ² s ⁻¹ R: 0.25 to 50mC W ⁻¹ C: 0.5 to 4 MJ m ⁻³ C ⁻¹ * Accuracy and measurement range vary with sensor type. See Sensor(s) Information.

4. Digital Liquid Densitometer (DH-300L)

Model: DH-300L
Other Standards : ASTM D792
Brand Name: DahoMeter

Features:

- Density value can be showed by one procedure;repeatedly continuous rapid measurement can be worked.
- Take samples conveniently;50CC or less would be okay.
- There is no cumbersome debugging and operation compared with traditional wechsler balance method and pycnometer method.
- It is very easy to clean measurement cup;can't get the limitation of the size of pycnometer caliber.
- Coordinate with the operation of thermostatic tank to measure the proportion with the required temperature.
- Adopt the completed special windproof and dustproof cover,which makes the structure convenient and durable.
- Volatile liquid,corrosivity liquid,vicidity liquid,strong acid and strong lye liquid can be measured quickly.

Specifications:

- Model:DH-300L
- Density resolution: 0.001 g/cm³.
- Maximum weight:300g.
- Minimum weight:0.005g.
- Measuring range: 0.001-99.999g/cm³.

Measurement type:

- Measurement Principle:Archimedes principle displacement method
- Measurement mode :1 group
- Measurement time :About 5 seconds
- Memory mode :memory in shorter time by one procedure
- Result disply :Density value
- Specific Gravity Measurement frame:stainless steel specific gravity measurement frame
- Calibration mode :auto correction with one button,auto detection.
- Measurement testing :distilled testing
- Output mode :standard interface of RS-232,output and print testing data conveniently

Technical Details

Manufacturer	HFBTE
Part Number	HFBTE
Item Weight	8.8 pounds
Product Dimensions	17.32 x 7.48 x 13.78 inches
Country of Origin	China
Size	Medium
Color	Blue+White
Style	Digital
Material	Plastic
Pattern	DH-300L(Max Weight 300g)
Power Source	Battery Powered
Batteries Included	NO
Batteries Required	NO

5. Viscosity meter (**LVDV-III ultra-programmable**)

Model: DV3TLV

Company Name: Brookfield

ISO Certification: 9001:2015

Description / Introduction

The Viscosity meter provides exceptional versatility in the modes of control, allowing the user to choose between traditional standalone operation, automatic operation via programmes downloaded from the PC, or complete control by PC utilising Brookfield RheocalcT Software. These modes of control are available in addition to traditional standalone operation.

- The Viscosity meter may be used as a classic Brookfield rheometer for the collection of single speed viscosity data using the simple to use touch screen. All that is required is to pick the spindle and speed, and then read the result from the display.
- The Viscosity meter has the capability to gather many data points via the use of programmes that may be built immediately on the touchscreen display.
- When equipped with the optional vane spindles, the Viscosity meter is able to provide a measurement that is direct of the yield stress.
- The Brookfield PG Flash Software may be used to programme the Viscosity meter to manage all parts of the test and data collecting without the requirement for the operator to watch the instrument; all the operator has to do is start the programme and then return to the printed test results (printer is optional). [For more information about PG Flash Software,
- The Brookfield RheocalcT Software will provide a platform for sophisticated data collecting and analysis in addition to performing all control and data collection operations of the Viscosity meter from the PC where it will be installed.

Technical Details

Speed	0.01 - 250 RPM
Gross Weight	10.5 kg
Net Weight	9 kg
Carton Volume	0.05 m ³
Carton Dimensions	22 in. (56 cm) W x 11 in. (28 cm) L x 22 in. (56 cm) H
Temperature Sensing Range:	-100°C to 300°C (-148°F to 572°F)
Viscosity Accuracy	±1.0% of full scale range
Viscosity Repeatability	±0.2% of Full Scale Range
Temperature Accuracy	±1°C -100°C to +149°C ±2°C +150°C to +300°C
Input Voltage	Universal Power Supply (90 - 264 VAC)
Number of increments	2.6K
Math Modeling	Temperature Control
Input Frequency	50/60 Hz
Power Consumption	150 VA
Operating Environment	0°C to 40°C temperature range (32°F to 104°F) 20% - 80%R.H.: non-condensing atmosphere

6. Data Acquisition System (anbai-AT4542)

Characters

- Range : -200° C~1300° C
- Resolution : 0.1° C
- Channel : Max extend to 128 channels
- Universal thermocouple input

AT45 series

AT45 series multi-channel temperature metres are controlled by a high-performance ARM microprocessor, have the ability to collect temperature data from multiple channels at once, provide upper/lower beep and communication transport, have a capacity that can be increased to 128 channels, are compatible with a wide range of temperature sensors, have a quick response, maintain stable data, and have a function that checks for broken detection.

Instrument supports RS-232 communication, and it is possible to complete data collecting, analysis, and printing using the computer software that comes included. provide support for storage on USB discs and save collected samples in real time. The user is able to independently adjust the data for each channel.

SPECIFICATIONS	
AT45 series	
Graduation	Thermocouple : J/K/T/E/S/N/B/R Thermal resistance PT100,CU50 (only for A series)
Accuracy	±0.2%±2dgt(not includ thermocouple)
Range	-200 °C ~1300 °C (variation depend on graduation)
Resolution	0.1°C
Channel	AT4508: 8 channel ; max 128 channels AT4516: 16 channel; max 128 channels AT4524: 24 channel ; max 128 channels AT4532: 32 channel ; max 128 channels
scan speed	fast : 100ms medium : 500ms slow : 1s
Adjustment	Error correction for each channel
Comparator	upper / lower beep, Each channel is set separately, upper /lower limit value
Interface	RS232C U disk
Software	ATS45data collection software
C o l d Junction	Accuracy : 0.5°C
Others	TFT-LCD color display , broken thermo- couple check function, Composite sam- pling
P o w e r supply	voltage : 85VAC ~ 260VAC Frequency : 50Hz/60Hz Power : 10VA
Sizes weight	216 * 88 * x300mm 3kg
Accessories	AT4508: thermocouple 8pcs (2m/pcs) AT4516: thermocouple 16pcs(2m/pcs) AT4524: 24pcs (2m/pcs AT4532: 32pcs (2m/pcs U disk standard data collection software ATL108 232 cable ATN2 USB box

7. Solar Irradiance Meter (pyranometer model TES 132)

Pyranometer (Datalogging)

Model: TES 132

Product description

The TES 132 Solar Power Meter is a precise equipment that is used in the field for the purpose of measuring solar radiation. It has had the complete cosine correction applied in order to account for the angle of sun incidence. The solar power metre is small, hardy, and simple to use all at the same time. The sun sensitive component that is used in the metre is a highly stable silicon photovoltaic detector that has a lengthy life span.

Specifications

- Range: 200.0 W/m² ,2000 W/m² 63.4 Btu/(ft² x h) , 634 Btu / (ft² x h)
- Resolution:0.1 W/m² ,1 W/m²0.1 Btu/(ft² x h) , 1 Btu / (ft² x h)
- Accuracy:±0.7dB (ref 94dB @1KHz)
- Sampling Rate:1 times/sec
- Battery:6 pcs 1.5V size AAA ●Battery life:Approx. 50hrs
- Size: 150(L)x72(W)x35(H) mm & Approx. 320g

Description Of LCD Display

- LCD Display: Display 4 digit displays with a maximum reading of 9999, the measured values, unit function symbols, and decimal points.
- Manual Data Memory Capacity : 99 sets.

Technical Details

Manufacturer	TES Electrical Electronic Corp.
Part Number	TES 132
Item Weight	11.3 ounces
Product Dimensions	5.91 x 2.83 x 1.38 inches
Item model number	TES-132
Batteries	6 AAA batteries required. (included)
Is Discontinued By Manufacturer	No
Size	full size
Color	Green
Material	Plastic
Power Source	battery-powered
Item Package Quantity	1
Included Components	Operation Manual, 6 pcs 1.5V size AAA, USB Cable, CD software
Batteries Included?	Yes
Batteries Required?	Yes
Description Pile	6 pcs 1.5V size AAA
Average Battery Life	50 Hours

8. Air Speed Meter (Anemometer model Lutron AM-4206)

Anemometer (ISO-9001, CE, IEC1010)

Model: AM-4206

FEATURES	
* Air flow : CMM (m ³ /min.) and CFM (ft ³ /min.)	* Thermistor sensor for temp. measurement, fast response time.
* Air velocity : m/s, ft/min, km/h, knots.	* Build-in low battery indicator.
* Air temperature : C degree, F degree.	* Operates from 006P DC 9V battery.
* 3 air flow mode : Instant, 2/3 Vmax, Average.	* RS 232 PC serial interface.
* Low-friction ball vane wheels is accurate in both high & low velocities.	* Separate probe, easy for operation of the different measurement environment.
* Large LCD with dual display.	* Used the durable, long-lasting components, including a strong, light weight ABS-plastic housing case.
* Record maximum and minimum reading with recall.	
* Data hold.	* Wide applications: use this anemometer to check air conditioning & heating systems, measure air velocities, wind speeds, temperature.
* Microcomputer circuit provides special function & offer high accuracy.	
* Auto shut off saves battery life.	

GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS			
Circuit	Exclusive one-chip of micro- computer LSI circuit.	Power off	Auto shut off saves battery life or manual off by push button.
Display	* 13 mm (0.5") Super large LCD display. * Dual function meter's display.	Sampling Time	Approx. 0.8 sec.
		Operating Humidity	Less than 80% RH.
Measurement	<i>Air velocity :</i> m/s (meters per second), km/h (kilometers per hour), ft/min (feet/per minute), knots (nautical miles per hour), mile/h (miles per hour), <i>Air flow :</i> CMM (m ³ /min.), CFM (ft ³ /min.) <i>Air temperature :</i> °C, °F. <i>Data hold.</i>	Operating Temperature	0°C to 50°C(32°Fto 122°F).
		Data Output	RS 232 PC serial interface.
		Power Supply	Alkaline or heavy duty type DC 9V battery, 006P, MN1604 (PP3) or equivalent.
		Power Current	Approx. DC 8.3 mA.
Memory Recall	Record maximum & minimum reading value with recall.	Weight	381 g/0.84 LB.
		Dimension	Main instrument: 180 x 72 x 32 mm (7.1 x 2.8 x1.3 inch).
		Accessories Included	Sensor head : Round, 72 mm Dia. Instruction manual. 1 PC. Sensor probe.
Sensor Structure	<i>Air velocity & Air flow :</i> Conventional twisted van arm and low friction ball bearing design. <i>Temperature :</i> Thermistor.	Optional Accessories	Software (Windows version, data record & data acquisition). SW-U801-WIN USB cable.....USB-01 RS232 cable.....UPCB-

APPENDIX J

EXPERIMENTAL TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION RESULTS

Table J.1 The temperature distribution at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 400 \text{ W/m}^2$.

	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fl} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fin} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{f2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{Nano} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_b ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_o ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
0.01 kg/s	28	27.4	44.1	39	30.2	32	29	32
0.02 kg/s	27.3	27.1	38.5	34	27.8	29.1	27	29
0.03 kg/s	27	27	35.5	31	27.6	27.9	27	28
0.04 kg/s	27	27	33	29	27.5	27.3	27	27.5
0.05 kg/s	27	27	32.6	28.5	27	27	27	27

Table J.2 The temperature distribution at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fl} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fin} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{f2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{Nano} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_b ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_o ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
0.01 kg/s	31.4	27.8	53.5	44.2	32	35	30	36.6
0.02 kg/s	28	27.1	45.2	39	29.5	33	29	31.3
0.03 kg/s	27.5	27	40	34	28.2	31	28.5	29.5
0.04 kg/s	27.1	27	38.3	32	27.4	30	28.1	28.4
0.05 kg/s	27	27	36.3	31.5	27.1	29.5	27.8	28

Table J.3 The temperature distribution at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 800 \text{ W/m}^2$.

	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fl} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fin} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{f2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{Nano} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_b ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_o ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
0.01 kg/s	34.7	28.2	62.8	50.2	36	39.5	34	40
0.02 kg/s	30.6	27.8	52.1	46	31.2	33.7	31.8	33.7
0.03 kg/s	28.7	27.5	46.1	39	29.7	32.5	31	31.2
0.04 kg/s	27.5	27.1	43	35	29	31.2	30	29.6
0.05 kg/s	27	27	40.3	31	27.7	30	29	28.7

Table J.4 The temperature distribution at various mass flow rates and solar irradiance $I_T = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$.

	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fl} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{fin} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{f2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{Nano} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_b ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_o ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
0.01 kg/s	38.6	29	70	63	38.9	40.7	35	42
0.02 kg/s	32.3	29.2	62	54	33.5	36	32	35
0.03 kg/s	30.3	28.6	51	46	30.5	33	30	32.6
0.04 kg/s	29.1	28.2	47	42	29.3	31	29	30.8
0.05 kg/s	28.1	28	44	38	28.5	30	28	29.7